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Table of Contents

Abstract	4
Introduction	4
Definition of 10 services	4
The EIRENE pillar structure	5
Survey	7
Results	8
Summary statistics	8
Outcomes per service	10
Services in relation to other ESFRIS	35
Next steps	37
Acknowledgements	37
ANNEXES	38
Annex 1	38
Annex 2	41
Annex 3a	48
Annex 3b	57
Annex 4a	67
Annex 5a	76
Annex 5b	79
Annex 5c	80
Annex 6	86
Annex 7	94
Annex 8	97

Abstract

EIRENE RI (Research Infrastructure for Environmental Exposure assessment in Europe) fills the gap in the European infrastructural landscape and pioneers the first EU infrastructure on human exposome (environmental determinants of health). EIRENE PPP aims to prepare the implementation of EIRENE RI as a consolidated European research infrastructure enabling the development of advanced technologies and complementary services on the characterization of complex environmental exposures and their impact on the European population.

In this deliverable, a multi-step procedure resulted in an inventory of the current core services present in Europe on the human exposome.

First, nine service categories were defined by EIRENE work package (WP) 2 and 6 leads. Next, a survey was constructed including questions about the type of services, the capacity, the 5-year outlook (WP2) and Human Resources related questions (WP6). Then, a pilot survey was undertaken in the Netherlands to identify which parties were able to provide which service(s). Finally, based on this pilot, the survey was improved and distributed by each EIRENE National node's representatives to exposome oriented institutes in their country.

Survey responses were compiled and analyzed, and results are summarized in this report. Thus far, 57 parties in 16 countries have indicated to provide services in the nine defined categories of human exposome research. Details regarding the types of service, the current capacity and the outlook of five years of all EIRENE services and relation to other ESFRI's are shared in this document and will form the basis of the roadmap of EIRENE RI services. The Human Resource and Training part will be reported separately (D6.1, D6.2).

Introduction

Work package two (WP2) of EIRENE PPP focuses on the development of specific services. This WP is structured in three main tasks: (i) the core services to be provided by the EIRENE RI will be identified, considering services already provided in other ESFRI RI to avoid duplicities. The identified services are structured in the pillar structure defined in WP1. (ii) the capacity and readiness to offer these services to the user community is assessed, and (iii) rules and procedures for a user's access to such services will be elaborated.

The current deliverable D2.1 links to the first task (i) and regards the list of the EIRENE RI core services according to the pillar structure as described in this report.

Definition of 10 services

Senior scientific staff of UU and Orebro identified and described 10 services in the field of exposure assessment in Europe (Table 1). Previous knowledge of several projects (SIRENE, HBM4EU, EURION, EHEN, PARC) was considered to come to a definition of these services. Detailed questions about the type of services (WP2) and the human resources (WP6) were integrated into an overview. This overview was the basis for a digital survey to assess which parties are able to offer which of the 10 service(s). More detailed description of the services can be found in annex 1.

Table 1 Description of 10 services in the field of Exposure Research Europe.

Nr	Service description
1	Collecting and providing samples (including bio, environmental, and specimen banks) to determine exogenous substances
2	Access to cohort study or survey data on an individual level
3	Measurements of exogenous substances including target and nontargeted measurements of chemical mixtures (or other pollutants) as well as parent and transformation exposure markers in humans and the environment
4	Omics-based analysis of markers of biological response (separate: metabolomics, lipidomics, adductomics, (epi)genomics, metagenomics/microbiomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, phenomics)
5	Quantification/determination of toxicity (human- and ecological), pathways and modes of action (in-vivo, ex-vivo, in-vitro, in-silico)
6	Biostatistical and/or bioinformatics tools and platforms to investigate the exposome and human health interactions
7	Databases and exposure maps on environmental factors (e.g. pollutants, temperature, noise, socio-economic, lifestyle)
8	FAIR cataloging of exposome data (e.g. cohorts, algorithms)
9	Training offerings in the field of exposome research and Training needs*
10	Additional service(s) **

* These outcomes are not part of this deliverable but will be reported under WP6. In the overviews below these are omitted.

** Services that were not listed could be added here.

The EIRENE pillar structure

A sustainable model of EIRENE services has been developed that includes 6 pillars (A-F) divided in 2 categories: 1) Trans National- and 2) Virtual access to Eirene services. Trans National services are comprised of chemical, toxicological and biological profiling. These services can either require a physical infrastructure, typically measurements in a laboratory, or remote access. Virtual services are comprised of environmental data, human data and tools and require a virtual infrastructure, typically online tools, platforms and data storage system and repositories. The services that were defined fit in the pillar structure (Table 2).

The EIRENE pillar structure is depicted in Figure 1, and embeds the services (Table 2).

Figure 1 Pillar structure EIRENE

Table 2 Pillar structure of exposome research, their domains and the 10 EIRENE services classified accordingly.

<u>Pillars</u>		<u>Domains</u>		<u>EIRENE classification services</u>
A	Chem. profiling	Physical and remote access	Laboratory capacities for chemical profiling (selective and non-selective data acquisition)	01. Collecting and providing samples (including bio, environmental, and specimen banks) to determine exogenous substances 03. Measurements of exogenous substances including target and nontargeted measurements of chemical mixtures (or other pollutants) as well as parent and transformation exposure markers in humans and the environment
B	Tox. profiling	Physical and remote access	Laboratory capacities for hazard assessment (non-animal toxicological models to test toxicity of chemicals, their mixtures and environmental samples).	05. Quantification/determination of toxicity (human- and ecological), pathways and modes of action (in-vivo, ex-vivo, in-vitro, in-silico)

C	Biol. profiling	Physical and remote access	Laboratory capacities for biological profiling (elucidating the impact of toxic exposures on health - genomics, epigenomics, metagenomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics).	03. Measurements of exogenous substances including target and nontargeted measurements of chemical mixtures (or other pollutants) as well as parent and transformation exposure markers in humans and the environment 04. Omics-based analysis of markers of biological response (separate: metabolomics, lipidomics, adductomics, (epi)genomics, metagenomics/microbiomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, phenomics)
D	Env. data	Virtual access	Access to data from large-scale/longitudinal environmental (air quality, indoor, water, soil, food, consumer products, etc.) monitoring studies (on-site and remote, including satellite data) for assessing the external exposome.	07. Databases and exposure maps on environmental factors (e.g. pollutants, temperature, noise, socio-economic, lifestyle)
E	Human data	Virtual access	Data and samples from longitudinal population cohorts covering various population groups and cross-sectional studies, health surveys, and clinical studies are invaluable sources of information on population exposure and health.	02. Access to cohort study or survey data on an individual level
F	Tools	Virtual access	Data processing, modeling, and presentation platforms, computational capacities, and tools for federated data analyses, and virtual laboratories and tools	06. Biostatistical and/or bioinformatics tools and platforms to investigate the exposome and human health interactions 08. FAIR cataloging of exposome data (e.g. cohorts, algorithms)

Survey

The online survey was created to be able to systematically assess the services that can be provided within all EU member states. First, a pilot was run in the Netherlands (Sept- Nov 2023). Based on the results the survey was further improved and send to all national node leaders who distributed the survey to their national partners (Dec 2023-Feb 2024). National Node partners were responsible to send it out to their existing and potential partners. The survey was taken by Universities and Institutes, and are referred to as parties in this document. The survey was closed at the end of February and results were send back to each country (to the national node leader) for a check on consistency and uniqueness compared to other ESFRI. This report shows the summarized information of the services from all respondents together.

Results

First the summary statistics of the basic information of the survey will be presented. Then, each service type (1-8 and 10) will be discussed separately. Next, the assessment of the uniqueness in relation to other ESFRI's is presented and discussed. Finally, we summarize next steps towards development of the roadmap.

Summary statistics

Here, all national nodes affiliated to EIRENE PPP distributed and responded to the survey to be able to provide services are reported. Table 3 shows the overview of responses to our survey. A total of 54 parties from 16 countries provided input via the online questionnaire. Five countries did not complete the questionnaire yet; Iceland, Spain, United Kingdom, Portugal and United States.

Table 3 Overview of countries for which information on exposome research services was provided and the number of parties per country that provide those.

Country	# of parties	Country	# of parties
Austria	3	Greece	11
Belgium	5	Italy	3
Cyprus	1	Luxembourg	4
Czech Republic	1	Netherlands	10
Denmark	1	Norway	2
Finland	1	Slovakia	2
France	1	Slovenia	5
Germany	1	Sweden	6

Additional remarks per country:

Austria:	Complete. Yet, in contact with Environmental Agency Austria, who may join.
Belgium:	Partially complete. More parties will be approached of which some may join (e.g University of Hasselt, Universities of Wallonia and Brussels).
Cyprus:	Complete.
Czech Republic:	Complete.
Denmark:	Partially complete.
Finland:	Complete.
France:	Complete.
Germany:	Complete. Services are from one institute, 5 departments each with their own discipline in exposome research. Yet, one other partner may join, the Umweltforschungszentrum.
Greece:	Complete.
Italy:	Complete
Luxembourg:	Complete.
Netherlands:	Complete.
Norway:	Partially complete, missing institutes UiO, NIVA, NINA, NTNU.
Slovakia:	Complete.
Slovenia:	Complete.
Sweden:	Complete.

Figure 2 shows how often the service types are mentioned by all parties across Europe (summary of the 16 countries). Measurements of exogenous substrates is the service mentioned most often, followed by the 5 services: 05 quantification/determination of toxicity, 04 omics based analysis, 01 collecting and providing samples, 02 access to cohort study and

Figure 2 Number of times (n) a type of service was selected. Sum of all 54 institutions.

survey data and 06 biostatistical and/or bioinformatics tools and platforms. Less often, 08 FAIR cataloging of exposome data, databases and exposure maps on environmental factors were mentioned.

Service 9 is not depicted in the figure because this is part of deliverable 6.1. Service 10 were all additional services mentioned (see section 10).

Outcomes per service

01. Collecting and providing samples (including bio, environmental, and specimen banks) to determine exogenous substances

The first service 'Collecting and providing samples for determination of exogenous substances like pollutants and chemicals' has been reported 42 times.

Figure 3 Word cloud of keywords mentioned in relation to service 01 Collecting and providing samples to determine exogenous substances.

Figure 3 shows a word cloud of the keywords mentioned at service 2 'Collecting and providing samples to determine exogenous substances'. Sample collection is mentioned most often. Then biobank was most often mentioned followed by environmental and specimen banks. Other words were mentioned only a few times.

Figure 4 shows the frequency distribution of the number of samples present structured by biobank, environmental- and specimen banks, respectively. Biobanks have in general larger sample sizes than environmental or specimen banks.

Figure 5 shows the expected changes in number of samples and size of storage units in the upcoming 5 years. Of the 42 banks, 20 reported on these changes. Not one bank expects a decrease, whereas 12 expect an increase in the number of storage units and 8 expect to stay the same. For the size of the storage units 9 expect to increase and 11 expect to stay the same. Furthermore, a question was asked about the quality of the biobanks and whether this is expected to decrease, increase or remains equal (stay the same). Of the 19 partners, 11 indicate an increase and 8 indicate this stays the same.

Figure 4 Distribution of number of samples per type of bank. Banks are split in three types; bio-, environmental- and specimen bank.

Figure 5 Expected change in coming 5 years (increase, stay the same, decrease) in number of storage units and size of storage units of banks (all three type of banks).

Overall, it can be concluded that this service will be composed of a large number of banks that will either stay the same or increase on several aspects in the coming 5 years.

02. Access to cohort study or survey data on an individual level

This second service regards access to a collection of cohorts that have specific data collected on an individual level with respect to exposure assessment. This makes the service unique for exposome research. We expect that the number of cohorts will increase in this category since many projects currently running are aimed at linking surface data (exposures) of different fields (environment, build, food, physical chemical) to the cohort data. From the current analysis Figure 6 shows that 67 cohorts are available for exposure assessments. These cohorts are owned by 24 institutes in 10 countries. Figure 7 shows the distribution of the cohorts in relation to the number of participants in the cohorts. This ranges from small (<100 participants) to very high numbers of participants (>100.000) with most cohorts having between 100 and 10.000 individuals. From one cohort the number of participants was not reported.

Figure 6 Number of countries, institutes that provide in total the number of cohorts with linked exposure data.

Figure 7 Distribution of number of individuals in the reported cohorts.

Figure 8 shows the expected changes in access to human health and/or exposure data in the upcoming 5 years. One does not expect changes, 7 probably not, 3 are not sure, 10 expect changes and 3 definitely expect changes. Figure 9 shows which changes are expected. This was asked for all answers given depicted in Figure 8 except “definitely not”. In general, most

cohorts expect positive changes with respect to features of data analysis, integration of new data to existing datasets, new software, number of cohorts and number of surveys. No negative changes were reported.

Details on the type, name and origin of the cohorts can be found in Annex 2.

Figure 8 Expected changes in the access to human health and/or exposure data in the coming 5 years reported by the institutes about their cohorts.

Figure 9 Type of changes in the access to human health and/or exposure data in the upcoming 5 years reported by the institutes about their cohorts.

03. Measurements of exogenous substances including targeted and non-targeted measurements of chemical mixtures (or other pollutants) as well as parent and transformation exposure markers in humans and the environment

Service 3 has been reported 40 times by institutes spanning 15 countries. Figure 10 shows a word cloud of the keywords selected by the service providers.

Figure 10 Word cloud of keywords of service 03 Measurements of exogenous substances including targeted- and non-targeted measurements of chemical mixtures

The national nodes indicated the following three aspects: 1) type of exogenous substrate that can be measured, 2) type of measurement instrument available and 3) the type of specimens that can be analyzed, which are listed in Annex 3. In addition, information on the physical infrastructure is summarized in Annex 3.

Figure 11 shows the distribution of answers to the question whether a change is expected in the upcoming 5 years in their service providing measurement of exogenous substances. The majority of the respondents reported to expect a change. Figure 12 shows that equipment quality and quantity is expected to increase in 2/3 of the cases, and in 1/3 of the cases no changes were reported. None of the respondents expects a negative change. Especially the number of different substrates that can be measured in the future is expected to increase. This has most likely to do with the increasingly sensitivity of the techniques and the available data about exogenous substrates.

Figure 11 Expected changes in the coming 5 years reported by the institutes about service 03 measuring exogenous substrates.

Figure 12 Type of changes in service 03 measurement of exogenous substrates in the coming 5 years reported by the institutes.

Figure 13 The presence of a physical infrastructure was answered with yes or no. In all cases, except one, a physical infrastructure is available for service 03 measuring exogenous substrates.

Figure 13 shows the number of times it was indicated that a physical infrastructure for this service is present. The physical infrastructure was further described in detail (see Annex 3). Figure 14 shows whether a change in physical infrastructure is expected in the coming 5 years. Most parties expect a change (probably yes (19), definitely yes (8)). Some are uncertain (might/might not (7)). The minority does not expect a change (probably not (4), definitely not (2)).

Figure 14 Expected change in the coming 5 years reported by the institutes about infrastructure of service 03 measuring exogenous substrates.

Figure 15 shows the expected change in the coming 5 year in the analysis capacity of measuring exogenous substrates. Most Parties with this service expect indeed to change in the coming 5 years in the analysis capacity. Figure 16 shows what type of change is expected

in the analysis capacity (this question followed for all of the answers in Figure 15 except 'definitely not'). Equipment and expertise tend to increase mostly and are thus the most important reasons why analysis capacity increases. The number of facilities is in most cases expected to stay the same although 4 expect to increase analysis also due to this reason. Personnel either increases or stays the same in a similar ration over the reported services. No decreases are expected for neither of the items.

The fifteen countries indicate they provide this service for a total of 81 different types of measurements (on the level of biological, environmental or other type of samples). Table 4 indicates the distribution of the capacity. The capacity is the number of samples per day that can be run. This capacity most likely reflects the total capacity the facilities have and not per se the free capacity for the purpose of EIRENE services. Whether 5%, 10 % or more will be free for EIRENE in the future remains to be determined and is part of next steps (see below).

Table 4 Amount of samples per day that can be run by the number of partners (n).

Nr of samples run per day	Number (n) of partners providing the service
0-100	58
100-1000	21
1000-10.000	1
>10.000	1

Figure 15 Expected changes in the coming 5 years reported by the institutes about analysis capacity of measuring exogenous substrates.

Figure 16 Type of changes in the analysis capacity of measurement of exogenous substrates in the coming 5 years reported by the institutes.

04. Omics-based analysis of markers of biological response (separate: metabolomics, lipidomics, adductomics, (epi)genomics, metagenomics/microbiomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, phenomics)

Omics-based analysis of markers of biological responses can be provided 29 times. This is a very diverse service using several highly sophisticated techniques on different samples and with different read outs. Full details of all text answers can be found in Annex 4.

Figure 17 Word cloud of keywords mentioned in relation to service 04 Omics-based analysis of markers of biological response.

Figure 17 shows a word cloud of the keywords mentioned in relation to the service 'omics-based analysis of markers of the biological response'. Clearly, metabolomics is the approach mentioned most, followed closely by lipidomics, transcriptomics and proteomics. The other omics techniques were mentioned less. Volatomics was not predefined and is the measurement of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) emitted by a biological system, under specific experimental conditions.

Figure 18 Expected change in the coming 5 years reported by the institutes about omics-based analysis.

Figure 18 shows that most parties do expect changes in the service coming 5 years. Annex 4 shows what types of changes are expected.

Furthermore, 28/29 times it was indicated that a physical infrastructure is present. Annex 4 shows what physical infrastructure are present in these 28 cases.

In this one exception of no infrastructure is was indicated that a tender is launched with an expected infrastructure present in Q3 2024. When operative, the infrastructure will include: liquid chromatograph triple quadrupole vacuum pumps nitrogen generator.

Figure 19 shows that 14/30 Parties do expect changes in the physical infrastructure of the omics services in the coming 5 years. Figure 20 shows what type of change is expected in the infrastructure (this question followed for all the answers in Figure 19 except 'definitely not'). Number of facilities are expected to stay the same in most of the cases (22) or increase (3 cases). Number of tools to perform omics measurements are expected to increase (15) or stay the same (9). Replacement or renewal of the infrastructure is expected to increase (12 cases) or remain the same (in 14 cases).

Figure 19 Expected changes in the coming 5 years reported by the institutes about the physical infrastructure of omics-based analysis.

Figure 20 Type of changes in the omics-based analysis in the coming 5 years reported by the institutes.

Figure 21 Current capacity (samples per year) for omics-based analysis per omics category.

Figure 21 shows the distribution of the reported capacity of samples that can be run per year for the different omics categories. Metabolomics is the most frequently reported omics type. In general, the capacity differs for all omics types, and most common are sample capacities under the 10.000 per year. One lipidomics and one transcriptomics facility reports capacity higher than 10.000 per year. The current capacity most likely reflects the total capacity the facilities have and not per se the free capacity for the purpose of EIRENE services. Whether 5%, 10 % or more will be free for EIRENE in the future remains to be determined and is part of next steps (see below).

Figure 22 Distribution of answers to the question whether changes are expected in the capacity to analyse omics samples in the coming 5 years.

Figure 22 shows that in most cases a change is expected (probably yes 10 cases and definitely yes 5 cases). In 6 cases this is uncertain (might/might not) and in 5 and 3 of the cases 'probably not' or 'definitely not' were answered respectively. The type of changes (for all answers of Figure 21 except when 'definitely not' was answered) are depicted in table 5.

Table 5 Distribution in answers on the question what type of change is expected with respect to number of facilities, number of tools and replacement/renewal of the infrastructure.

Parameter	Answer	Number of partners
Number of facilities	Increase	3
Number of facilities	Stay the same	22
Number of tools	Increase	15
Number of tools	Stay the same	9
Replacement/renewal of infrastructure	Increase	12
Replacement/renewal of infrastructure	Stay the same	14

05. Quantification/determination of toxicity (human- and ecological), pathways and modes of action (in-vivo, ex-vivo, in-vitro, in-silico)

This service includes quantification and/or determination of toxicity of various types of chemicals in human and ecological systems. Also, the pathways and modes of actions involved through in-vivo, ex vivo, in vitro and in silico techniques and model systems are part of this service. In 32 cases this service is provided. Figure 23 shows a word cloud of the keywords. A more detailed description of the services is provided in Annex 5. A wide range of in vitro, in silico, in vivo and ex vivo model systems are described.

Figure 23 Word cloud of keywords that were mentioned in relation to service 5 quantification/determination of toxicity

Figure 24 Distribution of answers on the question whether a change in the service of toxicity measurements is expected in the coming 5 years.

Figure 24 shows whether changes are expected in this type of service. In 4 and 5 cases definitely not and probably not is answered. In 8 cases it is not sure whether there will be changes (might/might not). In 9 cases probably yes is answered and in 5 cases definitely yes. So overall the majority expects changes over the coming 5 years. Annex 4 shows the type of change that are expected to occur. Mostly, changes are reported in the further development of the techniques and in personnel.

In total 31/32 Parties indicated that a physical infrastructure is currently available for this service of toxicity measurements. In this one case that no was entered as an answer, the explanation was that the equipment is not available at the department but present at the institute (TNO/NL). So at institute level it is present. Figure 25 shows whether a change in the infrastructure is expected. The minority does not expect changes (4 definitely not, and 7 probably not), 6 are unsure (might or might not), and the majority expects changes (11 times probably yes and 3 times definitely yes).

Figure 25 Distribution of answers on the question whether a change in physical infrastructure of service 05 is expected in the coming 5 years.

Table 6 shows the answers to the question what changes in physical infrastructure are expected in size and quality. The majority expects an increase in both quality and size.

Table 6 Number of times parties indicated that the quality or size of the infrastructure would decrease, increase or stay the same.

Quality	Increase	16
Quality	Stay the same	8
Quality	Decrease	0
Size	Increase	14
Size	Stay the same	10
Size	Decrease	0

Table 7 shows a detailed description of the available physical infrastructure of service 05 quantification and determination of toxicity. The ranges from specified in vitro high throughput imaging techniques to sophisticated in vivo toxicity models.

Table 7 Description of the available physical infrastructure of service 05 quantification and determination of toxicity.

Fully equipped high-end in vitro toxicological laboratories, also ready for iPS models. [As for any high-end research infrastructure - periodic upgrades will be needed]	Czech Republic
Fully equipped cell culture facility and GC-MS/FID/Fractionation workflow integrated with cell culture analysis. InCell 2200 HTS system for high-throughput imaging.	Sweden

Lab space (150m ²) for ecotox and in vitro tox testing available equipped with standard up to state-of-the-art equipment.	Belgium
Cell culture facility, Live cell imager, flow cytometry, plate reader, barrier function test, microscopy	Belgium
A State of the Art Eposure Facility for human exposure.	Denmark
BSL1 and BSL2 labs with cell culture air flow benches, xCelligence system for cell proliferation and behavior studies, 3D culture systems, Cytof (Helios/Hyperion), Cytex Aurora 5L cell culture lab, biochemical lab,	Germany
Incubator Conviron CPM 6010 Sensomat System (AQUALYTIC@ZN Tintometer GmbH, Germany) Microtox 500 analyzer (Strategic Diagnostics Inc.) 6405 UV/vis spectrophotometer (Jenway, UK) Milli-Q water purification apparatus basic laboratory equipment	Greece
The Unit of Process Control and Informatics (UPCI) owns a network of computing facilities, which is comprised of a network server (4 2.93Ghz processors Intel Xeon, 8MB cache memory, 96 GB RAM, 7 TB disks), a GPU server (NVIDIA Tesla P4 8GB memory+2 CPUS / 64 GB RAM/ 6 TB SSD storage) and several networked PCs linking with the wide range of software, communications and printing services. It will also utilize self developed cheminformatics and material modelling software applications, such as Jaqpot.	Greece
The main computational resources needed for the service will be required for the screening and are be available from two different settings. Specifically, 2 x HP DL 585 AMD 24-core servers, plus 2 custom AMD Ryzen 80-core + 2x 3090 GPU servers can be assigned to this project.	Greece
RNANO has a computing clusters that serves for the development of the in silico models	Greece
The Laboratory of Toxicology is fully equipped with modern analytical instruments for certifications, preliminary examination instruments and preparation instruments for extraction and purification of samples along with implementation of validated bioanalytical methods. For example: • Infrastructure for Q-FISH analysis of telomeres (microscope, hood, cell culture incubator etc.) • Chromatographic systems (LC/MS/MS, LC-MS, GC/MS, GC, HPLC) • Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry system (ICP-MS) • Automated high performance liquid chromatography (TOXIS) • fully automated immunoassay systems analysis ELISA spectrophotometers • Molecular techniques systems (PCR, Capillary Electrophoresis) • System immunofluorescence • Refrigerators for sample preservation All the above instrumentation comes along with supporting lab equipment (i.e., centrifuges, incubators etc.)	Greece
• Microarray Scanner Agilent Technologies SureScanUltra • qPCR AriaMX Agilent Technologies G8830A • Thermal Cycler Agilent Technologies 8800 PCR • Tape station system Agilent Technologies 2200 • Sample concentrator TECHNE FSC496D • Small Prime Centrifuge refrigerated Centurion Scientific K2015R • Semi-Micro Balances Adam Equipment ABL 225 • Class II Biological Safety Chamber Biobase BSC-1300IIB2-X • Deep freezer (-80 oC) of 700 lt for storage of biological samples	Greece
ADME-Tox in 3D assays and services in a 3-tier strategy; in silico, in vitro, in vivo (EMA CHMP, FDA Guidance for Industry) 3D cell microenvironment via profiling of extracellular vesicles/ exosomes -In-house capabilities are coupled with strategic networks and partnerships for discovery, validation and clinical development of biomarkers. -Translational biomarkers (target, mechanism & disease biomarkers) identify the impact of a chemical entity on organs or tissues before a clinical effect is evident. -Diagnostic biomarkers (predictive, prognostic & resistance biomarkers) empower population stratification and enable decisions for potential regulations and/or 26 personalized interventions. -Pharmacodynamic biomarkers used in pre- and post-exposure settings may shed light to the extent of target modulation, provide biological proof-of-activity, and inform decision making.	Greece
Windows and Unix servers	Greece
All cell culture and immunology infrastructure animal facility stem cell culture	Luxembourg
Fully established 100m ² cell culture, exposure equipment, FACS, Luminex,	Luxembourg
Cell culture, C. elegans and zebra fish embryos culture facilities, qPCR, histopathology pipeline, fluorescence microscopes, high throughput staining equipment, incubators at different temperatures.	Netherlands

https://www.kwrwater.nl/en/projecten/effect-based-water-quality-measurements-with-bioassays/	Netherlands
high throughput confocal microscopy infrastructure (4+ systems) - >10 fluorescent reporters - > 5 differentiation protocols for target tissues	Netherlands
High performance computer facility, access to VEGA (national high performance computer cluster)	Slovenia
Cell cultures and cell biology laboratories CO2 incubators, centrifuges, laminar flow hoods, -80°C freezers, Countess automated cell counter (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, USA), RT PCR system 7300, digester, balance, thermomixers, containers for storage of cell lines in liquid nitrogen etc. Fluorescent microscopy Fluorescent microscope (Nikon Eclipse 8000; Nikon Eclipse Ti), Fluorescent inverted microscope (Olympus IX70) and Microscope Olympus CKX41 and Olympus Provis AX70 fluorescence microscope (Olympus, Tokyo, Japan), EVOS7000 Imaging System-fully automated microscope for fluorescent and colorimetric image acquisition and large data processing, Metafer Metasystems (Scanning and Imaging Platform) all equipped with hardware and software for image analysis. Confocal microscopy Confocal microscopes: Leica TCS SP5 laser scanning confocal microscope mounted on a Leica DMI 6000 CS inverted microscope and confocal microscope Leica SP8 TCS with light-sheet microscopy module. All equipped with hardware and software for image analysis. Flow cytometry, spectrofluorimetry and luminometry MACSQuant analyser 10 flow cytometer (Miltenyi Biotech, Germany), spectral flow cytometer Cytek Aurora (Cytek Biosciences, Fremont, USA). Equipped with software for data analysis. Spectrofluorimetry and luminometry Spectrophotometer SynergyMx, (BioTek (Agilent), USA) and Spectrophotometer NanoDrop, Cytation 5 Cell Imaging Multi-Mode Reader (BioTek (Agilent), USA), and Luminometer Synergy HTX (BioTek (Agilent), USA).	Slovenia
Facility for Zebrafish studies. The zebrafish methods investigate embryotoxic effects according to OECD guideline 236, molecular changes on the transcriptome, behavioral alterations, and morphological changes using high-throughput image analyses and the video tracking software EthoVision®. The earthworm tests investigate uptake and effects, including reproduction and mortality (OECD 11268).	Sweden
Sample preparation, MS analysis of the samples, and data analysis and quantification.	Sweden
laboratories and exposure facilities	Sweden
Computational platforms including HPC2N	Sweden

Nine countries have indicated for their services (total of 43, so on average ~5 per country) the capacity in samples per year.

Table 8 shows what capacity is currently available. This capacity most likely reflects the total capacity the facilities have and not per se the free capacity for the purpose of EIRENE services. Whether 5%, 10 % or more will be free for EIRENE in the future remains to be determined and is part of next steps (see below).

Table 8 Capacity in samples per year of service 05 Toxicity measurements.

Capacity Samples per year	Number (n) of partners providing the service
0-1000	35
1000-10.000	7
10.000-100.000	0
100.000- 1.000.000	1

Figure 26 shows whether changes in capacity are expected in the coming 5 years. Ten parties do not expect changes (definitely no (2), probably no (8)), eight are uncertain (might or might not) and nine do expect changes (probably yes (7), definitely yes (2)). Figure 27 shows the type of changes that are expected in quality and size of the capacity.

Figure 26 Distribution of answers to the question whether a change in capacity of service 05 is expected in the coming 5 years.

Figure 27 Type of changes that are expected in the capacity of service 05 Toxicity measurements.

06. Biostatistical and/or bioinformatics tools and platforms to investigate the exposome and human health interactions

Service 06 covers biostatistical and/or bioinformatics tools and platforms to investigate the exposome and human health interactions in exposome research. This service is provided by 27 parties. Annex 6 shows information about the service including a description of biostatistical- and bioinformatic pipelines available, type of data (e.g. epigenetics, transcriptomics, metabolomics), type of analysis, type of methodology, type of tools and platforms.

Figure 28 shows a word cloud of the keywords mentioned for service 06. Data analysis tools are mentioned most often, followed by machine learning and data integration.

Figure 28 Word cloud of keywords related to service 06 biostatistical and/or bioinformatics tools and platforms.

Figure 29 shows the distribution of answers to the question whether changes are expected in the described service in the coming 5 years. Most parties expect a change (probably yes (4), definitely yes (9)). Four are uncertain (might or might not), and ~30% does not expect a change (definitely not (4), probably not (4)). What type of changes that are expected are described in Annex 6. Most mentioned are further development of the biostatistical and bioinformatic tools among which specific methodology and increase in personnel.

Figure 29 Distribution of answers to the question whether a change in service 06 is expected in the coming 5 years.

Figure 30 shows the distribution of answers to the question whether the processing capacity for biostatistics/bioinformatics are expected to change in the coming 5 years. Around 65% of the parties expect a change (probably yes (11), definitely yes (6)). Around 10% is uncertain (might or might not), and around 25% does not expect a change (definitely not (4), probably not (3)).

Figure 30 Distribution of answers to the question whether a change in processing capacity of biostatistics/bioinformatics is expected in the coming 5 years.

The answers to the question what type of changes in processing capacity will occur are depicted in Figure 31. Most parties expect an increase in quality (16) and size (16) of the processing capacity, a minority expects the quality (5) and size (4) remain the same, and a single partner expects a decrease.

Figure 31 Distribution of answers to the question what type of change is expected with respect to the quality and size of the processing capacity of Biostatistical and bioinformatic tools.

07. Databases and exposure maps on environmental factors (e.g. pollutants, temperature, noise, socio-economic, lifestyle)

Service 07 entails the databases and exposure maps on environmental factors. Annex 7 shows the description of the service including the type of environmental factor available, type of maps (incl. geographical area (e.g. region, country, EU wide, etc.)), and type of platforms used. A wide variety of exposure maps on diverse environmental factors are available.

Figure 32 Word cloud of keywords mentioned in relation to databases and exposure maps on environmental factors.

Figure 32 shows a word cloud of service 07 Databases and exposure maps on environmental factors. Data that are publicly available, and from all areas (Regional, National and International are mentioned equally often). Diverse types of maps are available (e.g. atmospheric, aquatics, chemical).

Figure 33 shows the answers to the questions whether changes are expected in the databases and exposure maps on environmental factors. Most parties indicate to expect a change (probably yes (9), definitely yes (4)) whereas a few are uncertain (might or might not (3)) and one answered probably not. The type of changes that are foreseen can be found in Annex 7. Most prominent changes are expected in enlarging databases and exposure maps, improving access of the available tools.

Figure 33 Distribution of answers to the question whether changes are expected in service 07 databases and exposure maps on environmental factors.

08. FAIR cataloguing of exposome data (e.g. cohorts, algorithms)

Service 08 aims to make exposome data FAIR: findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. The processes, systems and/or tools that facilitates to make data FAIR is offered by 14 parties in 7 countries.

Figure 34 shows a word cloud of Service 8.

Figure 34 Word cloud of keywords mentioned in relation to service 08 FAIR cataloguing.

In Annex 8, the parties provided their description of their services offered in this category. Figure 35 indicates the expected changes in this service. The majority of parties expect a change (probably yes (4), definitely yes (5)). Only 3 partners indicated to be uncertain of this (might/might not (3)). The types of changes that are provided in Annex 8.

Figure 35 Distribution in answers to the question whether a change in service 08 FAIR cataloguing is expected.

09. Training offerings in the field of exposome research and Training needs

This is reported in WP6 deliverable.

10. Additional Services

Twelve additional services have been reported. These are described in the Table 9 below. Roughly these can be clustered as follows:

- Modeling Additional Services 3,5,7,8
- Advanced Exposomics Additional Service 1
- Communication & Dissemination Additional Service 10,11
- Other Additional Service 2,4,6,12.

Whether 'Modeling' and 'Advanced Exposomics' are very different services and need a unique service description remains to be determined. Modeling could fit under service 6 'Biostatistical and/or bioinformatics tools and platforms to investigate the exposome and human health interactions'. Advanced exposomics (table 9, nr 1) and expertise in chromatography (table 9, nr 4) could fit under service 3 'Measurements of exogenous substances including target and nontargeted measurements of chemical mixtures (or other pollutants) as well as parent and transformation exposure markers in humans and the environment'.

Waste-water based measurements (table 9, nr 6) could fall under category 7 'Databases and exposure maps on environmental factors (e.g. pollutants, temperature, noise, socio-economic, lifestyle)'.

Table 9, nr 12 'Knowledge on and experience with federated data analyses, incl relevant ethics and privacy considerations' could fall under ESFRI ELIXIR.

Table 9 Additional services mentioned under category 10.

Country	nr	Description Additional Services
Austria	1	Advanced/customized data analysis for exposomics Includes suspect screening of substances of interest as well as non-targeted data analysis. In addition, Level 1 identification for 200+ relevant xenobiotics with quantitative data is also provided Types of exogenous substance: Non-targeted/Suspect screening of xenobiotics. Level 1 identification for more than 200+ compounds, including plasticizers, mycoestrogens and metabolites, perfluorinated alkylated substances, industrial side products, veterinary drugs and pesticides, phytoestrogens and metabolites, phytotoxins, polyphenols, personal care product ingredients/pharmaceuticals and metabolites, disinfection by-products, food by-processing products and air pollutants.
Belgium	2	Electrosensitivity tests_(ENVI-EHS)
	3	Modelling environmental resources: Assessing flood risk, air & water quality, soil quality, geological conditions and risks, accessibility and availability of (urban) green environments and climate change conditions (heat maps, storms, droughts).
	4	Expertise in sample pretreatment, analysis and data processing of chromatographic devices.
Greece	5	Development of Physiologically Based Kinetic (PBK) models PBK models utilize mathematical representations of physiological processes to estimate how chemical compounds are absorbed, distributed, metabolized, and eliminated within the body. PBK models can provide valuable insights into various endpoints, including but not limited to the prediction of systemic exposure levels, tissue-specific concentrations, and the identification of potential metabolites. Additionally, PBK models can be employed to estimate internal doses at target organs, helping to assess the risk posed by chemical exposures and contributing to regulatory decisions related to safety and risk assessment. Type of substances: chemicals, mixtures, complex materials (nanomaterials)

		Other info: The models are available as user-friendly web services through our Jaqpot platform. They can be accessed via API calls in various environments, integrated with other models, and seamlessly incorporated into risk assessment workflows.
	6	Indirect measurements of exposure in the population through wastewater-based epidemiology (WBE)
	7	PBPK and advanced AI models are also developed in the AUTH. PBPK models are used for the estimation of internal doses after exposure incidents. The generic model was originally developed in CSL code and has been completely converted to R code. The model can estimate the impact of exposure in almost all human organs including, GI tract, lungs, muscles, bones, heart, kidneys, liver, skin, blood, etc.
		Non-linear dynamics modelling of HR fluctuations and AFib detection/prediction in correlation with drug prescription and administration as well as drug toxicity
	8	Modeling the potential routes of pollutants in water resources through soil, based on information about the soil composition and structure and pollutant measurements to evaluate the severity of pollution, interpret the spreading rate and propose/invent ways to avoid spreading it to other locations.
Netherlands	9	High throughput Effect-Directed Analysis: use of microfraction collector (FractioMate).
	10	Evaluate for different groups of people (citizen and stakeholder perspectives) the (potential) risk perception and acceptance of the actual human health risks concerning (i) specific exposure pathways and (ii) exposomes. It is also possible to develop future scenarios for public perception and trust.
	11	Design suitable strategies for communicating about the relative importance of specific exposure pathways within the exposome, tailored to different groups of people (citizen and stakeholder perspectives). E.g. how can transparency about the exposome be used effectively to increase public perception (of the risks), acceptance (of the problem), and confidence (in the solutions)?
	12	Knowledge on and experience with federated data analyses, incl relevant ethics and privacy considerations

Services in relation to other ESFRIS

To be able to understand whether the countries have a complete list of services, unique services in their country and in Europe in relation to other ESFRIS, and have had interactions with stakeholders, the countries were asked to indicate the following:

Whether the list of services for EIRENE Europe is complete for your country? y/n

If not, please indicate which institute is still missing (this may be added in a later stage)

Whether the services for EIRENE in your country are unique for your country and not provided by another ESFRIS in your country.

Yes, partially, no (choose one answer). Please explain your answer.

Whether the services for EIRENE in your country are unique for Europe and not provided by another ESFRIS in Europe

Yes, partially, no, don't know (choose one answer). Please explain your answer.

Whether you have consulted stakeholders in your country to discuss the service list. Please comment and summarize the outcome here.

Table 10 summarizes the output of this questionnaire. Most of the countries indicate that the list of services they provide are complete. Furthermore, most of the countries indicate that their services are unique for the country. Whether this also is true on European level is for many of the countries not known or unsure. Roughly half of the country has already involved stakeholders.

Table 10 Outcome of the survey on the comparison of the offered services in relation to 1) completeness, 2) uniqueness in own country, 3) uniqueness in Europe and 4) stakeholder engagement. Green=yes, orange=partially, red=no, yellow is unknown/unsure.

	1	2	3	4
	Is the list of services complete for your country?	Are the services for EIRENE in your country unique for your country (and not provided by another ESFRI in your country)	Are the services for EIRENE in your country unique for Europe and not provided by another ESFRI in Europe	Were stakeholders consulted to discuss the service list?
Austria	Green	Green	Orange	Orange
Belgium	Orange	Yellow	Yellow	Red
Cyprus	Green	Green	Yellow	Green
Czech Republic	Green	Green	Green	Green
Denmark	Orange	Orange	Orange	Green
Finland	Green	Yellow	Red	Red
France	Green	Green	Yellow	Green
Germany	Green	Red	Red	Green
Greece	Green	Green	Green	Green
Italy	Green	Green	Green	Red
Luxembourg	Green	Green	Orange	Green
Netherlands	Green	Green	Orange	Green
Norway	Orange	Green	Orange	Red
Slovakia	Green	Green	Yellow	Red
Slovenia	Green	Green	Yellow	Red
Sweden	Green	Orange	Yellow	Green

Next steps

This survey will be used as input for further discussions and decisions that must be made to come to a roadmap for the development of EIRENE RI services (deliverable 2.2). Indeed, it serves as input to identify synergies and gaps in the landscape of existing ESFRIs, to make sure the provided services of EIRENE are unique and synergistic to existing research infrastructures.

Concrete actions that will start:

1. Addition of services by national nodes that have not provided input yet;
2. Discuss outcome of the questionnaire with the consortium;
3. Discussion whether current categorization is sufficiently or overly detailed;
4. Critical analysis whether provided services are unique to EIRENE (especially needed in the European context);
5. Critical analysis whether reported capacity is realistic.

EIRENE as a new research infrastructure will promote European excellence in Environmental & Health research by providing European researchers with transnational and/or virtual access to harmonized capacities, unique services, and comprehensive data addressing the current and future needs of public authorities. The current deliverable contributes to this ultimate goal.

Acknowledgements

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ANNEXES

Annex 1 Description of Services

Service 1 Collecting and providing samples (including bio, environmental, and specimen banks) to determine exogenous substances

Explanation Presence of biobanks, environmental banks and specimen banks as well as services for sample collection.

Describe the services your institution currently offers regarding service 1. The collection and provision of samples (including bio, environmental, and specimen banks) to determine exogenous substances.

Service 2 Access to human health and/or exposure data

The following questions are regarding the institute's access to cohort study or survey data on an individual level. It concerns the available cohort studies (either individual cohorts or existing cohort infrastructures) that are enriched with exposure data available at your institute.

Service 3 Measurements of exogenous substances including targeted- and non-targeted measurements of chemical mixtures (or other pollutants) as well as parent and transformation exposure markers in humans and the environment

Explanation For each service offered, please specify whether environmental samples, biological specimens, or both can be handled and in which matrices.

Information that was requested in the survey:

Type exogenous substance: Non-targeted/Suspect screening of xenobiotics (include list of xenobiotics, this can be at group level, e.g. food additives, drugs)

Type of measurement: LC-HRMS with semi-quantitative results.

Biological specimens/matrices: urine, serum, plasma, breast milk, placenta.

Service 4 Omics-based analysis of markers of biological response (separate: metabolomics, lipidomics, adductomics, (epi)genomics, metagenomics/microbiomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, phenomics).

Explanation For each service offered, please describe the type of matrices employed as well as the "omics" applied.

Information that was requested in the survey:

Type of omics: LC-MS/MS proteomics

Matrices: plasma, in vitro samples

Markers: both targeted as untargeted proteins (specify if possible)

Other info: e.g. qualitative and quantitative, type of equipment

Service 5 Quantification/determination of toxicity (human- and ecological), pathways and modes of action (in-vivo, ex-vivo, in-vitro, in-silico)

Explanation for each service offered, please include if it is in vivo, ex-vivo, in vitro, or in silico.

Information that was requested in the survey:

In vitro assessment - Safety and preclinical testing

Type of models: in vitro organ specific cell models, 2D/3D organoids of liver/hepatotoxicity, gut and skin epithelia, kidney, reprotoxicity - testicular models.

Type of samples: chemicals, mixtures, matrices (please specify further)

Mechanistic endpoints: nuclear receptor reporter gene assays, cell proliferation, tumor promotion and progression.

Other info: e.g. certifications, specific and/or unique equipment.

Service 6 Biostatistical and/or bioinformatics tools and platforms to investigate the exposome and human health interactions

Information that was requested in the survey:

Include description of biostatistical- and bioinformatic pipelines available, including type of data (e.g. epigenetics, transcriptomics, metabolomics), type of analysis, type of methodology, type of tools and platforms.

Service 7 Databases and exposure maps on environmental factors (e.g. pollutants, temperature, noise, socio-economic, life style)

Explanation For each database and/or exposure maps indicate the geographic area (e.g. region, country, EU wide etc) for which this is provided, type of environmental factor.

Information that was requested in the survey:

Include type of environmental factor available, type of maps (incl geographical area (e.g. region, country, EU wide, etc)), type of platforms used.

Service 8 FAIR cataloging of exposome data (e.g. cohorts, algorithms)

Explanation Services that aim to make exposome data FAIR: findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.

Information that was requested in the survey:

Describe processes, systems and/or tools that makes your data FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable).

Service 9 Training offerings part of WP 6, not part of WP2

Explanation Training offerings are training/education modules that you can offer to the EIRENE Infrastructure. These are focused on, or highly related to, the services you filled in this survey thus far. Also, they can be diverse e.g., academic courses and programmes, summer schools, tailored trainings, workshops.

Service 10

Additional service(s)

Information that was requested in the survey:

Describe any additional service(s) currently offered at your institute that have not yet been mentioned in sections 1-9

Annex 2 Description of Cohorts (service 2)

country	Department.and.unit.(if.applicable)	University/Institute	cohort	keywords	Number of individuals
Czech Republic	RECETOX - CELSPAC Infrastructure	Masaryk University, the Czech Republic	CELSPAC: TNG	Survey data,Cohort samples,Birth cohort	1.000-10.000
Czech Republic	RECETOX - CELSPAC Infrastructure	Masaryk University, the Czech Republic	CELSPAC: YA	Survey data,Cohort samples, Matured birth cohort	100-1.000
Czech Republic	RECETOX - CELSPAC Infrastructure	Masaryk University, the Czech Republic	PROSECO		10.000-100.000
Czech Republic	RECETOX - CELSPAC Infrastructure	Masaryk University, the Czech Republic	HAPIEE	Survey data,Cohort samples,Adult cohort,General population cohort	1.000-10.000
Czech Republic	RECETOX - CELSPAC Infrastructure	Masaryk University, the Czech Republic	ELSPAC	Survey data,General population cohort,Birth cohort	1.000-10.000
Germany	Medical Faculty	Leipzig University	LIFE Child	Survey data,Cohort samples,General population cohort,Birth cohort	1.000-10.000
Belgium	Environment health unit	ISSeP : Institut Scientifique de Service Public (Scientific Institute of Public Service)	BMH-WAL 1/2/3	Survey data,Cohort samples,Adult cohort,General population cohort,Birth cohort,Another, namely	1.000-10.000
Belgium	Environment health unit	ISSeP : Institut Scientifique de Service Public (Scientific Institute of Public Service)	BIOBRO	Survey data,Cohort samples,General population cohort	100-1.000
Belgium	Environment health unit	ISSeP : Institut Scientifique de Service Public (Scientific Institute of Public Service)	BMH-PFAS		1.000-10.000
Slovakia	Department of Environmental Medicine, Faculty of Public Health	Slovak Medical University in Bratislava	PCB cohort	Cohort samples,Birth cohort	100-1.000
Norway	Food safety	NIPH	The Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort (MoBa) study	Cohort samples,General population cohort,Birth cohort	>100.000
Norway	Food safety	NIPH	The Norwegian Environmental Biobank,	Survey data,Cohort samples,Adult cohort	1.000-10.000
Norway	Food safety	NIPH	MoBa sub studies Helix and Athlete		100-1.000
Norway	Food safety	NIPH	MoBa sub studies Helix and Athlete		<100

Slovenia	Department of Environmental Sciences	Jožef Stefan Institute	PHIME	Survey data, Cohort samples, Birth cohort	100-1.000
Slovenia	Department of Environmental Sciences	Jožef Stefan Institute	HEALS/EXES	Birth cohort	100-1.000
Slovenia	Department of Environmental Sciences	Jožef Stefan Institute	National HBM I		100-1.000
Slovenia	Department of Environmental Sciences	Jožef Stefan Institute	National HBM II	Survey data, Children and adolescence	1.000-10.000
Slovenia	Department of public health	University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Medicine	Children (7 years old) and adolescents (12 years old)	Survey data	1.000-10.000
Slovenia	Department of public health	University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Medicine	Adolescents (13 years old; 15 and 17 years old)	Survey data	1.000-10.000
Belgium	Environmental Intelligence	VITO	FLEHS	Survey data, Cohort samples, Adult cohort, General population cohort, Birth cohort, Another, namely, adolescent, children	1.000-10.000
Belgium	Environmental Intelligence	VITO	3xG	Survey data, Cohort samples, Birth cohort, pregnant women	100-1.000
Belgium	Department of Bio-analysis at the faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences	Ghent University, Belgium.	GLORIA-Gezondheidsmonitor	Survey data, Cohort samples, Adult cohort, General population cohort	10.000-100.000
Belgium	Department of Bio-analysis at the faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences	Ghent University, Belgium.	FLEXiGUT	Survey data, Cohort samples, Adult cohort, General population cohort, Birth cohort	100-1.000
Greece	Atmospheric Chemistry and Innovative Technologies Laboratory/INRASTES	NCSR DEMOKRITOS	The RHEA study (mother-child cohort in Crete, Greece)	Adult cohort, Birth cohort	100-1.000
Greece	Atmospheric Chemistry and Innovative Technologies Laboratory/INRASTES	NCSR DEMOKRITOS	LED-FERTYL cohort in Spain	Adult cohort, Birth cohort	100-1.000
Greece	Atmospheric Chemistry and Innovative Technologies Laboratory/INRASTES	NCSR DEMOKRITOS	PREDIMED cohort in Spain		100-1.000
Luxembourg	Environmental Research and Innovation (ERIN) Department	LIST	DEMOCOPHES LU	Mother children	100-1.000
Greece	Laboratory of Toxicology, Medical School	University of Crete (UOC)	Athletes integrated wellness	Cohort samples, Adult cohort, General population cohort	<100
Greece	Laboratory of Toxicology, Medical School	University of Crete (UOC)	Middle-aged integrated well-ness	Cohort samples, Adult cohort, General	<100

				population cohort	
Greece	Laboratory of Toxicology, Medical School	University of Crete (UOC)	Telomerase activation study		<100
Greece	Laboratory of Toxicology, Medical School	University of Crete (UOC)	Endocrine disruptors assessment in hair samples	Cohort samples, Adult cohort, General population cohort	<100
Slovakia	1. Faculty of Natural Sciences 2. University Science Park	Comenius University in Bratislava	General adults - DINCH metabolites in urine, Survey study	Survey data, Cohort samples, Adult cohort, General population cohort	100-1.000
Slovakia	1. Faculty of Natural Sciences 2. University Science Park	Comenius University in Bratislava	Newborns - DINCH metabolites in meconium and urine	Survey data, Birth cohort	<100
Slovakia	1. Faculty of Natural Sciences 2. University Science Park	Comenius University in Bratislava	Breast milk - DINCH metabolites	Survey data	<100
Greece	HERACLES Research Center on the Exposome and Health, Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki / Technologies Division, Environmental Engineering Laboratory, and, General Chemical Technology Laboratory, Department of Chemical Engineering Aristotle University of Thessaloniki/ 2nd Dept of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, School of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	EXHES	Birth cohort	1.000-10.000
Greece	HERACLES Research Center on the Exposome and Health, Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki / Technologies Division, Environmental Engineering Laboratory, and, General Chemical Technology Laboratory, Department of Chemical Engineering Aristotle University of Thessaloniki/ 2nd Dept of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, School of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	HBM4EU-MOM	General population cohort	100-1.000

Greece	HERACLES Research Center on the Exposome and Health, Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki / Technologies Division, Environmental Engineering Laboratory, and, General Chemical Technology Laboratory, Department of Chemical Engineering Aristotle University of Thessaloniki/ 2nd Dept of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, School of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	CROME & HERACLES (Exposome & Health)		1.000-10.000
Greece	HERACLES Research Center on the Exposome and Health, Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki / Technologies Division, Environmental Engineering Laboratory, and, General Chemical Technology Laboratory, Department of Chemical Engineering Aristotle University of Thessaloniki/ 2nd Dept of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, School of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	ICARUS	General population cohort	100-1.000
Greece	HERACLES Research Center on the Exposome and Health, Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki / Technologies Division, Environmental Engineering Laboratory, and, General Chemical Technology Laboratory, Department of Chemical Engineering Aristotle University of Thessaloniki/ 2nd Dept of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, School of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	URBANOME	General population cohort	1.000-10.000

Greece	HERACLES Research Center on the Exposome and Health, Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki / Technologies Division, Environmental Engineering Laboratory, and, General Chemical Technology Laboratory, Department of Chemical Engineering Aristotle University of Thessaloniki/ 2nd Dept of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, School of Medicine, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	PARC Waste Study	Occupational cohort	100-1.000
Greece	not applicable	National Hellenic Research Foundation (NHRF)	Cohort-based field studies	Cohort samples, Clinical cohort	1.000-10.000
Greece	not applicable	National Hellenic Research Foundation (NHRF)	EXHES	Birth cohort	100-1.000
Greece	not applicable	National Hellenic Research Foundation (NHRF)	URBANOME		1.000-10.000
Greece	Institute of Chemical Engineering Sciences (ICE-HT)	Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas (FORTH)	Blood Serum from mothers and umbilical cord (from male offspring) from pesticide-heavy regions (Thessaly vs Athens) - in collaboration with Profs George Mastorakos (Professor, Medical School, NKUA) and Maria Papagianni (Assistant Professor, School of Physical Education, Sport Science and Dietetics, University of Thessaly) - for investigation of pesticides as endocrine disruptors	Cohort samples, General population cohort, Mother and umbilical cohort	100-1.000
Greece	Department of Neurology, Aiginition University Hospital	Medical School, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens	National Network for Research of Neurodegenerative Diseases on the basis of Medical Precision (EDIAN) including patients with rare dementias (early onset and atypical cases)	Clinical cohort	100-1.000

Greece	Department of Neurology, Aiginition University Hospital	Medical School, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens	Cohort of patients with Dementia of any degenerative type and age of onset	Clinical cohort	100-1.000
Denmark	Public Health, Unit of Environment, Occupation and Health	Aarhus University, Faculty of Health	The Danish population	General population cohort	>100.000
Denmark	Public Health, Unit of Environment, Occupation and Health	Aarhus University, Faculty of Health	The Danish Blood Donor Study (DBDS)	Cohort samples, General population cohort	>100.000
Denmark	Public Health, Unit of Environment, Occupation and Health	Aarhus University, Faculty of Health	Danish National Birth Cohort (DNBC)		>100.000
Denmark	Public Health, Unit of Environment, Occupation and Health	Aarhus University, Faculty of Health	The Danish Twin Registry	Cohort samples	>100.000
Germany	Chemicals in the Environment (CITE), 1 Cell Toxicology, 2 Ecotoxicology, 3 Exposure Science, 4 Molecular Toxicology, 5 Environmental Immunology	Helmholtz-Center for Environmental Research (UFZ)	LINA and LISA cohort	Survey data, Cohort samples, Mother-child cohort	100-1.000
Germany	Chemicals in the Environment (CITE), 1 Cell Toxicology, 2 Ecotoxicology, 3 Exposure Science, 4 Molecular Toxicology, 5 Environmental Immunology	Helmholtz-Center for Environmental Research (UFZ)	X Name of Study ____ Placenta collection (1st and 3rd trimester)		
The Netherlands	RAPID	TNO	Cohort study on sustainable employability (CODI)	Survey data, Adult cohort, General population cohort, Occupational	10.000-100.000
The Netherlands	RAPID	TNO	NEA longi	Survey data, Adult cohort, occupational information	10.000-100.000
The Netherlands	RAPID	TNO	Study on Musculoskeletal disorders, Absenteeism, Stress and Health (SMASH)		1.000-10.000
The Netherlands	RAPID	TNO	Study on Transitions in Employment, Ability and Motivation (STREAM)	Survey data, Adult cohort, occupational information	1.000-10.000
The Netherlands	Donor Studies	Sanquin Blood Supply Foundation	Sanquin Future Health	Adult cohort, we will follow these individuals longitudinally	100-1.000
The Netherlands	IRAS One Health chemical	Utrecht University	PIAMA	Survey data, Cohort samples, Birth cohort, matured birth cohort	1.000-10.000

The Netherlands	IRAS One Health chemical	Utrecht University	AMIGO	Survey data, Adult cohort, General population cohort, Occupational and Environmental Health Prospective Cohort Study	10.000-100.000
The Netherlands	IRAS One Health chemical	Utrecht University	EPIC-NL		10.000-100.000
The Netherlands	IRAS One Health chemical	Utrecht University	Nightingale	Survey data, Cohort samples, Adult cohort, Shift work cohort	10.000-100.000
The Netherlands	IRAS One Health chemical	Utrecht University	Dutch Panel study	Survey data, Cohort samples, Adult cohort, General population cohort	100-1.000
The Netherlands	EDS	Amsterdam UMC, Location VUMC	Hoorn studies	General population cohort	1.000-10.000
The Netherlands	EDS	Amsterdam UMC, Location VUMC	Diabetes Care system cohort	Clinical cohort	10.000-100.000
The Netherlands	EDS	Amsterdam UMC, Location VUMC	Hoorn Meal study		<100
The Netherlands	Dept Genetics	University Medical Center Groningen	LifeLines	Survey data, Cohort samples, General population cohort	>100.000

Annex 3a Specification of Service 03 and description of infrastructure

Specifications of the Service	Description of physical infrastructure Service 03 measurement of exogenous substances	Country
<p>Non-targeted analysis Types of exogenous substance: Non-targeted/Suspect screening of xenobiotics. Level 1 identification for 100+ compounds, including plasticizers, mycoestrogens and metabolites, perfluorinated alkylated substances, industrial side products, veterinary drugs and pesticides, phytoestrogens and metabolites, phytotoxins, personal care product ingredients/pharmaceuticals and metabolites, disinfection by-products, food by-processing products and air pollutants</p> <p>Type of measurement: LC-HRMS with both relative and (if requested) absolute quantitation. Biological matrices: serum, plasma, urine and breast milk.</p>	<p>Agilent 1290 Infinity II Liquid Chromatography System SCIEX ZenoTOF 7600</p>	<p>Austria</p>
<p>Inorganic analysis Absolute quantification of multiple elements (metals, metalloids, non-metals) in biological and environmental samples by state-of-the-art inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry, in a clean room environment. Sample preparation for multi-element analysis (heating block or microwave-assisted acid digestion) of biological and environmental samples, in a clean room environment.</p>	<p>3 ICP-MS_instruments microwave, heating block, clean room HPLC for flow injection and speciation analysis</p>	<p>Austria</p>
<p>Targeted analysis Multi-class biomonitoring (targeted for more than 80 analytes) Types of exogenous substance: plasticizers, mycoestrogens and metabolites, perfluorinated alkylated substances, industrial side products and pesticides, phytoestrogens and metabolites, phytotoxins, personal care product ingredients/pharmaceuticals and metabolites, disinfection by-products, food processing by-products and air pollutants</p> <p>Type of measurement: Validated LC-MS (low resolution) with quantitative results. Biological matrices: serum, plasma, urine and breast milk.</p> <p>Additional comment: the method has been published (https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-30204-y)</p>	<p>Service 1. Multi-class biomonitoring (targeted for more than 80 analytes) Agilent 1290 Infinity II Liquid Chromatography System SCIEX QTRAP 6500</p>	<p>Austria</p>
<p>The Core Facility Metabolomics of the Medical University of Innsbruck offers access to state-of-the-art targeted/non-targeted/suspect screening workflows employing liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS).</p> <p>LC-high-resolution MS/MS analysis generates a comprehensive overview on the chemical composition of biological and environmental samples. Targeted LC-MS/MS is used for quantitative analysis.</p> <p>Type of exogenous substances: (1) Non-targeted/Suspect screening of xenobiotics, including illicit drugs, pharmaceuticals, environmental pollutants, industrial chemicals, pesticides, personal care products, and metabolites thereof. (2) Targeted/quantitative analysis of xenobiotics, including illicit drugs, pharmaceuticals, environmental pollutants (e.g., PFAS, bisphenols) and metabolites thereof</p> <p>Type of measurement: (1) LC-HRMS/MS with semiquantitative results. (2) LC-MS/MS with quantitative results.</p> <p>Biological specimens/matrices: serum, plasma, urine, saliva, tissue, cell culture. Environmental specimens/matrices: water including wastewater</p>	<p>The primary mission of the Core Facility Metabolomics of the Medical University of Innsbruck is to serve as an enabling resource for research and development programs at local, national and international level. The Core Facility Metabolomics is equipped with two HR-MS instruments (Orbitrap Exploris 240, Thermo; TripleToF 5600+, Sciex) and two low-resolution MS instruments (QTrap 6500+, Sciex, Xevo TQ-XS, Waters). All necessary devices for processing biological and environmental samples are available.</p>	<p>Austria</p>
<p>Target suspect and non-target analysis of biological (mostly human, but also animal) and environmental samples (not food). Techniques: * TIMS-TOF High Resolution MS and Orbitrap HR MS (coupled to UPLC or direct analysis-DART) * UPLC- QqQ MS * General sample preparation and chromatographic tools available</p>	<p>ISSeP has laboratories for the analysis of exogenous substances and compounds present in the environment (water, air, soil, dust, materials, biota). There is no infrastructure for carrying out analysis of exogenous compounds in biological matrices. These analyzes are carried out in partner laboratories. Different spectrometers (ICP AES, ICP MS, LC MS, GC MS) ionic chromatography, micro organism enumeration, PCR, Yes and Yas assay, ecotox assays (algae, daphnia,</p>	<p>Belgium</p>

	fish, invertebrates)	
LC-MS/MS and LC-HRMS analysis to detect mycotoxins (and its metabolites) in faeces (blood, urine and hair). Analysis of endocrine-disrupting chemicals in water.	All lab infrastructure for a high analytical infrastructure are available at VITO. We have around 500m2 lab space. Physical infrastructure consist of many apparatus (including chromatographic tools) and sample prep devices & techniques but specifically: * TIMS-TOF High Resolution MS and Orbitrap HR MS (coupled to UPLC or direct analysis-DART) * UPLC- QqQ MS	Belgium
	3 Xevo TQ-S LC-MS/MS 1 Synaps LC-HRMS 1 UPLC QDa en PDA detector In the lab of prof. Lynn Vanhaecke, we have 25% access to LA-REIMS and 25% ABSCIEX instrument.	Belgium
urine and saliva	mass spectrometers	Cyprus
LC-HRMS/MS (Orbitrap) & GC-HRMS (Orbitrap) profiling of human blood serum/plasma.	2*GC-Orbitrap Exploris 240 duoLC-Orbitrap Fusion duoLC-Orbitrap Exploris 480 Automation of sample prep.	Czech Republic
Targeted measurements of the environmental and human samples. Persistent organic pollutants, emergent pollutants, metabolites, heavy metals and trace elements.	Highly educated team, modern equipment, accredited SOP.	Czech Republic
Both environmental and biological specimens. PFAS: Targeted LC-MS/MS measurements with quantitative results; Serum, breast milk and other human samples, Food, Soil, sediment and other environmental samples, Water Bisphenol A: Targeted LC-MS/MS measurements with quantitative results; Urine, Consumer products, Water Phthalates: Targeted LC-MS/MS measurements with quantitative results; Urine, Cotinine: Targeted LC-MS/MS measurements with quantitative results; Urine, Serum Parabens: Targeted LC-MS/MS measurements with quantitative results; Urine, Serum, Consumer products, Water Organic tin compounds: Targeted GC-MS/MS measurements with quantitative results; Whole blood and other human samples, Fish and other animal samples, Food, Soil, sediment and other environmental samples Dioxins and PCBs: Targeted GC-MS/MS measurements with quantitative results; Serum, breast milk, placenta and other human samples, Fish and other animal samples, Food and feed, Soil, sediment and other environmental samples, Water, Other samples containing fat or oil PBDEs: Targeted GC-MS/MS measurements with quantitative results; Serum, breast milk, placenta and other human samples, Fish and other animal samples, Food and feed, Soil, sediment and other environmental samples, Water, Other samples containing fat or oil	2x GC-MS 3x LC-MS 2x Extraction devices	Finland
Type exogenous substance: Targeted analysis of persistent (i.e. dioxins, PCBs, PFASs, PBDEs) and non-persistent (i.e. bisphenols, phthalates, pesticides) chemicals as well as non-targeted/suspect screening of environmental chemicals Type of measurement: LC-MS/MS, GC-MS/MS and IC-MS/MS) with quantitative results. LC- and GC-HRMS with semi-quantitative results. Biological specimens/matrices: blood, urine, breast milk, hair, meconium, adipose tissue, placenta	Equipment and facilities for mass spectrometric analysis of trace pollutants, including targeted analysis (5 LC-MS/MS, 5 GC-MS/MS, 1 APGC-MS/MS, 1 IC-MS/MS, 1 ICP-MS/MS), non-targeted and suspect screening (2 LC-qToFMS, APGC-qToFMS, 2 GC-QEx, 1 LC-QEx, 1 LC-Ex)	France
Target / Suspect / Nontarget screening of organic xenobiotics (including pesticides, biocides, industrial chemicals, polymer additives, personal care products, including transformation products, etc.), in human (blood, urine, and environmental (water, sediment, biota) samples	Laboratories equipped for preparation of human and environmental samples (large scale and well-plate SPE, PLE, LLE) GC-HRMS (ToF and Orbitrap), LC-HRMS (Orbitrap), LC-ion mobility-ToF LC-QQQ-MS, GC-QQQ-MS Server infrastructure for large-scale HRMS data processing	Germany
Type exogenous substance: Targeted screening of endocrine disrupting compounds (e.g. triclosan, BPA) Type of measurement: GC-MS with semi-quantitative results. Environmental specimens/matrices: soil, sediment, sludge, water, wastewater	Agilent ICP-OES, Model 5800 VDV (heavy metal analysis) Agilent 7890-5975C GC-MS (EDCs analysis)	Greece

<p>Biological specimens/matrices: -</p> <p>Type substance: Targeted screening of heavy metals Type of measurement: ICP-OES with quantitative results.</p> <p>Environmental specimens/matrices: soil, sediment, sewage, sludge, water, wastewater Biological specimens/matrices: plant and animal tissues</p> <p>Type exogenous substance: Radioactivity (gamma radiation, alpha/beta gross radiation, radon)</p> <p>Type of measurement: gamma spectroscopy with High purity Ge detector with quantitative results. Alpha/beta low background counting system with quantitative results. Portable radon detector for air and water dissolved measurements.</p> <p>Environmental specimens/matrices: air, soil, water</p> <p>Biological specimens/matrices: urine, blood</p>	<p>Low Background Alpha/Beta Counting System MIRION Series 6LB</p> <p>Handheld Radioisotopic identifier MIRION SpiR-ID LT</p> <p>Coaxial Hyperpure Ge gamma ray detector</p> <p>AlphaGUARD DF2000 portable radon detector.</p>	
<p>*-Matrices that can be analyzed: environmental samples (drinking water, ground water, surface water, wastewater (influent and effluent), soil, sediment, sludge, biota (e.g. muscle tissue, liver) and biological samples (urine, serum/plasma, saliva)</p> <p>-Exogenous substances: Polar, semi-polar and non-polar xenobiotics (main classes: pharmaceuticals and personal care products, illicit drugs, plant protection products, industrial chemicals (including PFAS, benzotriazoles/benzothiazoles, tire additives, PAHs), artificial sweeteners and their transformation products/metabolites)</p> <p>-Instrumental analysis: LC-ESI-HRMS, LC-HESI-TIMS-HRMS, GC-APCI-HRMS, LC-MS/MS</p> <p>-Workflows: highly sensitive LC-MS/MS targeted methodologies with quantitative results, wide-scope HRMS targeted methodologies with quantitative results, suspect and non-target screening workflows with semi-quantitative results, retrospective screening, untargeted trend analysis</p>	<p>LC-ESI-HRMS, LC-HESI-TIMS-HRMS, GC-APCI-HRMS, LC-MS/MS, supporting lab equipment for pre-treatment, extraction and clean-up methods (ultrasound, microwave, solid-phase extraction devices, accelerated solvent extractor, freeze-dryer, bead beater homogenizer)</p>	Greece
<p>Chemical composition of particulate matter (PM) through sampling of filters followed by laboratory analysis, with emphasis on the main components of the aerosol such as organic (PAHs, CPs), ionic composition (chloride, sulfate, nitrate, phosphate, ammonia), and organic/elemental carbon</p> <p>State of the art analytical protocols for the monitoring of dioxins and dioxin like compounds in food, feed, air, soil, water and human samples.</p> <p>Development of analytical methods for monitoring and accurate measurement of emerging pollutants as perfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) and brominated flame retardants as bromodiphenyl ethers (PBDEs) and α-, β- and γ-stereoisomers of hexabromocyclododecane (HBCDD).</p> <p>Measurement of dioxins and dioxin like compound in serum, plasma and breast milk using state of the art protocols with GC-HRMS</p> <p>Measurement of emerging pollutants as PFASs and BFRs in serum, plasma, breast milk, urine and semen using state of the art protocols with LC-HRMS and GC-HRMS</p> <p>Non-targeted measurements of pollutants as well as parent and transformation exposure markers in humans and the environment using QToF high resolution mass spectrometry</p>	<p>Gas chromatograph (GC) with mass spectrometer (MS) and ECD detector (AGILENT 5975 GC / MS-ECD)</p> <p>Gas chromatograph (GC) with FID detector (AGILENT 1530N GC / FID) combined with thermal desorption system (TDS2 GERSTEL).</p> <p>Gas chromatograph (GC) with FID, PID (THERMO) detectors for greenhouse gas detection.</p> <p>Ion chromatography (IC) Dionex 1100</p> <p>Gas Chromatography - High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (GC/HRMS)</p> <p>Gas Chromatography- Triple Quadrupole Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS/MS)</p> <p>Liquid Chromatography-High resolution Quadrupole-Time-of-Flight(LC-Qtof)</p> <p>Liquid Chromatography - Triple Quadrupole Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS/MS)</p> <p>Pressurized liquid extraction apparatus</p>	Greece

	Fully automatic sample preparation system for POPs analysis	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type exogenous substance: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Acute or chronic drug use, pharmaceutical substances and exposure to pesticides, other toxicants, endocrine disruptors etc. o Measurements of pharmacokinetics o Molecular techniques DNA analysis, telomeres, telomerase measurements • Type of measurement <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Bioanalytical techniques <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Q-FISH analysis of telomeres (microscope, hood, cell culture incubator etc.) - Chromatographic systems (LC/MS/MS, LC-MS, GC/MS, GC, HPLC) - Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry system (ICP-MS) - Automated high performance liquid chromatography (TOXIS) - Fully automated immunoassay systems analysis ELISA spectrophotometers - Molecular techniques systems (PCR, Capillary Electrophoresis) - System immunofluorescence • Biological specimens/matrices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o urine, serum, plasma, breast milk, hair 	<p>The Laboratory of Toxicology is fully equipped with modern analytical instruments for certifications, preliminary examination instruments and preparation instruments for extraction and purification of samples along with implementation of validated bioanalytical methods. For example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infrastructure for Q-FISH analysis of telomeres (microscope, hood, cell culture incubator etc.) • Chromatographic systems (LC/MS/MS, LC-MS, GC/MS, GC, HPLC) • Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry system (ICP-MS) • Automated high performance liquid chromatography (TOXIS) • fully automated immunoassay systems analysis ELISA spectrophotometers • Molecular techniques systems (PCR, Capillary Electrophoresis) • System immunofluorescence • Refrigerators for sample preservation 	Greece
<p>Type exogenous substance: Non-targeted/Suspect screening of xenobiotics (phthalates, bisphenols, PAHs, PFAs, Flame retardants, pesticides, metals, microplastics)</p> <p>Type of measurement: LC-HRMS, GC – HRMS</p> <p>Biological specimens/matrices: urine, serum, plasma, breast milk</p> <p>Environmental samples: silicone wristbands, air sampling filters, water, dust</p> <p>Type exogenous substance: Targeted analysis of xenobiotics (phthalates, bisphenols, PAHs, PFAs, Flame retardants, pesticides, metals, microplastics)</p> <p>Type of measurement: LC-MS/MS, GC – MS/MS</p> <p>Biological specimens/matrices: urine, serum, plasma, breast milk, in vivo (D.rerio) & in vitro</p> <p>Environmental samples: silicone wristbands, air sampling filters, water, dust</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GC/MS-MS/QToF Agilent Technologies 7200A • LC/MS-MS/QToF Agilent Technologies 1290-6540 UHD • LC/MS-MS Thermo Scientific Orbitrap • LC/MS-MS Thermo Scientific Q Exactive Focus Orbitrap • Thermo Scientific TSQ Vantage LC-MS/MS • Trace GC Ultra Thermo, TSQuantum XLS. • ICP-MS • Triple Quadrupole LC-MS • Sample concentrator TECHNE FSC496D • Small Prime Centrifuge refrigerated Centurion Scientific K2015R • Semi-Micro Balances Adam Equipment ABL 225 • Class II Biological Safety Chamber Biobase BSC-1300IIB2-X • Deep freezer (-80 oC) of 700 lt for storage of biological samples 	Greece
	<p>LC-MS/MS ToF</p> <hr/> <p>MALDI-ToF (2)</p> <hr/> <p>Facilities for analysis and sample preparation</p>	Greece
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Screening of minerals and pesticides in water samples • GC-/LC-MS analysis of blood (plasma, serum, umbilical cord) samples for pesticides and other substances in targeted and untargeted way 	<p>Mineral and pesticide screening lab at the Mining & Metallurgical Engineering School, NTU Athens</p> <p>Mass Spectrometry-based Metabolomic Facility at FORTH/ICE-HT</p> <p>Access to Raman Spectroscopy facility and SEM</p>	Greece
<p>Type exogenous substance: Targeted and suspect screening of xenobiotics (PCDDs, PCDFs, DL-PCBs, NDL-PCBs, Organochlorinated pesticides, PBDEs, HBCDs, PFASs, OH-PAHs, PAHs), Major, Minor and Trace elements, Element Speciation, Nanoparticles of metals, Isotopic ratio analysis</p>	<p>Six laboratories for the analysis of organics equipped with: two GC-HRMS, one LC-HRMS, two GC-LRMS, and two LC-LRMS. The</p>	Italy

<p>Type of measurement: LC-MS/MS, GC-MS/MS, LC-HRMS, GC-HRMS, Q-ICP-MS; HR-ICP-MS; Ion Chromatography-ICP-MS; Single-Particle-ICP-MS; Multi-Collector-ICP-MS; Field Flow Fractionation-Multi-Angle Light scattering (FFF-MALS); UV-DAD; Direct Mercury Analyzer (DMA-80)</p> <p>Biological specimens/matrices: urine, serum, blood, plasma, breast milk.</p>	<p>available physical infrastructure for the analysis of Major, Minor and Trace elements, Element Speciation, Nanoparticles of metals, Isotopic ratio analysis were: Q-ICP-MS (no. 1); HR-ICP-MS (no. 1); Ion Chromatography (no. 1); Multi-Collector-ICP-MS (no. 1); FFF-MALS (no. 1); UV-DAD (no. 1); DMA (no.1); Microwave digestion systems (no. 2); hot-plate digestion system (no. 1).</p>	
<p>Heavy metal and ionic species; carbonaceous aerosol fractions in particulate matter for classifying Organic (OC) and Elemental (EC) Carbon; total and speciated Hg in environmental (air, water, soil, biota, waste) and biological (urine, hair, human breast milk) matrices; organic compounds (i.e., PCBs, pesticides, PAHs etc.) in environmental samples (various matrices such as sediments, contaminated soil, air samples, wastes, fresh and sea water). Ion chromatography (IC); Inductively Coupled Plasma-tandem Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS/MS); Ion Chromatography followed by Inductively Coupled Plasma-tandem Mass Spectrometry (IC-ICP-MS/MS); TD-AAS; Thermal-Optical Transmittance (TOT) methods. Direct Thermal Decomposition – Gold Amalgamation – Cold Vapor Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (CVAAS); Cold Vapor Atomic Fluorescence Spectrometry (CVAFS).</p>	<p>The physical infrastructure is equipped with two research open access infrastructures/laboratories where the relationship between environmental pollution and impact on human health are investigated, through the optimization of the methodology for the development of appropriate exposure, related to both characterization as well as to standardization of analytical methods. Another important facility is the “Biomonitoring Laboratory”, which is equipped with advanced technological instrumentations including, among others: a Direct Thermal Decomposition Mercury Analyzer (Nippon Instrument Corporation, MA-3000); the Tekran® Series 2600 system both allowing analysis of ultra-trace levels of mercury samples; the Ion chromatography followed by inductively coupled plasma-tandem mass spectrometry (IC-ICP-MS/MS) for quantification of heavy metal and ionic species; and the Semi-Continuous OCEC Carbon Aerosol analysis instrument by Sunset Laboratory Inc. for classifying Organic (OC) and Elemental (EC) Carbon by Thermal-Optical Transmittance (TOT) method.</p>	Italy
<p>Non-targeted/Suspect screening of xenobiotics (wide scope) LC-HRMS with RP or HILIC coupled with ESI +/-, optional semi-quant Matrices: water (surface, waste, ground), urine, serum/plasma, CSF, faeces, various other tissue samples</p>	<p>Thermo Vanquish UHPLC – Thermo Orbitrap Exploris 240 MS Thermo Vanquish UHPLC – Thermo Q Exactive HF MS SCIEX Exion LC – SCIEX Triple Quad 7500 MS Agilent 1290 LC–Agilent 6560 MS Dionex ICS-6000 – Thermo Q Exactive MS Agilent 8890 GC–Agilent 5977B MS Agilent 7890B GC–Agilent 5977A MS https://www.uni.lu/lcsb-en/facilities/metabolomics/</p>	Luxembourg
<p>Targeted and quantitative analysis of the following exogenous substances using different type of measurements: Indoor environment analysis: • pollutants in indoor dust: inorganic elements, pesticides, PAH, phthalates, flame retardants, PCB and PBDE using GC-MS; HBCDD and PFAS by UPLC-MS/MS • pollutants in indoor air: VOCs via TD-GC-MS and aldehydes via HPLC Human Biological Monitoring: • pollutants in urine: - inorganic elements by ICP-MS, - VOCs metabolites (e.g. SPMA and SBMA) by UPLC-MS/MS - HBCDD and PFAS by UPLC-MS/MS - Phthalates by UPLC-MS/MS - Bisphenols by GC-MS/MS • pollutants in blood: - inorganic elements via ICP-MS - PCB and PBDE using GC-MS/MS - Pesticides by GC-MS/MS and LC-MS/MS - Phthalates by - Glutathione via UPLC-MS/MS</p>	<p>State of the art infrastructure and technical equipment that are used for the evaluation of indoor pollution, occupational hygiene and human biological monitoring. A fully equipped laboratory to perform analytical chemistry including the following analytical instruments: TD-GCMS 8890-5977, GC-MS 7890A -5975C, GC-MS 6890N-5975, GC-MS/MS 9000-7010B, HPLC 1260 Infinity, UPLC-MS/MS, ICP-MS 7700, ICP-MS 7900, GC-QToF 8890-7250, LC-ICP-MS/MS-8900</p>	Luxembourg

<p>Drugs, illicit drugs, metals, POPs, mycotoxins, pesticides, fluorinated chemicals</p>	<p>LC-MS/MS, GC-MS/MS etc</p>	<p>Luxemburg</p>
<p>LC and GC-mass spectrometry analysis. Services are offered for targeted mass spectrometry quantification of environmental organic chemicals in human samples (blood, urine, breast milk).</p>	<p>LC and GC-mass spectrometry</p>	<p>Norway</p>
<p>Type exogenous substance: Targeted measurements of the elements (Cd, Pb, Zn, Cu, Mn, Mg, Ca, Se, Fe, Au, Ti, As ...) Type of measurement: FAAS, ETA-AAS, ICP-MS Biological specimens/matrices: whole blood, urine, serum, plasma, breast milk.</p> <p>Type exogenous substance: Targeted measurements of 17 2,3,7,8-subst. PCDDs/Fs, 12 DL-PCBs (#77, 81, 126, 169, 105, 114, 118, 123, 156, 157, 167, 189), 6 NDL-PCBs (#28, 52, 101, 138, 153, 180), 8 PBDEs (#28, 47, 99, 100, 153, 154, 183, 209) Type of measurement: GC-HRMS with quantitative results. Biological specimens/matrices: serum, plasma, breast milk. Food and feed. Environmental matrices: sediment, soil, air particles, water.</p>	<p>Analytical laboratories at Slovak Medical University in Bratislava with long years of expertise in the field of determination of toxic substances in food, feed, human samples (serum, breast milk) and environmental samples.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (Thermo XSeries 2); • Flame atomic absorption spectrometer (Varian AA240FS) with deuterium background correction • Flameless atomic absorption spectrometer (Varian AA280Z) with graphite furnace and Zeeman background correction Microwave accelerated reaction system (CEM MarsXpress) • High Performance Microwave Digestion System Milestone MLS 1200 MEGA • UV Water Purification System <p>High-resolution mass spectrometer combined with two gas chromatographs (Thermo Fisher Scientific) for target analysis of persistent organic pollutants. Chemical laboratories equipped with manual and semi-automated extraction systems and devices for sample preparation, extraction, clean-up and fractionation of different groups of substances.</p>	<p>Slovakia</p>
<p>Targeted screening/DINCH metabolites by HPLC-MS/MS; matrices: urine (service available), and in meconium and breast milk (service available in cca 2 years).</p> <p>Other services: Characterization of humic substances (humic acids, fulvic acids) isolated from soil, peat and airborne dust particles using size exclusion chromatography (SEC). Determination of the content of humic substances in matrices of different origin (soil, lignite, peat, extracts from waterworks sludge etc.).</p>	<p>HPLC-MS/MS, HRMS</p>	<p>Slovakia</p>
<p>targeted: trace elements and their speciation, stable isotopes of light and heavy metals, Phthalates, parabens, BPs, PFAS, pharmaceuticals, triclosan non-targeted/screening: LC-HGME, orbitrap Samples: urine, blood, serum, breast milk, meconium, placenta, cord tissue,</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Isotope ratio mass spectrometers (IRMS): Europa Scientific 20-20 stable isotope analyzer with ANCA-SL and ANCA-TG preparation modules for solid, liquid and gas samples; IsoPrime100 - Vario PYRO Cube (OH/CNS Pyrolyser/Elemental Analyser); IsoPrime GV with gas chromatography and combustion unit for stable isotope analyses of organic compound (GC-C-IRMS) o Mass spectrometers for identification and analysis of organic compounds – target, non-target analysis: GC-MSD, LC-QToF, LC-QTrap, GC-IT-MS, UHPLC-HRMS(/MS) - Orbitrap o Multicollector ICP-MS (Nu Instruments) for stable isotope analysis of trace elements o Mass spectrometers for speciation and elemental analysis: ICP-MS (Agilent 7500 series), ICP-MS QQQ, Laser ablation ICP-MS o Mercury analysis and speciation: Cold vapour atomic absorption spectrometry (CV AAS, detector Milton Roy, Model 1255, two 	<p>Slovenia</p>

	<p>systems); Cold vapour atomic fluorescence spectrometry (CV AFS, detector Tekran, model 2500) with double amalgamation system and Hg vapour calibration system; Cold vapour atomic fluorescence spectrometry (CV AFS, two systems with Brooks Rand detectors); Direct Mercury Analyzer (DMA 80 – Milestone Microwave Laboratory Systems)</p>	
<p>Screening of xenobiotic: drugs, pollutants, food additives LC-HRMS with semi-quantitative results Biological matrices: urine, serum, plasma</p>	<p>Laboratories at the Faculty of Pharmacy (UL FFA) are fully equipped with instrumentation for organic synthesis, analysis of synthetic products and PADMET evaluation: NMR spectrometer Bruker AVANCE III 400 MHz; Microplate reader TECAN Sapphire II; Multi-Mode Microplate Reader (SINERGY H4) and robot for automatic pipetting (PRECISION XS); EliSpot/FluoroSpot Reader, ELR08IFL; Nano ITC system for microcalorimetry TA Instruments; FT-IR spectrometer Perkin Elmer Spectrum BX; Polarimeter Perkin-Elmer 241 MCHPLC Agilent Technologies 1100 ;Gas chromatograph with mass selective detector Shimadzu GCMS-QP2010 Ultra; Ultra HPLC with triple quadrupole tandem MS spectrometer (UHPLC/MS/MS) Agilent 6460; Chromatographic system ÅKTAexplorer 10 S 82.427 Thermo Vanquish Duo UHPLC system with double LC s Corona™ Veo™ RS Charged Aerosol detector (HRMS compatible); High resolution mass spectrometer HPLC-HRMS Exactive Plus Orbitrap Mass Spectrometer – Thermo (resolution 140.000) coupled with UHPLC Thermo Ultimate 3000; HPLC-MS Advion CMSL single quadropol (coupled with HPLC 1260 InfinityII and Advion reader for TLC-MS); UHPLC-MS Agilent 6545XT AdvanceBIO Q-ToF (coupled with 1290 Infinity II), Thermo Vanquish Duo UHPLC system with double LC s Corona™ Veo™ RS Charged Aerosol detector (HRMS compatible); UHPLC Thermo Ultimate 3000; Workstation with two 14-core Intel Xeon Gold 5120, 48 GB RAM-a, 1 TB SSD, 8 TB HDD in graphic card RTX 2080 Ti 9.000 (structure-based drug design software: Autodock, FlexX, Gold, eHiTS, ROCS, etc.); Imaging flow cytometer, Amnis ImageStreamX Mk II; BD FACSCalibur Flow Cytometer; Flow cytometer Attune NxT, Life Technologies; Raman Spectrometer - Confocal Raman Atomic Force Microscope XploRA PLUS-OmegaScope; Confocal microscope Axio Observer Z1; Next generation sequencer, MiSeq, Illumina 141.925 Sequencer, Genome Lab GeXP, Beckman Coulter 95.302 qPCR system, Light Cycler 480, Roche 47.439 qPCR system ABI PRISM Nucleic Acid PrepStation 80.652 Automated Platform for Live Cell Imaging; Transgenomic WAVE MD</p>	<p>Slovenia</p>

	<p>dHPLC SISTEM Plus; Biobanking system, Arpege, PHCBI; Biotage Isolera flash chromatography system; Parr 4560 mini bench top reactor; Chromatotron 7924T Harrison Research circular chromatography system; Discover (CEM Corporation) microwave synthesis system.</p> <p>The Faculty of Pharmacy also has three fully equipped cell laboratories. The researchers have direct access to the equipment, infrastructure and expertise of two infrastructure centers operating at the Faculty of Pharmacy: EATRIS Slovenia (https://www.ffa.uni-lj.si/en/faculty/organization/Infrastructural-centres/eatris-slovenia) and Infrastructural Center for Drug Analysis (https://www.ffa.uni-lj.si/en/research/research-equipment/0/infrastructural-center-for-drug-analysis).</p>	
<p>Effect-directed analysis (EDA) combining bioassays and non-target screening using LC-HRMS</p> <p>Type of measurement: LC-MS/MS; GC-MS/MS for target screening</p> <p>LC-HRMS with semi-quantitative results using suspect/Non-targeted screening</p> <p>Environmental matrices: water, soil, sediment, air</p> <p>Biological specimens/matrices: serum, plasma, tissues, organs</p>	<p>3 LC-MS/MS</p> <p>1 GC-MS</p> <p>1 GC-MS/MS</p> <p>1 LC-HRMS</p> <p>1 EDA platform</p> <p>3 sample preparation labs for environmental matrices (water, soil, sediment, air) and biological specimens matrices (serum, plasma, tissues, organs)</p>	Sweden
<p>Non-target and suspect screening of micropollutants and other xenobiotics (PFASs, PAHs, drugs and transformation products). SFC, LC and TDU-GC-mass spectrometry analysis. Human (biofluids, tissues and breath), biota and abiotic (water, soil and air) samples.</p>	<p>Equipment and facilities for mass spectrometric analysis of trace pollutants and other xenobiotics, including non-target and suspect screening (LC/GC/SFC-qToFMS, APGC-qToFMS, LC-QqQ, GC-MS, TDU-GC-OrbitrapMS). Entire workflow from extraction to data analysis.</p>	Sweden
<p>Targeted SFC, LC and GC-mass spectrometry analysis. Services are offered for quantification of micropollutants and other xenobiotics (PFASs, PAHs, drugs and transformation products). Human (biofluids and tissues), biota and abiotic (water, soil and air) samples.</p>	<p>Equipment and facilities for mass spectrometric analysis of trace pollutants, including three LC-MS/MS systems, SFC-MS/MS, LC/SFC/GC-qToFMS, GC-MS and GC-OrbitrapMS. Entire workflow from extraction to data analysis.</p>	Sweden
<p>SU/ACES direct the National Facility for Exposomics, SciLifeLab, which has expertise in small molecule untargeted mass spectrometry in human and environmental samples. We offer combined target (180 priority analytes such as environmental pollutants, drugs, hormones, dietary substances) and nontarget coverage (typically >10,000 features with MS2 spectra) of the chemical exposome in biofluids, tissues, and environmental samples (water, air, soil). Comprehensive trace analysis by liquid (LC) or gas chromatography (GC) with Orbitrap mass spectrometers operating in full scan with parallel data-independent (DIA) MS2 (for LC workflows). We offer specialty methods for enhanced exposomics of human plasma by phospholipid depletion, and for environmental water by in-line solid phase extraction. High throughput structural annotation of unknown small molecules using molecular networking, in silico fragmentation and PubChemLite. All data processing uses open science software and FAIR data management. Exposure markers, including exposome-metabolome interactions are elucidated by multivariate data analysis and modeling.</p>	<p>Positive pressure clean laboratory for sample processing, and adjacent mass spectrometry facility, currently housing three orbitrap mass spectrometers:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. GC-Q Exactive 2. LC-Q Exactive HFX with in-line SPE 3. LC Exploris 480 	Sweden
<p>Type of exogenous substance: PFAS, phthalates, bisphenols, mycotoxins</p> <p>Type of measurement: LC-MS/MS with quantitative results</p> <p>Biological matrices: plasma, serum, urine, breast milk</p>	<p>We have an instrument park of 5 triple quadrupole mass spectrometers dedicated to quantification of exogenous and endogenous compounds. This is accompanied by dedicated sample processing laboratory (BSL2) and robotic sample preparation equipment.</p>	Sweden
<p>Type exogenous substance: Non-targeted/Suspect screening of xenobiotics (any kind of polar and non polar small organic molecules)</p> <p>Type of measurement: LC-HRMS, qTOF with semi-quantitative results (APCI and ESI ionization modes). GC-HRMS, Pyr/GC-MS.</p>	<p>LC-HRMS, qTOF equipped with APCI and ESI ionization modes.</p> <p>GC-HRMS</p> <p>GCxGC-MS</p>	The Netherlands

<p>Biological specimens/matrices: urine, serum, plasma, breast milk, placenta, human and animal major organs. Environmental matrices: Surface and drinking water, influent and effluent water, food, soil, consumer products, house dust, nano-, micro-plastics.</p>	<p>Pyr/GC-MS</p>	
<p>https://www.kwrwater.nl/en/experts-expertises/expertises/chemical-laboratory/</p>	<p>https://www.kwrwater.nl/en/experts-expertises/expertises/chemical-laboratory/</p>	<p>The Netherlands</p>
<p>Type exogenous substance: both target quantitative determination and (semi-quantitative) non-targeted/suspect screening of xenobiotics (small molecules: pesticides, biocides, natural toxins, environmental contaminants, POPs, processing contaminants, food contact materials, veterinary drugs, endocrine disruptors, illegal substances in food supplements, environmental degradation products, plant, animal, human metabolites of these, radionuclides (gamma/alfa/beta emitters) Type of measurement: target: LC-MS/MS, GC-MS/MS; Suspect screening/non-target screening: LC-HRMS, GC-HRMS (Orbitrap based). Sample matrices: food & feed (including animal products), environmental (soil, sediment, household dust, fish, earthworms/insects, wristbands), human & animal: urine, serum, plasma, dry blood spots, breast milk, faeces, hair, nails, saliva.</p>	<p>LC-MS/MS (Waters, Sciex), LC-Q-trap-MS/MS (Sciex), LC-Q-Orbitrap HRMS (from classic to IQ-X), GC-MS/MS (Agilent), GC-Orbitrap-HRMS; ICP-MS/MS, ICP-MS (also combined with chromatography for element speciation) Equipment of measurement of radionuclides [would need to go after the details, but includes gamma, beta, alfa) BSL-2 laboratory Laboratory infrastructure to facilitate sample pretreatment (homogenisation/aliquotation), sample extraction & cleanup, manual and (semi)automated (96-well plate, microSPE) -80C and -18C storage facilities</p>	<p>The Netherlands</p>
<p>Consultation with sample owners on how to provide (meta)data to Exposome Scan . Consultation on the FAIR reporting of data generated by Exposome Scan. (Putative) characterization and identification of metabolic features by comparing with a reference chemical library and computational tools Statistical support for complex network of exposure-related interactions of compounds measured, and their effect measured with metabolomics (and other omics). Full service: taking control over the complete process from delivering samples and meta-data to the interpretation of study results.</p>	<p>-</p>	<p>The Netherlands</p>
<p>Combination of targeted and non-targeted LC-HRMS analysis with an increasing list of targets, including endogenous metabolites, drugs, pesticides, PFAS. Semi-quantitative analysis in plasma.</p>	<p>Workcell for automated sample handling, several LC-HRMS instruments and LC-MS/MS instruments and a GC-Orbitrap MS. Also there is a research lab with LC and MS instruments for innovative exposome research.</p>	<p>The Netherlands</p>

Annex 3b

Description of the systems and capacity to measure exogenous substances.

Country	Systems and Equipement	Type of samples	Number of samples per day
Austria	Agilent 1290 Infinity II Liquid Chromatography System SCIEX ZenoTOF 7600	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	100-1.000
Austria	3 ICP-MS_instruments microwave, heating block, clean room HPLC for flow injection and speciation analysis	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	100-1.000
Austria	3 ICP-MS_instruments microwave, heating block, clean room HPLC for flow injection and speciation analysis	Environmental samples	100-1.000
Austria	Service 1. Multi-class biomonitoring (targeted for more than 80 analytes) Agilent 1290 Infinity II Liquid Chromatography System SCIEX QTRAP 6500	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	100-1.000
Austria	The primary mission of the Core Facility Metabolomics of the Medical University of Innsbruck is to serve as an enabling resource for research and development programs at local, national and international level. The Core Facility Metabolomics is equipped with two HR-MS instruments (Orbitrap Exploris 240, Thermo; TripleTof 5600+, Sciex) and two low-resolution MS instruments (QTrap 6500+, Sciex, Xevo TQ-XS, Waters). All necessary devices for processing biological and environmental samples are available.	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100
Austria	The primary mission of the Core Facility Metabolomics of the Medical University of Innsbruck is to serve as an enabling resource for research and development programs at local, national and international level. The Core Facility Metabolomics is equipped with two HR-MS instruments (Orbitrap Exploris 240, Thermo; TripleTof 5600+, Sciex) and two low-resolution MS instruments (QTrap 6500+, Sciex, Xevo TQ-XS, Waters). All necessary devices for processing biological and environmental samples are available.	Environmental samples	0-100
Belgium	ISSeP has laboratories for the analysis of exogenous substances and compounds present in the environment (water, air, soil, dust, materials, biota). There is no infrastructure for carrying out analysis of exogenous compounds in biological matrices. These analyzes are carried out in partner laboratories. Different spectrometers (ICP AES, ICP MS, LC MS, GC MS) ionic chromatography, micro organism enumeration, PCR, Yes and Yas assay, ecotox assays (algae, daphnia, fish, invertebrates)	Environmental samples	1.000-10.000
Belgium	All lab infrastructure for a high analytical infrastructure are available at VITO. We have around 500m2 lab space. Physical infrastructure consist of many apparatus (including chromatographic tools) and sample prep devices & techniques but specifically: * TIMS-TOF High Resolution MS and Orbitrap HR MS (coupled to UPLC or direct analysis-DART) * UPLC- QqQ MS	nanoplastics	0-100
Belgium	All lab infrastructure for a high analytical infrastructure are available at VITO. We have around 500m2 lab space. Physical infrastructure consist of many apparatus (including chromatographic tools) and sample prep devices & techniques but specifically: * TIMS-TOF High Resolution MS and Orbitrap HR MS (coupled to UPLC or direct analysis-DART) * UPLC- QqQ MS	degradation products of xenobiotics	0-100
Belgium	All lab infrastructure for a high analytical infrastructure are available at VITO. We have around 500m2 lab space. Physical infrastructure consist of many apparatus (including chromatographic tools) and sample prep devices & techniques but specifically: * TIMS-TOF High Resolution MS and Orbitrap HR MS (coupled to UPLC or direct	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100

	analysis-DART) * UPLC- QqQ MS		
Belgium	All lab infrastructure for a high analytical infrastructure are available at VITO. We have around 500m2 lab space. Physical infrastructure consist of many apparatus (including chromatographic tools) and sample prep devices & techniques but specifically: * TIMS-TOF High Resolution MS and Orbitrap HR MS (coupled to UPLC or direct analysis-DART) * UPLC- QqQ MS	Environmental samples	0-100
Belgium	3 Xevo TQ-S LC-MS/MS 1 Synaps LC-HRMS 1 UPLC QDa en PDA detector In the lab of prof. Lynn Vanhaecke, we have 25% access to LA-REIMS and 25% ABSCIEX instrument.	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100
Belgium	3 Xevo TQ-S LC-MS/MS 1 Synaps LC-HRMS 1 UPLC QDa en PDA detector In the lab of prof. Lynn Vanhaecke, we have 25% access to LA-REIMS and 25% ABSCIEX instrument.	Environmental samples	0-100
country	description	Type of sample	Answer
Cyprus	mass spectrometers	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	100-1.000
Czech Republic	2*GC-Orbitrap Exploris 240 duoLC-Orbitrap Fusion duoLC-Orbitrap Exploris 480 Automation of sample prep.	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100
Czech Republic	2*GC-Orbitrap Exploris 240 duoLC-Orbitrap Fusion duoLC-Orbitrap Exploris 480 Automation of sample prep.	Environmental samples	0-100
Czech Republic	Highly educated team, modern equipment, accredited SOP.	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100
Czech Republic	Highly educated team, modern equipment, accredited SOP.	Environmental samples	0-100
Finland	2x GC-MS 3x LC-MS 2x Extraction devices	industrial raw material (e.g. plastics, acids)	0-100
Finland	2x GC-MS 3x LC-MS 2x Extraction devices	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100
Finland	2x GC-MS 3x LC-MS 2x Extraction devices	Environmental samples	0-100
France	Equipment and facilities for mass spectrometric analysis of trace pollutants, including targeted analysis (5 LC-MS/MS, 5 GC-MS/MS, 1 APGC-MS/MS, 1 IC-MS/MS, 1 ICP-MS/MS), non-targeted and suspect screening (2 LC-qToFMS, APGC-qToFMS, 2 GC-QEx, 1 LC-QEx, 1 LC-Ex)	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100
Germany	Laboratories equipped for preparation of human and environmental samples (large scale and well-plate SPE, PLE, LLE) GC-HRMS (ToF and Orbitrap), LC-HRMS (Orbitrap), LC-ion mobility-ToF LC-QQQ-MS, GC-QQQ-MS Server infrastructure for large-scale HRMS data processing	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100
Germany	Laboratories equipped for preparation of human and environmental samples (large scale and well-plate SPE, PLE, LLE) GC-HRMS (ToF and Orbitrap), LC-HRMS (Orbitrap), LC-ion mobility-ToF	Environmental samples	0-100

	LC-QQQ-MS, GC-QQQ-MS Server infrastructure for large-scale HRMS data processing		
Greece	Agilent ICP-OES, Model 5800 VDV (heavy metal analysis) Agilent 7890-5975C GC-MS (EDCs analysis) Low Background Alpha/Beta Counting System MIRION Series 6LB Handheld Radioisotopic identifier MIRION SpiR-ID LT Coaxial Hyperpure Ge gamma ray detector AlphaGUARD DF2000 portable radon detector.	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100
Greece	Agilent ICP-OES, Model 5800 VDV (heavy metal analysis) Agilent 7890-5975C GC-MS (EDCs analysis) Low Background Alpha/Beta Counting System MIRION Series 6LB Handheld Radioisotopic identifier MIRION SpiR-ID LT Coaxial Hyperpure Ge gamma ray detector AlphaGUARD DF2000 portable radon detector.	Environmental samples	0-100
Greece	LC-ESI-HRMS, LC-HESI-TIMS-HRMS, GC-APCI-HRMS, LC-MS/MS, supporting lab equipment for pre-treatment, extraction and clean-up methods (ultrasound, microwave, solid-phase extraction devices, accelerated solvent extractor, freeze-dryer, bead beater homogenizer)	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100
Greece	LC-ESI-HRMS, LC-HESI-TIMS-HRMS, GC-APCI-HRMS, LC-MS/MS, supporting lab equipment for pre-treatment, extraction and clean-up methods (ultrasound, microwave, solid-phase extraction devices, accelerated solvent extractor, freeze-dryer, bead beater homogenizer)	Environmental samples	0-100
Greece	Gas chromatograph (GC) with mass spectrometer (MS) and ECD detector (AGILENT 5975 GC / MS-ECD) Gas chromatograph (GC) with FID detector (AGILENT 1530N GC / FID) combined with thermal desorption system (TDS2 GERSTEL). Gas chromatograph (GC) with FID, PID (THERMO) detectors for greenhouse gas detection. Ion chromatography (IC) Dionex 1100 Gas Chromatography - High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (GC/HRMS) Gas Chromatography- Triple Quadrupole Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS/MS) Liquid Chromatography-High resolution Quadrupole-Time-of-Flight(LC-Qtof) Liquid Chromatography - Triple Quadrupole Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) Pressurized liquid extraction apparatus Fully automatic sample preparation system for POPs analysis	Environmental samples	0-100
Greece	The Laboratory of Toxicology is fully equipped with modern analytical instruments for certifications, preliminary examination instruments and preparation instruments for extraction and purification of samples along with implementation of validated bioanalytical methods. For example: • Infrastructure for Q-FISH analysis of telomeres (microscope, hood, cell culture incubator etc.) • Chromatographic systems (LC/MS/MS, LC-MS, GC/MS, GC, HPLC) • Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry system (ICP-MS) • Automated high performance liquid chromatography (TOXIS) • fully automated immunoassay systems analysis ELISA spectrophotometers • Molecular techniques systems (PCR, Capillary Electrophoresis)	Food	0-100

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System immunofluorescence • Refrigerators for sample preservation 		
Greece	<p>The Laboratory of Toxicology is fully equipped with modern analytical instruments for certifications, preliminary examination instruments and preparation instruments for extraction and purification of samples along with implementation of validated bioanalytical methods. For example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infrastructure for Q-FISH analysis of telomeres (microscope, hood, cell culture incubator etc.) • Chromatographic systems (LC/MS/MS, LC-MS, GC/MS, GC, HPLC) • Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry system (ICP-MS) • Automated high performance liquid chromatography (TOXIS) • fully automated immunoassay systems analysis ELISA spectrophotometers • Molecular techniques systems (PCR, Capillary Electrophoresis) • System immunofluorescence • Refrigerators for sample preservation 	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100
Greece	<p>The Laboratory of Toxicology is fully equipped with modern analytical instruments for certifications, preliminary examination instruments and preparation instruments for extraction and purification of samples along with implementation of validated bioanalytical methods. For example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infrastructure for Q-FISH analysis of telomeres (microscope, hood, cell culture incubator etc.) • Chromatographic systems (LC/MS/MS, LC-MS, GC/MS, GC, HPLC) • Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry system (ICP-MS) • Automated high performance liquid chromatography (TOXIS) • fully automated immunoassay systems analysis ELISA spectrophotometers • Molecular techniques systems (PCR, Capillary Electrophoresis) • System immunofluorescence • Refrigerators for sample preservation 	Environmental samples	0-100
Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GC/MS-MS/QToF Agilent Technologies 7200A • LC/MS-MS/QToF Agilent Technologies 1290-6540 UHD • LC/MS-MS Thermo Scientific Orbitrap • LC/MS-MS Thermo Scientific Q Exactive Focus Orbitrap • Thermo Scientific TSQ Vantage LC-MS/MS • Trace GC Ultra Thermo, TSQuantum XLS. • ICP-MS • Triple Quadrupole LC-MS • Sample concentrator TECHNE FSC496D • Small Prime Centrifuge refrigerated Centurion Scientific K2015R • Semi-Micro Balances Adam Equipment ABL 225 • Class II Biological Safety Chamber Biobase BSC-1300IIB2-X • Deep freezer (-80 oC) of 700 lt for storage of biological samples 	In vitro or in vivo	100-1.000
Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GC/MS-MS/QToF Agilent Technologies 7200A • LC/MS-MS/QToF Agilent Technologies 1290-6540 UHD • LC/MS-MS Thermo Scientific Orbitrap • LC/MS-MS Thermo Scientific Q Exactive Focus Orbitrap • Thermo Scientific TSQ Vantage LC-MS/MS • Trace GC Ultra Thermo, TSQuantum XLS. • ICP-MS • Triple Quadrupole LC-MS • Sample concentrator TECHNE FSC496D • Small Prime Centrifuge refrigerated Centurion Scientific K2015R • Semi-Micro Balances Adam Equipment ABL 225 • Class II Biological Safety Chamber Biobase BSC-1300IIB2-X • Deep freezer (-80 oC) of 700 lt for storage of biological samples 	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	100-1.000
Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GC/MS-MS/QToF Agilent Technologies 7200A • LC/MS-MS/QToF Agilent Technologies 1290-6540 UHD • LC/MS-MS Thermo Scientific Orbitrap • LC/MS-MS Thermo Scientific Q Exactive Focus Orbitrap • Thermo Scientific TSQ Vantage LC-MS/MS • Trace GC Ultra Thermo, TSQuantum XLS. • ICP-MS • Triple Quadrupole LC-MS • Sample concentrator TECHNE FSC496D • Small Prime Centrifuge refrigerated Centurion Scientific K2015R • Semi-Micro Balances Adam Equipment ABL 225 	Environmental samples	100-1.000

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Class II Biological Safety Chamber Biobase BSC-1300IIB2-X • Deep freezer (-80 oC) of 700 lt for storage of biological samples 		
Greece	<p>LC-MS/MS ToF MALDI-ToF (2)</p> <p>Facilities for analysis and sample preparation</p>	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	100-1.000
Greece	<p>LC-MS/MS ToF MALDI-ToF (2)</p> <p>Facilities for analysis and sample preparation</p>	Environmental samples	100-1.000
Greece	<p>Mineral and pesticide screening lab at the Mining & Metallurgical Engineering School, NTU Athens</p> <p>Mass Spectrometry-based Metabolomic Facility at FORTH/ICE-HT</p> <p>Access to Raman Spectroscopy facility and SEM</p>	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100
Greece	<p>Mineral and pesticide screening lab at the Mining & Metallurgical Engineering School, NTU Athens</p> <p>Mass Spectrometry-based Metabolomic Facility at FORTH/ICE-HT</p> <p>Access to Raman Spectroscopy facility and SEM</p>	Environmental samples	0-100
Italy	Six laboratories for the analysis of organics equipped with: two GC-HRMS, one LC-HRMS, two GC-LRMS, and two LC-LRMS. The available physical infrastructure for the analysis of Major, Minor and Trace elements, Element Speciation, Nanoparticles of metals, Isotopic ratio analysis were: Q-ICP-MS (no. 1); HR-ICP-MS (no. 1); Ion Chromatography (no. 1); Multi-Collector-ICP-MS (no. 1); FFF-MALS (no. 1); UV-DAD (no. 1); DMA (no.1); Microwave digestion systems (no. 2); hot-plate digestion system (no. 1).	Food	0-100
Italy	Six laboratories for the analysis of organics equipped with: two GC-HRMS, one LC-HRMS, two GC-LRMS, and two LC-LRMS. The available physical infrastructure for the analysis of Major, Minor and Trace elements, Element Speciation, Nanoparticles of metals, Isotopic ratio analysis were: Q-ICP-MS (no. 1); HR-ICP-MS (no. 1); Ion Chromatography (no. 1); Multi-Collector-ICP-MS (no. 1); FFF-MALS (no. 1); UV-DAD (no. 1); DMA (no.1); Microwave digestion systems (no. 2); hot-plate digestion system (no. 1).	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100
Italy	Six laboratories for the analysis of organics equipped with: two GC-HRMS, one LC-HRMS, two GC-LRMS, and two LC-LRMS. The available physical infrastructure for the analysis of Major, Minor and Trace elements, Element Speciation, Nanoparticles of metals, Isotopic ratio analysis were: Q-ICP-MS (no. 1); HR-ICP-MS (no. 1); Ion Chromatography (no. 1); Multi-Collector-ICP-MS (no. 1); FFF-MALS (no. 1); UV-DAD (no. 1); DMA (no.1); Microwave digestion systems (no. 2); hot-plate digestion system (no. 1).	Environmental samples	0-100
Italy	The physical infrastructure is equipped with two research open access infrastructures/laboratories where the relationship between environmental pollution and impact on human health are investigated, through the optimization of the methodology for the development of appropriate exposure, related to both characterization as well as to standardization of analytical methods. Another important facility is the "Biomonitoring Laboratory", which is equipped with advanced technological instrumentations including, among others: a Direct Thermal Decomposition Mercury Analyzer (Nippon Instrument Corporation, MA-3000); the Tekran® Series 2600 system both allowing analysis of ultra-trace levels of mercury samples; the Ion chromatography followed by inductively coupled plasma-tandem mass spectrometry (IC-ICP-MS/MS) for quantification of heavy metal and ionic species; and the Semi-Continuous OCEC Carbon Aerosol analysis instrument by Sunset Laboratory Inc. for classifying Organic (OC) and Elemental (EC) Carbon by Thermal-Optical Transmittance (TOT) method.	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100
Italy	The physical infrastructure is equipped with two research open access infrastructures/laboratories where the relationship between environmental pollution and impact on human health are investigated, through the optimization of the methodology for the development of appropriate exposure, related to both characterization as well as to standardization of analytical methods. Another important facility is the "Biomonitoring Laboratory", which is equipped with advanced technological instrumentations including, among others: a Direct Thermal Decomposition Mercury Analyzer (Nippon Instrument Corporation, MA-3000); the Tekran® Series 2600 system both allowing analysis of	Environmental samples	0-100

	ultra-trace levels of mercury samples; the Ion chromatography followed by inductively coupled plasma-tandem mass spectrometry (IC-ICP-MS/MS) for quantification of heavy metal and ionic species; and the Semi-Continuous OCEC Carbon Aerosol analysis instrument by Sunset Laboratory Inc. for classifying Organic (OC) and Elemental (EC) Carbon by Thermal-Optical Transmittance (TOT) method.		
Luxembourg	Thermo Vanquish UHPLC – Thermo Orbitrap Exploris 240 MS Thermo Vanquish UHPLC – Thermo Q Exactive HF MS SCIEX Exion LC – SCIEX Triple Quad 7500 MS Agilent 1290 LC–Agilent 6560 MS Dionex ICS-6000 – Thermo Q Exactive MS Agilent 8890 GC–Agilent 5977B MS Agilent 7890B GC–Agilent 5977A MS https://www.uni.lu/lcsb-en/facilities/metabolomics/	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100
Luxembourg	Thermo Vanquish UHPLC – Thermo Orbitrap Exploris 240 MS Thermo Vanquish UHPLC – Thermo Q Exactive HF MS SCIEX Exion LC – SCIEX Triple Quad 7500 MS Agilent 1290 LC–Agilent 6560 MS Dionex ICS-6000 – Thermo Q Exactive MS Agilent 8890 GC–Agilent 5977B MS Agilent 7890B GC–Agilent 5977A MS https://www.uni.lu/lcsb-en/facilities/metabolomics/	Environmental samples	0-100
Luxembourg	State of the art infrastructure and technical equipment that are used for the evaluation of indoor pollution, occupational hygiene and human biological monitoring. A fully equipped laboratory to perform analytical chemistry including the following analytical instruments: TD-GCMS 8890-5977, GC-MS 7890A -5975C, GC-MS 6890N-5975, GC-MS/MS 9000-7010B, HPLC 1260 Infinity, UPLC-MS/MS, ICP-MS 7700, ICP-MS 7900, GC-QToF 8890-7250, LC-ICP-MS/MS-8900	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	100-1.000
Luxembourg	State of the art infrastructure and technical equipment that are used for the evaluation of indoor pollution, occupational hygiene and human biological monitoring. A fully equipped laboratory to perform analytical chemistry including the following analytical instruments: TD-GCMS 8890-5977, GC-MS 7890A -5975C, GC-MS 6890N-5975, GC-MS/MS 9000-7010B, HPLC 1260 Infinity, UPLC-MS/MS, ICP-MS 7700, ICP-MS 7900, GC-QToF 8890-7250, LC-ICP-MS/MS-8900	Environmental samples	0-100
Luxembourg	LC-MS/MS, GC-MS/MS etc	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100
Luxembourg	LC-MS/MS, GC-MS/MS etc	Environmental samples	0-100
Netherlands	LC-HRMS, qTOF equipped with APCI and ESI ionization modes. GC-HRMS GCxGC-MS Pyr/GC-MS	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100
Netherlands	LC-HRMS, qTOF equipped with APCI and ESI ionization modes. GC-HRMS GCxGC-MS Pyr/GC-MS	Environmental samples	0-100
Netherlands	LC-MS/MS (Waters, Sciex), LC-Q-trap-MS/MS (Sciex), LC-Q-Orbitrap HRMS (from classic to IQ-X), GC-MS/MS (Agilent), GC-Orbitrap-HRMS; ICP-MS/MS, ICP-MS (also combined with chromatography for element speciation) Equipment of measurement of radionuclides [would need to go after the details, but includes gamma, beta, alfa] BSL-2 laboratory Laboratory infrastructure to facilitate sample pretreatment (homogenisation/aliquotation), sample extraction & cleanup, manual and (semi)automated (96-well plate, microSPE) -80C and -18C storage facilities	food & feed	100-1.000
Netherlands	LC-MS/MS (Waters, Sciex), LC-Q-trap-MS/MS (Sciex), LC-Q-Orbitrap HRMS (from classic to IQ-X), GC-MS/MS (Agilent), GC-Orbitrap-HRMS; ICP-MS/MS, ICP-MS (also combined with chromatography for element speciation) Equipment of measurement of radionuclides [would need to go after the details, but includes gamma, beta, alfa]	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100

	BSL-2 laboratory Laboratory infrastructure to facilitate sample pretreatment (homogenisation/aliquotation), sample extraction & cleanup, manual and (semi)automated (96-well plate, microSPE) -80C and -18C storage facilities		
Netherlands	LC-MS/MS (Waters, Sciex), LC-Q-trap-MS/MS (Sciex), LC-Q-Orbitrap HRMS (from classic to IQ-X), GC-MS/MS (Agilent), GC-Orbitrap-HRMS; ICP-MS/MS, ICP-MS (also combined with chromatography for element speciation) Equipment of measurement of radionuclides [would need to go after the details, but includes gamma, beta, alfa] BSL-2 laboratory Laboratory infrastructure to facilitate sample pretreatment (homogenisation/aliquotation), sample extraction & cleanup, manual and (semi)automated (96-well plate, microSPE) -80C and -18C storage facilities	Environmental samples	0-100
Netherlands		Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100
Netherlands	Workcell for automated sample handling, several LC-HRMS instruments and LC-MS/MS instruments and a GC-Orbitrap MS. Also there is a research lab with LC and MS instruments for innovative exposome research.	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	100-1.000
Netherlands	Workcell for automated sample handling, several LC-HRMS instruments and LC-MS/MS instruments and a GC-Orbitrap MS. Also there is a research lab with LC and MS instruments for innovative exposome research.	Environmental samples	0-100
Norway	LC and GC-mass spectrometry	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	>10.000
Slovakia	Analytical laboratories at Slovak Medical University in Bratislava with long years of expertise in the field of determination of toxic substances in food, feed, human samples (serum, breast milk) and environmental samples. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (Thermo XSeries 2); Flame atomic absorption spectrometer (Varian AA240FS) with deuterium background correction Flameless atomic absorption spectrometer (Varian AA280Z) with graphite furnace and Zeeman background correction Microwave accelerated reaction system (CEM MarsXpress) High Performance Microwave Digestion System Milestone MLS 1200 MEGA UV Water Purification System High-resolution mass spectrometer combined with two gas chromatographs (Thermo Fisher Scientific) for target analysis of persistent organic pollutants. Chemical laboratories equipped with manual and semi-automated extraction systems and devices for sample preparation, extraction, clean-up and fractionation of different groups of substances.	Food and feed	0-100
Slovakia	Analytical laboratories at Slovak Medical University in Bratislava with long years of expertise in the field of determination of toxic substances in food, feed, human samples (serum, breast milk) and environmental samples. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (Thermo XSeries 2); Flame atomic absorption spectrometer (Varian AA240FS) with deuterium background correction Flameless atomic absorption spectrometer (Varian AA280Z) with graphite furnace and Zeeman background correction Microwave accelerated reaction system (CEM MarsXpress) High Performance Microwave Digestion System Milestone MLS 1200 MEGA UV Water Purification System High-resolution mass spectrometer combined with two gas chromatographs (Thermo Fisher Scientific) for target analysis of persistent organic pollutants. Chemical laboratories equipped with manual and semi-automated extraction systems and devices for sample preparation, extraction, clean-up and fractionation of different groups of substances.	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100

Slovakia	<p>Analytical laboratories at Slovak Medical University in Bratislava with long years of expertise in the field of determination of toxic substances in food, feed, human samples (serum, breast milk) and environmental samples.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (Thermo XSeries 2); Flame atomic absorption spectrometer (Varian AA240FS) with deuterium background correction Flameless atomic absorption spectrometer (Varian AA280Z) with graphite furnace and Zeeman background correction Microwave accelerated reaction system (CEM MarsXpress) High Performance Microwave Digestion System Milestone MLS 1200 MEGA UV Water Purification System <p>High-resolution mass spectrometer combined with two gas chromatographs (Thermo Fisher Scientific) for target analysis of persistent organic pollutants.</p> <p>Chemical laboratories equipped with manual and semi-automated extraction systems and devices for sample preparation, extraction, clean-up and fractionation of different groups of substances.</p>	Environmental samples	0-100
Slovakia	HPLC-MS/MS, HRMS	humine analyses	0-100
Slovakia	HPLC-MS/MS, HRMS	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100
Slovenia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Isotope ratio mass spectrometers (IRMS): Europa Scientific 20-20 stable isotope analyzer with ANCA-SL and ANCA-TG preparation modules for solid, liquid and gas samples; IsoPrime100 - Vario PYRO Cube (OH/CNS Pyrolyser/Elemental Analyser); Isoprime GV with gas chromatography and combustion unit for stable isotope analyses of organic compound (GC-C-IRMS) Mass spectrometers for identification and analysis of organic compounds – target, non-target analysis: GC-MSD, LC-QToF, LC-QTrap, GC-IT-MS, UHPLC-HRMS(/MS) - Orbitrap Multicollector ICP-MS (Nu Instruments) for stable isotope analysis of trace elements Mass spectrometers for speciation and elemental analysis: ICP-MS (Agilent 7500 series), ICP-MS QQQ, Laser ablation ICP-MS Mercury analysis and speciation: Cold vapour atomic absorption spectrometry (CV AAS, detector Milton Roy, Model 1255, two systems); Cold vapour atomic fluorescence spectrometry (CV AFS, detector Tekran, model 2500) with double amalgamation system and Hg vapour calibration system; Cold vapour atomic fluorescence spectrometry (CV AFS, two systems with Brooks Rand detectors); Direct Mercury Analyzer (DMA 80 – Milestone Microwave Laboratory Systems) 	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100
Slovenia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Isotope ratio mass spectrometers (IRMS): Europa Scientific 20-20 stable isotope analyzer with ANCA-SL and ANCA-TG preparation modules for solid, liquid and gas samples; IsoPrime100 - Vario PYRO Cube (OH/CNS Pyrolyser/Elemental Analyser); Isoprime GV with gas chromatography and combustion unit for stable isotope analyses of organic compound (GC-C-IRMS) Mass spectrometers for identification and analysis of organic compounds – target, non-target analysis: GC-MSD, LC-QToF, LC-QTrap, GC-IT-MS, UHPLC-HRMS(/MS) - Orbitrap Multicollector ICP-MS (Nu Instruments) for stable isotope analysis of trace elements Mass spectrometers for speciation and elemental analysis: ICP-MS (Agilent 7500 series), ICP-MS QQQ, Laser ablation ICP-MS Mercury analysis and speciation: Cold vapour atomic absorption spectrometry (CV AAS, detector Milton Roy, Model 1255, two systems); Cold vapour atomic fluorescence spectrometry (CV AFS, detector Tekran, model 2500) with double amalgamation system and Hg vapour calibration system; Cold vapour atomic fluorescence spectrometry (CV AFS, two systems with Brooks Rand detectors); Direct Mercury Analyzer (DMA 80 – Milestone Microwave Laboratory Systems) 	Environmental samples	0-100
Slovenia	<p>Laboratories at the Faculty of Pharmacy (UL FFA) are fully equipped with instrumentation for organic synthesis, analysis of synthetic products and PADMET evaluation: NMR spectrometer Bruker AVANCE III 400 MHz; Microplate reader TECAN Sapphire II; Multi-Mode Microplate Reader (SINERGY H4) and robot for automatic pipetting (PRECISION XS); EliSpot/FuoroSpot Reader, ELR08IFL; Nano ITC system for microcalorimetry TA Instruments; FT-IR spectrometer Perkin Elmer Spectrum BX; Polarimeter Perkin-Elmer 241 MCHPLC Agilent Technologies 1100 ;Gas chromatograph with mass selective detector Shimadzu GCMS-QP2010 Ultra; Ultra HPLC with triple quadrupole tandem MS spectrometer (UHPLC/MS/MS) Agilent 6460; Chromatographic system ÄKTAexplorer 10 S 82.427 Thermo Vanquish Duo UHPLC</p>	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100

	<p>system with double LC s Corona™ Veo™ RS Charged Aerosol detector (HRMS compatible); High resolution mass spectrometer HPLC-HRMS Exactive Plus Orbitrap Mass Spectrometer – Thermo (resolution 140.000) coupled with UHPLC Thermo Ultimate 3000; HPLC-MS Advion CMSL single quadropol (coupled with HPLC 1260 InfinityII and Advion reader for TLC-MS); UHPLC-MS Agilent 6545XT AdvanceBIO Q-ToF (coupled with 1290 Infinity II), Thermo Vanquish Duo UHPLC system with double LC s Corona™ Veo™ RS Charged Aerosol detector (HRMS compatible); UHPLC Thermo Ultimate 3000; Workstation with two 14-core Intel Xeon Gold 5120, 48 GB RAM-a, 1 TB SSD, 8 TB HDD in graphic card RTX 2080 Ti 9.000 (structure-based drug design software: Autodock, FlexX, Gold, eHiTS, ROCS, etc.); Imaging flow cytometer, Amnis ImageStreamX Mk II; BD FACSCalibur Flow Cytometer; Flow cytometer Attune NxT, Life Technologies; Raman Spectrometer - Confocal Raman Atomic Force Microscope XploRA PLUS-OmegaScope; Confocal mycroscope Axio Observer Z1; Next generation sequencer, MiSeq, Illumina 141.925 Sequencer, Genome Lab GeXP, Beckman Coulter 95.302 qPCR system, Light Cycler 480, Roche 47.439 qPCR system ABI PRISM Nucleic Acid PrepStation 80.652 Automated Platform for Live Cell Imaging; Transgenomic WAVE MD dHPLC SISTEM Plus; Biobanking system, Arpege, PHCBi; Biotage Isolera flash chromatograpy system; Parr 4560 mini bench top reactor; Chromatotron 7924T Harrison Research circular chromatography system; Discover (CEM Corporation) microwave synthesis system.</p> <p>The Faculty of Pharmacy also has three fully equipped cell laboratories.</p> <p>The researchers have direct access to the equipment, infrastructure and expertise of two infrastructure centers operating at the Faculty of Pharmacy: EATRIS Slovenia (https://www.ffa.uni-lj.si/en/faculty/organization/Infrastructural-centres/eatris-slovenia) and Infrastructural Center for Drug Analysis (https://www.ffa.uni-lj.si/en/research/research-equipment/0/infrastructural-center-for-drug-analysis).</p>		
Slovenia	<p>Laboratories at the Faculty of Pharmacy (UL FFA) are fully equipped with instrumentation for organic synthesis, analysis of synthetic products and PADMET evaluation: NMR spectrometer Bruker AVANCE III 400 MHz; Microplate reader TECAN Sapphire II; Multi-Mode Microplate Reader (SINERGY H4) and robot for automatic pipetting (PRECISION XS); EliSpot/FluoroSpot Reader, ELR08IFL; Nano ITC system for microcalorimetry TA Instruments; FT-IR spectrometer Perkin Elmer Spectrum BX; Polarimeter Perkin-Elmer 241 MCHPLC Agilent Technologies 1100 ;Gass chromatograph with mass selective detector Shimadzu GCMS-QP2010 Ultra; Ultra HPLC with triple quadropole tandem MS spectrometer (UHPLC/MS/MS) Agilent 6460; Chromatographic system ÄKTAexplorer 10 S 82.427 Thermo Vanquish Duo UHPLC system with double LC s Corona™ Veo™ RS Charged Aerosol detector (HRMS compatible); High resolution mass spectrometer HPLC-HRMS Exactive Plus Orbitrap Mass Spectrometer – Thermo (resolution 140.000) coupled with UHPLC Thermo Ultimate 3000; HPLC-MS Advion CMSL single quadropol (coupled with HPLC 1260 InfinityII and Advion reader for TLC-MS); UHPLC-MS Agilent 6545XT AdvanceBIO Q-ToF (coupled with 1290 Infinity II), Thermo Vanquish Duo UHPLC system with double LC s Corona™ Veo™ RS Charged Aerosol detector (HRMS compatible); UHPLC Thermo Ultimate 3000; Workstation with two 14-core Intel Xeon Gold 5120, 48 GB RAM-a, 1 TB SSD, 8 TB HDD in graphic card RTX 2080 Ti 9.000 (structure-based drug design software: Autodock, FlexX, Gold, eHiTS, ROCS, etc.); Imaging flow cytometer, Amnis ImageStreamX Mk II; BD FACSCalibur Flow Cytometer; Flow cytometer Attune NxT, Life Technologies; Raman Spectrometer - Confocal Raman Atomic Force Microscope XploRA PLUS-OmegaScope; Confocal mycroscope Axio Observer Z1; Next generation sequencer, MiSeq, Illumina 141.925 Sequencer, Genome Lab GeXP, Beckman Coulter 95.302 qPCR system, Light Cycler 480, Roche 47.439 qPCR system ABI PRISM Nucleic Acid PrepStation 80.652 Automated Platform for Live Cell Imaging; Transgenomic WAVE MD dHPLC SISTEM Plus; Biobanking system, Arpege, PHCBi; Biotage Isolera flash chromatograpy system; Parr 4560 mini bench top reactor; Chromatotron 7924T Harrison Research circular chromatography system; Discover (CEM Corporation) microwave synthesis system.</p> <p>The Faculty of Pharmacy also has three fully equipped cell laboratories.</p> <p>The researchers have direct access to the equipment, infrastructure and expertise of two infrastructure centers operating at the Faculty of Pharmacy: EATRIS Slovenia (https://www.ffa.uni-lj.si/en/faculty/organization/Infrastructural-centres/eatris-slovenia) and Infrastructural Center for Drug Analysis (https://www.ffa.uni-lj.si/en/research/research-equipment/0/infrastructural-center-for-drug-analysis).</p>	Environmental samples	0-100
Sweden	<p>3 LC-MS/MS 1 GC-MS 1 GC-MS/MS 1 LC-HRMS 1 EDA platform</p>	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	0-100

	3 sample preparation labs for environmental matrices (water, soil, sediment, air) and biological specimens matrices (serum, plasma, tissues, organs)		
Sweden	3 LC-MS/MS 1 GC-MS 1 GC-MS/MS 1 LC-HRMS 1 EDA platform 3 sample preparation labs for environmental matrices (water, soil, sediment, air) and biological specimens matrices (serum, plasma, tissues, organs)	Environmental samples	100-1.000
Sweden	Equipment and facilities for mass spectrometric analysis of trace pollutants and other xenobiotics, including non-target and suspect screening (LC/GC/SFC-qToFMS, APGC-qToFMS, LC-QqQ, GC-MS, TDU-GC-OrbitrapMS). Entire workflow from extraction to data analysis.	Biological specimens collected for TD-GC analysis (e.g., breath biopsy)	0-100
Sweden	Equipment and facilities for mass spectrometric analysis of trace pollutants and other xenobiotics, including non-target and suspect screening (LC/GC/SFC-qToFMS, APGC-qToFMS, LC-QqQ, GC-MS, TDU-GC-OrbitrapMS). Entire workflow from extraction to data analysis.	Environmental samples collected for TD-GC analysis (e.g., air samples)	0-100
Sweden	Equipment and facilities for mass spectrometric analysis of trace pollutants and other xenobiotics, including non-target and suspect screening (LC/GC/SFC-qToFMS, APGC-qToFMS, LC-QqQ, GC-MS, TDU-GC-OrbitrapMS). Entire workflow from extraction to data analysis.	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	100-1.000
Sweden	Equipment and facilities for mass spectrometric analysis of trace pollutants and other xenobiotics, including non-target and suspect screening (LC/GC/SFC-qToFMS, APGC-qToFMS, LC-QqQ, GC-MS, TDU-GC-OrbitrapMS). Entire workflow from extraction to data analysis.	Environmental samples	100-1.000
Sweden	Equipment and facilities for mass spectrometric analysis of trace pollutants, including three LC-MS/MS systems, SFC-MS/MS, LC/SFC/GC-qToFMS, GC-MS and GC-OrbitrapMS. Entire workflow from extraction to data analysis.	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	100-1.000
Sweden	Equipment and facilities for mass spectrometric analysis of trace pollutants, including three LC-MS/MS systems, SFC-MS/MS, LC/SFC/GC-qToFMS, GC-MS and GC-OrbitrapMS. Entire workflow from extraction to data analysis.	Environmental samples	100-1.000
Sweden	Positive pressure clean laboratory for sample processing, and adjacent mass spectrometry facility, currently housing three orbitrap mass spectrometers: 1. GC-Q Exactive 2. LC-Q Exactive HFX with in-line SPE 3. LC Exploris 480	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	100-1.000
Sweden	Positive pressure clean laboratory for sample processing, and adjacent mass spectrometry facility, currently housing three orbitrap mass spectrometers: 1. GC-Q Exactive 2. LC-Q Exactive HFX with in-line SPE 3. LC Exploris 480	Environmental samples	100-1.000
Sweden	We have an instrument park of 5 triple quadrupole mass spectrometers dedicated to quantification of exogenous and endogenous compounds. This is accompanied by dedicated sample processing laboratory (BSL2) and robotic sample preparation equipment.	Biological specimens (e.g. plasma)	100-1.000
Sweden	We have an instrument park of 5 triple quadrupole mass spectrometers dedicated to quantification of exogenous and endogenous compounds. This is accompanied by dedicated sample processing laboratory (BSL2) and robotic sample preparation equipment.	Environmental samples	0-100

Annex 4a Descriptions of service 4

Description regarding measurements of omics-based analysis of markers of biological response.	Description physical infrastructure	Changes that might occur	Country
Type of omics: LC-MS/MS metabolomics Matrices: plasma, serum, tissue Markers: endogenous metabolites Other info: e.g. qualitative	See Service 3	Service will be made open access within the next 5 years (no FTE at the current stage)	Austria
Type of omics: LC-MS/MS metabolomics Matrices: plasma, serum, urine, tissue, cell culture. Markers: targeted and non-targeted analysis of metabolites, including amino acids, acyl carnitines, bile acids, sugars, organic acids, nucleotides. Other info: qualitative and quantitative analysis employing different kinds of mass spectrometer (Orbitrap Exploris 240, Thermo; TripleTOF 5600+, Sciex; QTrap 6500+, Sciex, Xevo TQ-XS, Waters)	The primary mission of the Core Facility Metabolomics of the Medical University of Innsbruck is to serve as an enabling resource for research and development programs at local, national and international level. The Core Facility Mass Spectrometry provides expertise and state-of-the-art technologies for the qualitative and quantitative analysis of small bioorganic molecules. The Core Facility Metabolomics is equipped with two high-resolution mass spectrometers (Orbitrap Exploris 240, Thermo; TripleTof 5600+, Sciex) and two low-resolution mass spectrometers (QTrap 6500+, Sciex, Xevo TQ-XS, Waters). All necessary devices for processing biological and environmental samples are available.	Extended analysis service (e.g., coverage of additional compound classes)	Austria
LC-MS/MS metabolomics. Quantitative target analysis of biomarkers of effect with the following applications: - target analyses of polar metabolites in urine and blood (metabolomics) - target analyses of relevant lipid species in blood (lipidomics)		Tender will be launched in Jan 2024, we expect to have the infrastructure operational by September 2024. When operative, the infrastructure will include: liquid chromatograph triple quadrupole vacuum pumps nitrogen generator PC and software for data acquisition and for qualitative and quantitative data analysis	Belgium
LC-MS/MS targeted and untargeted proteomics and OLINK targeted proteomics, qualitative and quantitative. Samples: liquid biopsies (human, animal, plant), in vitro samples, tissues	LC-MS/MS: several state-of-the-art platforms (Bruker TIMS-TOF Pro coupled to EvoSep-LC, Thermo Qexactive Plus) OLINK: Target 96 & Target 48 (Human & Mouse)		Belgium
Metabolomics with focus on mycotoxins & EDC's in water		Both skills and capacity will increase.	Belgium
*LC/MS/MS based detection of DNA methylation and hydroxymethylation *Sequence specific DNA methylation-pyrosequencing we do not do the "omics" end points. We often hire a service to do that -Exposure assessment service catalogue- https://lamh.be/en			Belgium

<p>GC-MS/MS metabolomics in urine and saliva Biomarkers of exposure to xenobiotics Biomarkers of effect (oxidative stress and inflammation)</p>	<p>GC-MS/MS Agilent</p>	<p>addition of proteomics</p>	<p>Cyprus</p>
<p>Quantitative analysis of proteins in human blood samples Quantitative analysis of metabolites in human blood samples Profiling of metabolites in human blood samples</p>	<p>GC-Q GC-HRMS (Orbitrap Exploris 240 - one shared with exogenous) LC-PDA duoLC-Orbitrap Exploris 480 - shared with exogenous duoLC-Orbitrap Fusion - shared with exogenous LC-QqQ 2*low flow LC-QqQ</p>	<p>Increased number of assays/analytes available for quantification</p>	<p>Czech Republic</p>
<p>Type of omics: metagenomics (preparation of library for 16S/ITS rRNA amplicon sequencing, Shotgun sequencing, multiplex qPCR) Matrices: human, animal, and environmental samples Markers: both targeted as untargeted analysis of microbial DNA Other info: qualitative and quantitative analyses, bioinformatical analysis The Microbiome Laboratories (MGL) is a specialized research facility that provides advanced resources and expertise to support the analysis of microbial communities in various biological systems. This facility offers a range of services to researchers, including sample processing, NA extraction, preparation of sequencing library. Our core facility is staffed by expert molecular geneticists and microbiologists who work with researchers to design experiments that generate high-quality microbiome data. The facility's experts are proficient in a wide range of microbiome analysis techniques, including 16S and ITS rRNA gene sequencing, shotgun metagenomics, and target microbial species or gene analysis. The facility also provides support for sample collection and processing, including optimization of sampling protocols, and quality control checks. The MGL core facility plays a critical role in advancing our understanding of the microbial communities that inhabit various ecosystems, including the human body, animals, models (organoids, biofilms), and environmental samples (soil, water, dust, etc.). By providing expert support and resources, this facility helps researchers to analyze microbiome data, identify microbial communities, and understand their roles in various biological systems. Ultimately, this work can lead to insights into the prevention and treatment of various diseases and improvements in environmental management practices. MGL provides state-of-the-art infrastructure, expert support, and service for a wide range of genomics applications to internal and external customers. This is a new core facility at the RECETOX Research Infrastructure primarily focuses</p>	<p>Our laboratories are fully equipped, we disposed with the molecular biological laboratories (laminar flow-boxes, thermocyclers, equipment for gel electrophoresis, UV-Vis spectrophotometers, imaging systems, centrifuges and others), as well as with the microbiological laboratory (incubator, microscope etc.). We have direct access to Real Time PCR systems at RECETOX; our lab collaborate with sequencing core facilities that have NGS technologies (Illumina NovaSeq equipment etc.), however, we can also use the massive parallel sequencers Illumina NextSeq and MiSeq equipment and Bioanalyzer or TapeStation at Masaryk University.</p>	<p>Introduction of new methodological approaches.</p>	<p>Czech Republic</p>

on the analysis of microbial genome in the environmental, animal, and human samples, however, we are able to do also genomic analysis of human DNA and RNA.			
LC-MS/MS proteomics, NGS , O-link, MRI	In collaboration with Department of Biology, AU		Denmark
Type of omics: LC-MS/MS proteomics Matrices: plasma, in vitro samples, in vivo samples from tissue, metaproteomics from microbiome samples Markers: both targeted and untargeted proteins Other info: e.g. qualitative and quantitative, type of equipment 3x LC-Orbitrap Type of omics: LC-MS/MS metabolomics Matrices: plasma, in vitro samples, in vivo samples from tissue, (meta)metabolomics from microbiome samples Markers: both targeted and untargeted proteins Other info: e.g. qualitative and quantitative, type of equipment 3x qtraps, 1 Orbitrap, 2 gc-MS/MS	ProMetheus platform for proteomics and metabolomics at UFZ: https://www.ufz.de/index.php?de=48839		Germany
Type of omics: microLC-QTOF-MS metabolomics Matrices: blood plasma, urine, fecal extract, breast milk, human amniotic fluid Markers: both targeted and untargeted metabolites Other info: Qualitative and quantitative, Type of instrument: microLC-tripleTOF MS, Analytical LC-tripleTOF MS	EKSPERT nanoLC400 EKSIGENT with Triple TOF SCIEX6600+_with _ SCIEX SelexION WATERS ACQUITY ULTRA PERFORMANCE _LC with Triple TOF SCIEX6600+_with _ SCIEX SelexION SHIMADJOU QP2010 series GC-MS	Initiation of lipidomics studies	Greece
ype of omics to be explored by UTH: Epigenomics / transcriptomics, metagenomics / microbiomics, and metabolomics. Matrices: water column, soil / sediment, feces, urine, whole blood, animal tissue, plant tissue, animal products (milk, eggs, etc). Markers: e-DNA, targeted group genes differential expression, pathogen DNA/RNA, RNA sequencing, e-DNA whole genome analysis, genes relevant to antibiotic resistance through microarray, DNA methylation tails. An important part of this activity will concern antimicrobial resistance. In this case, investigation will be initiated with classical microbiology methods. In particular samples will be cultivated on appropriate culture media, following pre-enrichment – if necessary. Culture media will be selected according to sample type and possible pathogens present on the sample (e.g. ISO 6579-1:2017 for the detection, enumeration and serotyping of Salmonella spp.). Bacterial isolated will followingly be subjected to identification (Vitek 2) and susceptibility testing via phenotypic methods. More	Please describe the available physical infrastructure (technology/instrumentation) The VITEK 2 system, which is an instrument that provides fast, accurate microbial identification, and antibiotic susceptibility testing. Microbial identification and antimicrobial susceptibility (AST) testing are performed with an expanded identification database, the most automated platform available, rapid results, improved confidence, with minimal labor time. The VITEK 2 system provides greater automation while increasing safety and eliminating repetitive manual operations. The rapid response time means results can be provided more quickly than with manual microbial identification and AST techniques. It analyzes MIC patterns and detects resistance phenotypes. Thermocycler for gene amplification via PCR, a multifunctional, multipurpose PCR instrument, that can meet the requirements of different PCR reaction tube, different number of holes and the different types of PCR experiments with		Greece

<p>precisely, the disk diffusion test and/or broth dilution will be applied. Phenotypic antimicrobial resistance will, moreover, be evaluated using automated systems (Vitek 2). Finally, resistance mechanisms will be molecularly defined conducting bacterial DNA extraction and PCR. For the detection of viral pathogens, DNA or RNA extraction will be carried out on the samples, based on the genome of the suspected virus. Amplification of a targeted segment of the nucleic acid of the virus will then be performed by PCR.</p>	<p>dynamic display of time and temperature.</p>		
<p>Type of omics: LC-MS/MS proteomics and Q-FISH metabolomics Matrices: Plasma, urine, hair and other biological matrices Markers: Targeted and untargeted proteins (i.e., telomerase, shelterin complex) telomeres Info: Qualitative and quantitative analysis</p>	<p>Infrastructure for Q-FISH analysis of telomeres (microscope, hood, cell culture incubator etc.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chromatographic systems (LC/MS/MS, LC-MS, GC/MS, GC, HPLC) • Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry system (ICP-MS) • Automated high performance liquid chromatography (TOXIS) • fully automated immunoassay systems analysis ELISA spectrophotometers • Molecular techniques systems (PCR, Capillary Electrophoresis) • System immunofluorescence 	<p>Evolution and establishment state-of-the-art protocols for holistic analysis on the regulation of telomeres, telomerase, shelterin and interconnected molecular pathways as a biomarker of effect.</p>	<p>Greece</p>
<p>Type of omics: UPLC- MS/MS metabolomics Matrices: urine, serum, plasma, in vitro samples, in vivo samples (D.rerio) Markers: untargeted (polar & unpolar metabolites, lipids) Other info: ü Agilent 6540 HRMS-QTOF/ LC-MS/MS system analysis with multiple analytical columns (Reversed Phase & HILIC) ü LTQ Orbitrap Velos Pro (Thermo Scientific)</p> <p>Type of omics: NMR metabolomics Matrices: urine, serum, plasma Markers: untargeted Other info: 600 MHz Varian spectrometer</p> <p>Type of omics: GC-MS metabolomics Matrices: urine Markers: untargeted Other info: GC/MS-MS/QTOF Agilent Technologies 7200A</p> <p>Type of omics: LC- MS/MS metabolomics Matrices: urine, serum, plasma, in vitro samples, in vivo samples (D.rerio) Markers: targeted (SPLASH® LIPIDOMIX® & MSMLSä (Mass Spectrometry Metabolite Library) Other info: • Thermo Scientific TSQ Vantage LC-MS/MS • Trace GC Ultra Thermo, TSQuantum XLS.</p> <p>Type of omics: Transcriptomics Matrices: blood, in vitro samples, in vivo samples (D.rerio) Markers: microarray Other info: Agilent SureScan Microarray</p>	<p>Ø Internal exposome Analytical infrastructure: Equipped with benches, hoods, and specialized equipment for sample preparation, metabolites extraction, and RNA extraction.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GC/MS-MS/QTOF Agilent Technologies 7200A • LC/MS-MS/QTOF Agilent Technologies 1290-6540 UHD • LC/MS-MS Thermo Scientific Orbitrap • LC/MS-MS Thermo Scientific Q Exactive Focus Orbitrap • Thermo Scientific TSQ Vantage LC-MS/MS • Trace GC Ultra Thermo, TSQuantum XLS. • ICP-MS • Triple Quadrupole LC-MS • Triple Quadrupole LC-MS • NMR 600 MHz Agilent Technologies PremiumCOMPACT • Microarray Scanner Agilent Technologies SureScanUltra • RT-PCR Agilent Technologies G8830A • Thermal Cycler Agilent Technologies 8800 PCR • Tape station system Agilent Technologies 2200 • Sample concentrator TECHNE FSC496D • Small Prime Centrifuge refrigerated Centurion Scientific K2015R • Semi-Micro Balances Adam Equipment ABL 225 • Class II Biological Safety Chamber Biobase BSC-1300IIB2-X • Deep freezer (-80 oC) of 700 lt for storage of biological samples • Illumina/ MGI 99 technology 	<p>Addition of an instrument for RNA-seq analysis.</p>	<p>Greece</p>

<p>Scanner™ (G2600, Agilent Technologies, Inc., USA)</p>	<p>Ø IT infrastructure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High powered, networked computing facilities and web servers and teaching/workshop space. • 40TB server shelf hosted by the IT AUTH Center; Consists of several VMs for different projects. • 8 high-end PCs • 6 high-end laptops 		
<p>Type of omics: UHPLC- MS metabolomics Matrices: urine, serum, plasma, in vitro samples, in vivo samples Markers: untargeted, targeted Other info: ü UHPLC - LTQ Orbitrap Velos, Thermo Scientific ü HPLC-LCQ Fleet / Thermo Scientific Type of omics: NMR metabolomics Matrices: urine, serum, plasma, in vitro samples, in vivo samples Markers: untargeted, targeted Other info: ü Varian V600 MHz, ü Varian V300 MHz, ü Varian V400 MHz Solid state Type of omics: GS – MS/MS metabolomics Matrices: urine, serum, plasma, in vitro samples, in vivo samples Markers: targeted</p> <p>Other info: Varian Saturn 2000 GC-MS-MS System</p> <p>Type of omics: metagenomics/transcriptomics Matrices: In vitro, in vivo, ex vivo Aim: Identifying dietary factors with enhanced prebiotic activity given the development of novel food products which promote health and quality of life, of the elderly in particular.</p> <p>Other info: 16S Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS)</p> <p>Type of omics: Epigenomics (DNA methylation) Matrices: tissues and FFPE samples, as well as liquid biopsies. Other info: genome-wide screening methods (Illumina Infinium methylation EPIC beadchip) and locus- or gene-specific analysis (pyrosequencing)</p> <p>Multi-omics (LC-MSn) and high-resolution particle-by-particle 3D fluorescent microscopy (extracellular vesicles/exosomes; nature, number, cargos). The secretome and membrane proteome may add an extra information layer.</p>	<p>NMR Spectroscopy Facility</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Varian V600 MHz Magnet: 14.1 Tesla 54 mm bore Varian Superconducting Magnet Probes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $^1\text{H}\{^{13}\text{C}/^{15}\text{N}\}$ 5mm PFG Automatable Triple Resonance • $^1\text{H}\{^{15}\text{N}-^{31}\text{P}\}$ 5 mm PFG AutoX Indirect Detect 600 • $^1\text{H}-^{19}\text{F}/^{15}\text{N}-^{31}\text{P}$ 5mm PFG AutoX DB600 Applications: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single or double resonance studies to fully characterize organic compounds • DOSY pulse sequence for the separation of mixture components • Triple resonance experiments of chemical or biomolecular samples. Capability for ^1H observation with simultaneous or single irradiation of ^{13}C and ^{15}N frequencies. 2. Varian V300 MHz Magnet: 7 Tesla 52 mm bore Oxford Magnet Probe: $^1\text{H}/^{19}\text{F}/^{31}\text{P}/^{13}\text{C}$ 5mm PFG AutoSwitchable Application: Single or double resonance studies to fully characterize organic compounds 3. Varian V400 MHz Solid state Magnet: 9.4 Tesla WB 89 mm bore Oxford Magnet Probes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o 3.2 mm Double Resonance HX-Mas Solids probe o 25 KHz MAS spinning, ^{31}P to ^{15}N observe channel $^{19}\text{F}-^1\text{H}$ Decouple channel, 147 KHz decoupling strength Applications: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ^{13}C, ^{31}P MAS and CP-MAS with HP ^1H decoupling • Drug-membrane interactions • Determination of coordination states of ^{27}Al, ^{29}Si • Drug polymorphism studies • Characterization of other metal complexes <p>UHPLC - LTQ Orbitrap Velos, Thermo Scientific HPLC-LCQ Fleet / Thermo Scientific</p> <p>Varian Saturn 2000 GC-MS-MS System</p> <p>FACS ARIA II (BD): Multicolour high-speed cell sorter, equipped with 2 lasers (488, 633 nm) and 7 detectors to measure up to 7 fluorescent parameters.</p>	<p>New instruments have been purchased e.g. LC-TIMS-MS MALDI-ToF, new NMR, Cryo-EM suite (4), SACS, Multiple Sequencer</p>	<p>Greece</p>

	<p>The instrument is capable of the simultaneous sorting of four populations into tubes or plates.</p> <p>Analytical Laboratory Equipment Ø Gas Chromatography GC-Varian, 3400 CX Ø Two Spectra System HPLC instruments (Thermo Fisher Scientific) Ø FT IR spectrometer with ATR unit (Bruker-Tensor 27) Ø UV/VIS spectrometer (Varian) Ø Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC7, Perkin Elmer, Pyrex s/w) Ø Parallel synthesis apparatus, Syncore Buchi Ø Microwave reactors, CEM Ø Ultrasound reactor, (Sonics & Materials) Ø Pressure reactor (PARR) Ø Spinning band distillation apparatus</p> <p>16S Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS)</p> <p>genome-wide screening methods (Illumina InfiniummethylationEPICbeadchip)</p> <p>locus- or gene-specific analysis (pyrosequencing)</p>		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GC-MS and LC-MS-MS metabolomics • various matrices plasma, serum, various tissues (in cellular and animal models) - brain, heart, • mainly untargeted • quantitative (LCQ-MS ThermoFinnigan) - Tecan automatic liquid handler, Agilent GC-triple quad MS 	<p>ISO 9001:2015certified MS-based metabolomics laboratory - the first and currently only with this certification in Greece in Metabolomics and Bioinformatics Analyses at FORTH/ICE-HT</p>	<p>Additional Methods, but deterioration of Equipment with age (need for new equipment)</p>	<p>Greece</p>
<p>Epigenomics (human and mouse) for 5 methyl cytosine, 6-methyl adenine ATAC-Seq, Cut&tag. Matrix: anything containing DNA Analysis: EWAS, exposure effect identification</p>	<p>Illumina iScan, Illumina NextSeq Bioinformatics server with capacity to run epigenome wide studies with 2-3,000 sample</p>	<p>Increase in capacity and services available</p>	<p>Luxembourg</p>
<p>LC-MS/MS based lipidomics and metabolomics</p>	<p>Thermo Vanquish UHPLC – Thermo Orbitrap Exploris 240 MS</p> <p>Thermo Vanquish UHPLC – Thermo Q Exactive HF</p> <p>SCIEX Exion LC – SCIEX Triple Quad 7500 MS</p> <p>Agilent 1290 LC–Agilent 6560 MS Dionex ICS-6000 – Thermo Q Exactive MS</p> <p>Agilent 8890 GC–Agilent 5977B MS Agilent 7890B GC–Agilent 5977A MS https://www.uni.lu/lcsb-en/facilities/metabolomics/</p>		<p>Luxembourg</p>
<p>LC-MS/MS lipidomics and metabolomics (qTOF) Tissue imaging mass spectrometry. Matrices: plasma, in vitro samples, ex vivo samples. Markers: targeted and untargeted polar</p>	<p>LC-HRMS (qTOF, LC-MS/MS, MALDI-TOF)</p>	<p>Incorporation of new equipment and newer software and workflows for data analysis.</p>	<p>Netherlands</p>

metabolites and lipids. Other info: quantitative and qualitative.			
transcriptomics, metabolomics plasma and other biological matrices, e.g. fish mucus			Norway
Type of omics: Transcriptomics - targeted gene expression analysis Matrices: in vitro samples (human and animal cell lines, zebrafish embryos) Markers: targeted genes (using Taqman Gene Expression Assays) Other info: qualitative and quantitative equipment: RT-PCR (Real time PCR; LightCycler 480 (Roche), Viia 7 and QuantStudio 7 Flex Real (Applied Biosystems), qPCR cyclers ABI 7900 HT and ABI 7900HT Fast Sequence Detection System (Applied Biosystems), Droplet Digital PCR system QX100 and QX200 (BioRad), nanofluidic digital PCR; BioMark System (Fluidigm)	RT-PCR (Real time PCR; LightCycler 480 (Roche), Viia 7 and QuantStudio 7 Flex Real (Applied Biosystems), qPCR cyclers ABI 7900 HT and ABI 7900HT Fast Sequence Detection System (Applied Biosystems), Droplet Digital PCR system QX100 and QX200 (BioRad), nanofluidic digital PCR; BioMark System (Fluidigm)	Related to the service we already have: we expect to upgrade the current experimental approach and equipment. We expect also to follow the state-of- the-art trends and novelties in the field.	Slovenia
LC-MS/MS metabolomic Plasma, in vitro samples	Laboratories at the Faculty of Pharmacy (UL FFA) are fully equipped with instrumentation for organic synthesis, analysis of synthetic products and PADMET evaluation: NMR spectrometer Bruker AVANCE III 400 MHz; Microplate reader TECAN Sapphire II; Multi-Mode Microplate Reader (SINERGY H4) and robot for automatic pipetting (PRECISION XS); EliSpot/FluoroSpot Reader, ELR08IFL; Nano ITC system for microcalorimetry TA Instruments; FT-IR spectrometer Perkin Elmer Spectrum BX; Polarimeter Perkin-Elmer 241 MCHPLC Agilent Technologies 1100 ;Gass chromatograph with mass selective detector Shimadzu GCMS- QP2010 Ultra; Ultra HPLC with triple quadrupole tandem MS spectrometer (UHPLC/MS/MS) Agilent 6460; Chromatographic system ÄKTAexplorer 10 S 82.427 Thermo Vanquish Duo UHPLC system with double LC s Corona™ Veo™ RS Charged Aerosol detector (HRMS compatible); High resolution mass spectrometer HPLC- HRMS Exactive Plus Orbitrap Mass Spectrometer – Thermo (resolution 140.000) coupled with UHPLC Thermo Ultimate 3000; HPLC-MS Advion CMSL single quadropol (coupled with HPLC 1260 InfinityII and Advion reader for TLC-MS); UHPLC-MS Agilent 6545XT AdvanceBIO Q-ToF (coupled with 1290 Infinity II), Thermo Vanquish Duo UHPLC system with double LC s Corona™ Veo™ RS Charged Aerosol detector (HRMS compatible); UHPLC Thermo Ultimate 3000; Workstation with two 14-core Intel Xeon Gold 5120, 48 GB RAM-a, 1 TB SSD, 8 TB HDD in graphic card RTX 2080 Ti 9.000 (structure-based drug design software: Autodock, FlexX, Gold, eHiTS, ROCS, etc.); Imaging flow cytometer, Amnis ImageStreamX Mk II; BD FACSCalibur	Expansion of the Olink qPCR readout to NGS readout.	Slovenia

	<p>Flow Cytometer; Flow cytometer Attune NxT, Life Technologies; Raman Spectrometer - Confocal Raman Atomic Force Microscope XploRA PLUS-OmegaScope; Confocal microscope Axio Observer Z1; Next generation sequencer, MiSeq, Illumina 141.925 Sequencer, Genome Lab GeXP, Beckman Coulter 95.302 qPCR system, Light Cycler 480, Roche 47.439 qPCR system ABI PRISM Nucleic Acid PrepStation 80.652 Automated Platform for Live Cell Imaging; Transgenomic WAVE MD dHPLC SISTEM Plus; Biobanking system, Arpege, PHCBI; Biotage Isolera flash chromatography system; Parr 4560 mini bench top reactor; Chromatotron 7924T Harrison Research circular chromatography system; Discover (CEM Corporation) microwave synthesis system.</p> <p>The Faculty of Pharmacy also has three fully equipped cell laboratories.</p> <p>The researchers have direct access to the equipment, infrastructure and expertise of two infrastructure centers operating at the Faculty of Pharmacy: EATRIS Slovenia (https://www.ffa.uni-lj.si/en/faculty/organization/Infrastructural-centres/eatris-slovenia) and Infrastructural Center for Drug Analysis (https://www.ffa.uni-lj.si/en/research/research-equipment/0/infrastructural-center-for-drug-analysis).</p>		
<p>a) Metabolomics/Exposomics platform: MS-based approaches; non-target analysis of biological samples using LC-qToF. Different methods for analysis of polar, semi-polar, and non-polar metabolites in combination with analysis of environmental pollutants. Approaches for human/animal metabolism including gut microbiota functioning. In-house database with approx 900 metabolites and 600 analytical standards available for quantitation. Analysis of biological matrices. Possibility for sample prep automation. Fully integrated with data processing workflows.</p> <p>b) Lipidomics: Analysis of molecular lipids using LC-qToF. Identification of lipids using a custom database search (approx 500 metabolites). Calculation of lipids concentration based on lipid-class calibration curves. LC-fractionation can be employed for further concentration/purification/isolation of lipids species. Analysis of biological matrices. Possibility for sample prep automation. Fully integrated with data processing workflows.</p> <p>c) Volatomics (and air samples): analysis of breath biopsy and air samples using TDU-GC-Orbitrap. Non-targeted approach. Fully integrated with data processing workflows.</p>	<p>Multiple high-resolution LC-qToF-MS instruments for lipidomics and exposomics/metabolomics, and TDU-GC-Orbitrap for volatomics/air analysis. Database with approx 900 metabolites for metabolomics/exposomics and 600 analytical standards available for quantitation; 500 metabolites for measurement of lipid levels. Integration between data acquisition and data pre-processing. Robotic platform (Andrew Alliance) for sample prep. Full workflow from extraction to data analysis.</p>		Sweden

<p>LC-MS/MS proteomics Matrices: in any cell types, cell lysate, body fluids or tissues. Untargeted</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Platform for systematic identification of protein targets of chemicals in any cell types, cell lysate, body fluids or tissues. • Platform to predict toxicity of complex mixtures: Identification of target proteins is an unique opportunity to deconvolute the toxicity of complex mixtures. • Platform for environmental proteomic and ecotoxicoproteomics <p>EQUIPMENT:High Resolution Trapped Ion Mobility timsTOF HT, Q Exactive HF Hybrid Quadrupole-Orbitrap Mass Spectrometer,UltrafleXtreme MALDI system and LC separation and specific software for analysis.</p>	<p>EQUIPMENT:High Resolution Trapped Ion Mobility timsTOF HT, Q Exactive HF Hybrid Quadrupole-Orbitrap Mass Spectrometer,UltrafleXtreme MALDI system. In addition, lab for sample preparation, and LC separation, and specific software for analysis.</p>		<p>Sweden</p>
<p>Type of omics: LC-MS/MS metabolomics Matrices: plasma, serum, urine, cells (supernatant, extracts), tissue Markers: targeted methods for metabolites and lipids. These include targeted quantitative panels as well as broad qualitative screening methods.</p>	<p>We have a dedicated instrument park consisting of 5 triple quadrupoles (LC-MS/MS) that can be used for metabolomics and lipidomics analyses.</p>	<p>The breadth of the panels offered will continue to increase. In addition, new instrumentation will be acquired - increasing performance and sensitivity.</p>	<p>Sweden</p>

Annex 5a Specification of Service 05 Quantification/Determination of Toxicity

<p>VITO can offer several in vitro tests (endocrine disruption testing, skin sensitization, BCOP eye damage testing, 3D skin & eye irritation and corrosion, genotoxicity, inhalation exposure testing). VITO also offers zebra fish embryo testing as non-animal alternative for humane tox testing (teratogenicity, developmental neurotox, hepato tox). In terms of aquatic testing, we can offer OECD and ISO guideline testing with algae and waterflea, zebra fish embryo and bacteria (microtox). For in silico, VITO offers QSAR analysis (multiple models).</p>	Belgium
<p>In vitro assessment – Cyto-Genotoxicity testing Type of models: in vitro lung specific cell models, 3D spheroid culture, and trans well coculture model of lung toxicity. Type of samples: Particles, Nanoparticles, fibers, chemicals Mechanistic endpoints: Barrier function, cell proliferation, DNA damage, cell cycle progression</p>	Belgium
<p>Models: Human exposures Mechanistic Inflammation</p>	Denmark
<p>In vitro assessment – Safety and preclinical testing Type of models: in vitro high-throughput screening assays. In vitro organ specific cell models, 2D/3D organoids of liver/hepatotoxicity, gut and skin epithelia, kidney, reprotoxicity - testicular models Type of samples: chemicals, mixtures, matrices, water, sediment, biota, human tissues, blood Mechanistic endpoints: nuclear receptor reporter gene assays, cell proliferation, tumor promotion and progression, adaptive stress responses, developmental neurotoxicity, mitochondrial toxicity Other info: unique equipment; CITEPro Facility at UFZ for high-throughput in vitro assays (www.ufz.de/citepro) Models: in vitro organ specific cell models, cell models for liver/hepatotoxicity, cultivation of gut microbiota, immune cells, adipocytes, immune cell co-culture, placenta models (spheroids, organoids, explants -human), mammary gland organoids (mouse), ovary culture (mouse) Type of samples: single chemicals and mixture of chemicals Mechanistic endpoints: immune cell differentiation, immunotox, adipocyte differentiation and functionality, placenta functionality, branching of mammary gland, oocyte maturation states, nuclear receptors activity, chemicals-protein interaction, hepatocyte functionality, single cell analysis by transcriptomics and proteomics, intestinal microbiome functionality and effects on gut-liver and gut-brain axis, reprotox In vivo: mouse models for substance application (e. g. endocrine disruptors) and repro-toxicity outcome In vitro: 2D cell culture of various cell lines and primary cells for toxicological assays; 3D spheroid and organoid culture for toxicological assays Analysis of the impact of EDC mixtures and individual substances Endpoints: cell proliferation, cell behavior, cell migration and adhesion, organ functionality</p>	Germany
<p>Ecological toxicity testing Type of models: aquatic organisms Type of samples: chemicals, mixtures, water, activated sludge Mechanistic endpoints: Growth inhibition, acute immobilization, respiration inhibition</p>	Greece
<p>In silico assessment Type of models: Quantitative-Structure-Activity Relationships (QSAR), read-across models Type of substances: chemicals, mixtures, complex materials (nanomaterials) Predicted endpoints: QSAR models can predict a wide range of toxicological endpoints and effects, including but not limited to LD50 (Lethal Dose 50), LC50 (Lethal Concentration 50), NOAEL (No Observed Adverse Effect Level), IC50 (Inhibitory Concentration 50), and more. These models are applied to assess various types of toxicity, such as Respiratory and Dermal Sensitization, Genotoxicity and Mutagenicity, Carcinogenicity, Endocrine Disruption, Reproductive and Developmental Toxicity, Skin and Eye Irritation/Corrosion, and Aquatic Toxicity, among others. Other info: The models are available as user-friendly web services through our Jaqpot platform. They can be accessed via API calls in various environments, integrated with other models, and seamlessly incorporated into risk assessment workflows.</p>	Greece
<p>PBPK MODELING Toxicokinetic Modeling: Predictions of absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) of toxic substances in humans and wildlife. This includes developing custom PBPK models for new chemicals or pharmaceuticals. Custom Model Development for Novel Compounds: Development of PBPK models for new drugs or industrial chemicals, especially those lacking detailed experimental data. Machine learning towards pharmacokinetic parameters from chemical structure data.</p>	Greece

<p>SYSTEMS BIOLOGY</p> <p>Toxicological Pathway Analysis: Analysis of biochemical pathways to explore mechanisms of toxicity at a molecular level. This includes identifying potential biomarkers for early detection of toxic effects.</p> <p>High-Throughput Screening Data Analysis: Machine learning for analysis of large datasets from high-throughput screening of chemicals for toxicological effects, helping to prioritize chemicals for further testing and reduce the need for animal testing.</p> <p>Ecosystem Impact Modeling: Modeling of impact of toxic substances on ecosystems, predicting effects on different species and the interplay with environmental factors.</p> <p>Data-Driven Predictive Modeling for Drug-Induced Toxicity: Development predictive models for drug-induced liver injury, cardiotoxicity, or other specific organ toxicities, leveraging large datasets from preclinical and clinical studies.</p>	
<p>In silico toxicity assessment via the development to (Q)SAR models and grouping approaches.</p> <p>Type of models: QSAR models</p> <p>Type of materials: metallic and metal oxide nanomaterials, hybrid multicomponent metallic nanoparticles, metal-based chemicals</p> <p>Mechanistic endpoints: Various endpoints can be used for QSAR model development, including half-maximal concentrations (LC50, IC50, EC50), as long as sufficient endpoint data is available</p>	Greece
<p>In vitro/in vivo/ in silico/ clinical: Safety and preclinical testing for xenobiotics, new drug candidates, food additives /products etc.</p> <p>Type of models: in vitro cell cultures, animal facilities, PBPK tools, clinical samples</p> <p>Type of samples: biological samples (hair, blood, urine, tissues), in vitro matrices from cell cultures etc.</p> <p>Mechanistic endpoints: gene assays, ageing prediction, wellness evaluation models, pharmacokinetic predictions</p> <p>Certifications: ISO 9001</p>	Greece
<p>Toxicity quantification with advanced multidimensional QSARs (and QSPRs) which include hierarchical methods and mode of action methodologies. In house Python and R code has been developed for the introduction of QSARs. Cheminformatics libraries employed are the RDKit and the CDK.</p> <p>A549, HepaRG and primary cell cultures, in-vitro testing for cell proliferation and cell survival, DNA degradation, gene reporter assays and RNA-silencing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ex-vivo explant 3D mucosa models to test for chemical substance toxicity - Rat and zebrafish in-vivo models to test for chemical substance toxicity 	Greece
<p>ADME-Tox in 3D assays and services in a 3-tier strategy; in silico, in vitro, in vivo (EMA CHMP, FDA Guidance for Industry)</p> <p>3D cell microenvironment via profiling of extracellular vesicles/ exosomes</p> <p>In-house capabilities are coupled with strategic networks and partnerships for discovery, validation and clinical development of biomarkers.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ü Translational biomarkers (target, mechanism & disease biomarkers) identify the impact of a chemical entity on organs or tissues before a clinical effect is evident. ü Diagnostic biomarkers (predictive, prognostic & resistance biomarkers) empower population stratification and enable decisions for potential regulations and/or personalised interventions. ü Pharmacodynamic biomarkers used in pre- and post-exposure settings may shed light to the extent of target modulation, provide biological proof-of-activity, and inform decision making. 	Greece
<p>Reconstructed metabolic models of various mouse tissues for animal studies (brain, heart)</p> <p>Standardized Meta-database of human protein-protein interactions (PICKLE)</p> <p>Standardized Meta-database of human metabolic models (under development)</p>	Greece
<p>Development of new methods of assessing immunotoxicity epigenetic effects of exposure (in vitro, in vivo)</p>	Luxembourg
<p>In vitro lung, in vitro skin, in vitro liver, in vitro intestine, partly in combinations, *D, chemicals, nanomaterials</p> <p>respiratory sensitization, irritation, cell viability, inflammasome</p>	Luxembourg

<p>In vitro assessment (cell based and protein based assays). In vivo assessment (Zebra fish embryos, C. elegans). Mechanistic endpoints: nuclear receptor reporter gene assays, cell proliferation, competitive binding assays, cellular transport assays, histopathology, reproductive and growth assessment, Organoid models.</p>	Netherlands
<p>https://www.kwrwater.nl/en/projecten/effect-based-water-quality-measurements-with-bioassays/ https://www.kwrwater.nl/en/projecten/qsar-tools-and-bioassays-for-emerging-contaminants-and-transformation-products/</p>	Netherlands
<p>In vitro assessment - Safety and preclinical testing Type of models: in vitro organ specific cell models, iPSC 2D/3D organoids of liver, kidney, mammary gland, heart, pancreas. Type of samples: chemicals, mixtures Mechanistic endpoints: CRISPR-based fluorescent protein reporters for cellular stress responses including oxidative stress, DNA damage, inflammation, mitotoxicity, unfolded protein response, estrogen signaling, cell proliferation. Other info: high throughput microscopy (NL BiImaging).</p>	Netherlands
<p>In silico modeling of different physico-chemical and biological endpoints Type of modes: QSAR models, different chemometrical models for classification and grouping of chemicals (artificial neural networks, genetic algorithm,...), mechanistic models for research of protein-ligand interactions (docking, molecular mechanics, quantum chemistry)</p>	Slovenia
<p>1.) In vitro assessment: Safety and preclinical testing Type of models: in vitro organ specific cell models (cell lines, mostly hepatic cell line of human and fish origin, but any kind of cell lines can be used if available in the lab); 2D/3D spheroids (from permanent liver cell lines - human: e.g., HepG2, C3A, Huh6 etc.; zebrafish: e.g., ZFL. Type of samples: chemicals, mixtures, nanoparticles, environmental samples Mechanistic endpoints: cytotoxicity and particularly genotoxicity; mutagenicity in bacteria - Salmonella typhimurium strains for Ames assay and SOS/umuC assay; some methodological approaches for endocrine disruption Other info: mutagenicity studies performed according to the OECD standards for Good Laboratory Practice (GLP)</p> <p>2.) In vivo assessment using zebrafish embryo model (OECD 236 - Fish Embryo Acute Toxicity (FET) Test) Experiments performed only on Danio rerio embryos since they are not considered as animals (until they feed with yolk). FET complemented with transcriptomic analysis (expression of targeted genes) and assessment of behaviour (Danio Vision system) Type of samples: chemicals, mixtures, nanoparticles, environmental samples Mechanistic endpoints: toxicity</p>	Slovenia
<p>In vitro cell models, in silico models Chemicals, mixtures nuclear receptor reporter gene assays, cell proliferation, cytotoxicity, cell adhesion</p>	Slovenia
<p>In vitro: a) High-Content Screening (HCS)/High-Content Analysis (HCA) by Cell Painting assay, optimized for a variety of cell lines including immune system cells, liver cells, and intestinal cells. Analysis of single chemicals, chemical mixtures, and nanoparticles. Possibility of integrating Cell Painting assay with effect-directed analysis (EDA).</p> <p>In vitro: b) In vitro reporter cell assay for determination of endocrine disruptor activity, AhR activity of chemicals or chemical mixtures using reporter cell assay (CALUX bioassays; AhR, ER, AR, TR). Possibility of integrating in vitro assay with complete GC-MS/Fractionation workflow for effect-directed analysis (EDA).</p>	Sweden
<p>In-vivo models for aquatic and terrestrial systems. Zebrafish OECD 236 and earthworm OECD 11268. Chemical, chemical mixtures, and the possibility of integration with GC-MS/Fractionation workflows.</p> <p>a) Zebrafish: embryotoxic, molecular, behavioral and morphological tests. High-throughput image analyses using video tracking software EthoVision.</p> <p>b) Earthworm: reproduction and mortality.</p>	Sweden
<p>In vitro or in chemico: High-throughput identification of protein targets of individual chemical or mixtures Type of model: any in vitro model, tissue or body fluid. Samples: cells, proteomes and chemicals. Endpoints: unbiased identification of protein targets of chemicals. Unique implementation of TPP method for chemicals at LiU</p>	Sweden
<p>In vivo models for aquatic ecotoxicology. Micro- and macroalgae (freshwater and brackishwater) used to assess ecotoxicity according to OECD and other existing guidelines. Endpoints include growth inhibition, photosynthesis activity, a battery of oxidative status biomarkers, and reproduction (red algae). Bioassays with invertebrate models (Daphnia, Nitocra, rotifers, amphipods) include the following endpoints: behavioral, physiological, biomarkers for detoxification and metabolic activity, DNA adductome, microbiome shifts.</p>	Sweden
<p>Service in developing QSARs, PBK models and machine learning based models for unsupervised or supervised modelling</p>	Sweden

Annex 5b Type of changes that are expected in quantification/determination of toxicity (service 05)

Potential extra investments might occur.	Belgium
Further refinement of the model	Belgium
Potential changes - (1) extension of the portfolio / assay battery, (2) introducing new models (NAMs)	Czech Republic
Further increase in the HTS capacity	Germany
Upgrade	Greece
We anticipate a significant evolution in toxicity quantification and determination services, driven by the increased adoption of advanced machine learning and artificial intelligence methodologies. These advancements will not only enhance the accuracy and efficiency of toxicity predictions but also incorporate interpretability into model development.	Greece
We Expect a significant increase in the adoption of in silico methods for toxicity assessment. These methods are likely to become more refined, accurate, and accepted by regulatory bodies. The integration of big data analytics and artificial intelligence (AI) in in silico toxicology will enhance predictive capabilities. Machine learning models can learn from vast datasets, including chemical structures, biological activity, and clinical data, to predict toxicity more reliably. With the anticipated advances in computational power, in silico models will become more sophisticated, allowing for more complex simulations and accurate predictions. Moreover, there will be an increase in collaborative and open-source platforms that allow researchers from different disciplines to contribute to and access in silico tools, democratizing the field. Additionally, more data harmonization in regulatory standards for in silico methods will take place, with global regulatory bodies working together to set guidelines that facilitate the wider acceptance of these methods.	Greece
The extension of the service to include a wider range of nanomaterials for the in silico toxicity assessment	Greece
Evolution and establishment of state-of-the-art protocols for holistic analysis on preclinical or further on clinical level of various xenobiotic compounds. Establishment of state-of-the-art protocols for ageing and exposome analysis.	Greece
Integration of metabolic with protein network models More cellular and tissue metabolic models reconstructed	Greece
More employees, more facilities, more tissues	Luxembourg
more focus on AOPs	Netherlands
Increase in expertise and infrastructures.	Netherlands
acquiring more staff	Netherlands
More reporters; more target tissues represented; advanced imaging technologies	Netherlands
Performing additional methodologies for the safety assessment (or genotoxicity assessment) of chemicals, nanoparticles. We are already developing NAMs and models as alternatives for animal experiments.	Slovenia
Addition of pipelines to identify targets from species in the environment.	Sweden
Hopefully we can have better and more stable manning	Sweden

Annex 5c Capacity of the services

Country	Description of service	Type of sample	Number of samples per year
Austria	Molecular biology laboratories including tissue culture facilities (hypoxia incubator, a fully equipped radioisotope laboratory and a liquid scintillation counter (Perkin-Elmer)), a CASY cell counter, a state-of-the-art confocal microscope as well as inverse phase contrast microscopes, a four laser Beckman Coulter Cytoflex S flow cytometer, a Biotek multiplate reader, ImageXpress® Pico, an Odyssey® DLx Imager (Immunoblotting), a CryoStar™ NX50 Cryostat, a QuantStudio3 RT-qPCR system, a Agilent TapeStation 4150, a microwave unit (MARS6, CEM, Germany), a Zeenit 700P Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer, and a Mercur Atomic Fluorescence Spectrometer (Analytik Jena).	Real-time Viability assay	0-1000
Austria	Molecular biology laboratories including tissue culture facilities (hypoxia incubator, a fully equipped radioisotope laboratory and a liquid scintillation counter (Perkin-Elmer)), a CASY cell counter, a state-of-the-art confocal microscope as well as inverse phase contrast microscopes, a four laser Beckman Coulter Cytoflex S flow cytometer, a Biotek multiplate reader, ImageXpress® Pico, an Odyssey® DLx Imager (Immunoblotting), a CryoStar™ NX50 Cryostat, a QuantStudio3 RT-qPCR system, a Agilent TapeStation 4150, a microwave unit (MARS6, CEM, Germany), a Zeenit 700P Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer, and a Mercur Atomic Fluorescence Spectrometer (Analytik Jena).	In-vitro testing of chemicals	0-1000
Austria	Molecular biology laboratories including tissue culture facilities (hypoxia incubator, a fully equipped radioisotope laboratory and a liquid scintillation counter (Perkin-Elmer)), a CASY cell counter, a state-of-the-art confocal microscope as well as inverse phase contrast microscopes, a four laser Beckman Coulter Cytoflex S flow cytometer, a Biotek multiplate reader, ImageXpress® Pico, an Odyssey® DLx Imager (Immunoblotting), a CryoStar™ NX50 Cryostat, a QuantStudio3 RT-qPCR system, a Agilent TapeStation 4150, a microwave unit (MARS6, CEM, Germany), a Zeenit 700P Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer, and a Mercur Atomic Fluorescence Spectrometer (Analytik Jena).	Determination of oxidative stress after treatment with various substances	0-1000
Belgium	Lab space (150m ²) for ecotox and in vitro tox testing available equipped with standard up to state-of-the-art equipment.	chemicals	0-1000
Belgium	Lab space (150m ²) for ecotox and in vitro tox testing available equipped with standard up to state-of-the-art equipment.	environmental matrices	0-1000
Belgium	Lab space (150m ²) for ecotox and in vitro tox testing available equipped with standard up to state-of-the-art equipment.	drug compounds	0-1000
Czech Republic	Fully equipped high-end in vitro toxicological laboratories, also ready for iPS models. [As for any high-end research infrastructure - periodic upgrades will be needed]	Individual chemicals	0-1000
Czech Republic	Fully equipped high-end in vitro toxicological laboratories, also ready for iPS models. [As for any high-end research infrastructure - periodic upgrades will be needed]	Environmental, materials	0-1000
Czech Republic	Fully equipped high-end in vitro toxicological laboratories, also ready for iPS models. [As for any high-end research infrastructure - periodic upgrades will be needed]	Human samples	0-1000
Germany	BSL1 and BSL2 labs with cell culture air flow benches, xCelligence system for cell proliferation and behavior studies, 3D culture systems, Cytof (Helios/Hyperion), Cytek Aurora 5L cell culture lab, biochemical lab,	Cellular models	0-1000
Germany	BSL1 and BSL2 labs with cell culture air flow benches, xCelligence system for cell proliferation and behavior studies, 3D culture systems, Cytof (Helios/Hyperion), Cytek Aurora 5L cell culture lab, biochemical lab,	In vivo samples	1.000-10.000
Germany	BSL1 and BSL2 labs with cell culture air flow benches, xCelligence system for cell proliferation and behavior	Microbiome, in vivo	0-1000

	studies, 3D culture systems, Cytof (Helios/Hyperion), Cytex Aurora 5L cell culture lab, biochemical lab,		
Germany	BSL1 and BSL2 labs with cell culture air flow benches, xCelligence system for cell proliferation and behavior studies, 3D culture systems, Cytof (Helios/Hyperion), Cytex Aurora 5L cell culture lab, biochemical lab,	Microbiome in vitro	0-1000
Greece	The main computational resources needed for the service will be required for the screening and are be available from two different settings. Specifically, 2 x HP DL 585 AMD 24-core servers, plus 2 custom AMD Ryzen 80-core + 2x 3090 GPU servers can be assigned to this project.	Virtual chemicals	100.000-1.000.000
Greece	The Laboratory of Toxicology is fully equipped with modern analytical instruments for certifications, preliminary examination instruments and preparation instruments for extraction and purification of samples along with implementation of validated bioanalytical methods. For example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infrastructure for Q-FISH analysis of telomeres (microscope, hood, cell culture incubator etc.) • Chromatographic systems (LC/MS/MS, LC-MS, GC/MS, GC, HPLC) • Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry system (ICP-MS) • Automated high performance liquid chromatography (TOXIS) • fully automated immunoassay systems analysis ELISA spectrophotometers • Molecular techniques systems (PCR, Capillary Electrophoresis) • System immunofluorescence • Refrigerators for sample preservation All the above instrumentation comes along with supporting lab equipment (i.e., centrifuges, incubators etc.)	ü In vitro models	0-1000
Greece	The Laboratory of Toxicology is fully equipped with modern analytical instruments for certifications, preliminary examination instruments and preparation instruments for extraction and purification of samples along with implementation of validated bioanalytical methods. For example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infrastructure for Q-FISH analysis of telomeres (microscope, hood, cell culture incubator etc.) • Chromatographic systems (LC/MS/MS, LC-MS, GC/MS, GC, HPLC) • Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry system (ICP-MS) • Automated high performance liquid chromatography (TOXIS) • fully automated immunoassay systems analysis ELISA spectrophotometers • Molecular techniques systems (PCR, Capillary Electrophoresis) • System immunofluorescence • Refrigerators for sample preservation All the above instrumentation comes along with supporting lab equipment (i.e., centrifuges, incubators etc.)	ü In vivo models	0-1000
Greece	The Laboratory of Toxicology is fully equipped with modern analytical instruments for certifications, preliminary examination instruments and preparation instruments for extraction and purification of samples along with implementation of validated bioanalytical methods. For example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infrastructure for Q-FISH analysis of telomeres (microscope, hood, cell culture incubator etc.) • Chromatographic systems (LC/MS/MS, LC-MS, GC/MS, GC, HPLC) • Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry system (ICP-MS) • Automated high performance liquid chromatography (TOXIS) • fully automated immunoassay systems analysis ELISA spectrophotometers 	ü Ex vivo models	0-1000

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Molecular techniques systems (PCR, Capillary Electrophoresis) • System immunofluorescence • Refrigerators for sample preservation <p>All the above instrumentation comes along with supporting lab equipment (i.e., centrifuges, incubators etc.)</p>		
Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microarray Scanner Agilent Technologies SureScanUltra • qPCR AriaMX Agilent Technologies G8830A • Thermal Cycler Agilent Technologies 8800 PCR • Tape station system Agilent Technologies 2200 • Sample concentrator TECHNE FSC496D • Small Prime Centrifuge refrigerated Centurion Scientific K2015R • Semi-Micro Balances Adam Equipment ABL 225 • Class II Biological Safety Chamber Biobase BSC-1300IIB2-X • Deep freezer (-80 oC) of 700 lt for storage of biological samples 	A549, HepaRG and primary cell cultures	0-1000
Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microarray Scanner Agilent Technologies SureScanUltra • qPCR AriaMX Agilent Technologies G8830A • Thermal Cycler Agilent Technologies 8800 PCR • Tape station system Agilent Technologies 2200 • Sample concentrator TECHNE FSC496D • Small Prime Centrifuge refrigerated Centurion Scientific K2015R • Semi-Micro Balances Adam Equipment ABL 225 • Class II Biological Safety Chamber Biobase BSC-1300IIB2-X • Deep freezer (-80 oC) of 700 lt for storage of biological samples 	Ex-vivo explant 3D mucosa models	0-1000
Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microarray Scanner Agilent Technologies SureScanUltra • qPCR AriaMX Agilent Technologies G8830A • Thermal Cycler Agilent Technologies 8800 PCR • Tape station system Agilent Technologies 2200 • Sample concentrator TECHNE FSC496D • Small Prime Centrifuge refrigerated Centurion Scientific K2015R • Semi-Micro Balances Adam Equipment ABL 225 • Class II Biological Safety Chamber Biobase BSC-1300IIB2-X • Deep freezer (-80 oC) of 700 lt for storage of biological samples 	Rat and zebrafish in-vivo models	0-1000
Greece	<p>ADME-Tox in 3D assays and services in a 3-tier strategy; in silico, in vitro, in vivo (EMA CHMP, FDA Guidance for Industry)</p> <p>3D cell microenvironment via profiling of extracellular vesicles/ exosomes</p> <p>In-house capabilities are coupled with strategic networks and partnerships for discovery, validation and clinical development of biomarkers.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translational biomarkers (target, mechanism & disease biomarkers) identify the impact of a chemical entity on organs or tissues before a clinical effect is evident. • Diagnostic biomarkers (predictive, prognostic & resistance biomarkers) empower population stratification and enable decisions for potential regulations and/or personalised interventions. • Pharmacodynamic biomarkers used in pre- and post-exposure settings may shed light to the extent of target modulation, provide biological proof-of-activity, and inform decision making. 	In vivo	0-1000
Greece	<p>ADME-Tox in 3D assays and services in a 3-tier strategy; in silico, in vitro, in vivo (EMA CHMP, FDA Guidance for Industry)</p> <p>3D cell microenvironment via profiling of extracellular vesicles/ exosomes</p> <p>In-house capabilities are coupled with strategic networks and partnerships for discovery, validation and clinical development of biomarkers.</p>	In vitro	0-1000

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ü Translational biomarkers (target, mechanism & disease biomarkers) identify the impact of a chemical entity on organs or tissues before a clinical effect is evident. ü Diagnostic biomarkers (predictive, prognostic & resistance biomarkers) empower population stratification and enable decisions for potential regulations and/or personalised interventions. ü Pharmacodynamic biomarkers used in pre- and post-exposure settings may shed light to the extent of target modulation, provide biological proof-of-activity, and inform decision making. 		
Luxembourg	All cell culture and immunology infrastructure animal facility stem cell culture	Flow cytometry	1.000-10.000
Luxembourg	All cell culture and immunology infrastructure animal facility stem cell culture	Immune function	0-1000
Luxembourg	Fully established 100m2 cell culture, exposure equipment, FACS, Luminex,	Materials/chemicals	0-1000
Netherlands	Cell culture, C. elegans and zebra fish embryos culture facilities, qPCR, histopathology pipeline, fluorescence microscopes, high throughput staining equipment, incubators at different temperatures.	Cell based Assays	0-1000
Netherlands	Cell culture, C. elegans and zebra fish embryos culture facilities, qPCR, histopathology pipeline, fluorescence microscopes, high throughput staining equipment, incubators at different temperatures.	Protein based assays	1.000-10.000
Netherlands	Cell culture, C. elegans and zebra fish embryos culture facilities, qPCR, histopathology pipeline, fluorescence microscopes, high throughput staining equipment, incubators at different temperatures.	Zebra Fish embryos	0-1000
Netherlands	Cell culture, C. elegans and zebra fish embryos culture facilities, qPCR, histopathology pipeline, fluorescence microscopes, high throughput staining equipment, incubators at different temperatures.	C. elegans	0-1000
Netherlands	still needs to be checked/specified.	to be checked	0-1000
Netherlands	'- high throughput confocal microscopy infrastructure (4+ systems) - >10 fluorescent reporters - > 5 differentiation protocols for target tissues	imaging in 96 or 384 well format	1.000-10.000
Slovenia	High performance computer facility, access to VEGA (national high performance computer cluster)	chemicals with known property	1.000-10.000
Slovenia	High performance computer facility, access to VEGA (national high performance computer cluster)	genomic data	1.000-10.000
Slovenia	<p>Cell cultures and cell biology laboratories CO2 incubators, centrifuges, laminar flow hoods, -80°C freezers, Countess automated cell counter (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, USA), RT PCR system 7300, digester, balance, thermomixers, containers for storage of cell lines in liquid nitrogen etc.</p> <p>Fluorescent microscopy Fluorescent microscope (Nikon Eclipse 8000; Nikon Eclipse Ti), Fluorescent inverted microscope (Olympus IX70) and Microscope Olympus CKX41 and Olympus Provis AX70 fluorescence microscope (Olympus, Tokyo, Japan), EVOS7000 Imaging System-fully automated microscope for fluorescent and colorimetric image acquisition and large data processing, Metafer Metasystems (Scanning and Imaging Platform) all equipped with hardware and software for image analysis.</p> <p>Confocal microscopy Confocal microscopes: Leica TCS SP5 laser scanning confocal microscope mounted on a Leica DMI 6000 CS inverted microscope and confocal microscope Leica SP8 TCS with high-sheet microscopy module. All equipped with hardware and software for image analysis.</p> <p>Flow cytometry, spectrofluorimetry and luminometry MACSQuant analyser 10 flow cytometer (Miltenyi Biotech, Germany), spectral flow cytometer Cytek Aurora (Cytek Biosciences, Fremont, USA). Equipped with software for</p>	chemicals	0-1000

	<p>data analysis.</p> <p>Spectrofluorimetry and luminometry Spectrophotometer SynergyMx, (BioTek (Agilent), USA) and Spectrophotometer NanoDrop, Cytation 5 Cell Imaging Multi-Mode Reader (BioTek (Agilent), USA), and Luminometer Synergy HTX (BioTek (Agilent), USA).</p>		
Slovenia	<p>Cell cultures and cell biology laboratories CO2 incubators, centrifuges, laminar flow hoods, -80°C freezers, Countess automated cell counter (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, USA), RT PCR system 7300, digestorji, balance, thermomixers, containers for storage of cell lines in liquid nitrogen etc.</p> <p>Fluorescent microscopy Fluorescent microscope (Nikon Eclipse 8000; Nikon Eclipse Ti), Fluorescent inverted microscope (Olympus IX70) and Microscope Olympus CKX41 and Olympus Provis AX70 fluorescence microscope (Olympus, Tokyo, Japan), EVOS7000 Imaging System-fully automated microscope for fluorescent and colorimetric image acquisition and large data processing, Metafer Metasystems (Scanning and Imaging Platform) all equipped with hardware and software for image analysis.</p> <p>Confocal microscopy Confocal microscopes: Leica TCS SP5 laser scanning confocal microscope mounted on a Leica DMI 6000 CS inverted microscope and confocal microscope Leica SP8 TCS with light-sheet microscopy module. All equipped with hardware and software for image analysis.</p> <p>Flow cytometry, spectrofluorimetry and luminometry MACSQuant analyser 10 flow cytometer (Miltenyi Biotech, Germany), spectral flow cytometer Cytek Aurora (Cytek Biosciences, Fremont, USA). Equipped with software for data analysis.</p> <p>Spectrofluorimetry and luminometry Spectrophotometer SynergyMx, (BioTek (Agilent), USA) and Spectrophotometer NanoDrop, Cytation 5 Cell Imaging Multi-Mode Reader (BioTek (Agilent), USA), and Luminometer Synergy HTX (BioTek (Agilent), USA).</p>	nanoparticles	0-1000
Slovenia	<p>Cell cultures and cell biology laboratories CO2 incubators, centrifuges, laminar flow hoods, -80°C freezers, Countess automated cell counter (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, USA), RT PCR system 7300, digestor, balance, thermomixers, containers for storage of cell lines in liquid nitrogen etc.</p> <p>Fluorescent microscopy Fluorescent microscope (Nikon Eclipse 8000; Nikon Eclipse Ti), Fluorescent inverted microscope (Olympus IX70) and Microscope Olympus CKX41 and Olympus Provis AX70 fluorescence microscope (Olympus, Tokyo, Japan), EVOS7000 Imaging System-fully automated microscope for fluorescent and colorimetric image acquisition and large data processing, Metafer Metasystems (Scanning and Imaging Platform) all equipped with hardware and software for image analysis.</p> <p>Confocal microscopy Confocal microscopes: Leica TCS SP5 laser scanning confocal microscope mounted on a Leica DMI 6000 CS inverted microscope and confocal microscope Leica SP8 TCS with light-sheet microscopy module. All equipped with hardware and software for image analysis.</p> <p>Flow cytometry, spectrofluorimetry and luminometry MACSQuant analyser 10 flow cytometer (Miltenyi Biotech, Germany), spectral flow cytometer Cytek Aurora (Cytek Biosciences, Fremont, USA). Equipped with software for data analysis.</p> <p>Spectrofluorimetry and luminometry</p>	environmental samples	0-1000

	Spectrophotometer SynergyMx, (BioTek (Agilent), USA) and Spectrophotometer NanoDrop, Cytation 5 Cell Imaging Multi-Mode Reader (BioTek (Agilent), USA), and Luminometer Synergy HTX (BioTek (Agilent), USA).		
Slovenia		in vitro assays	1.000-10.000
Sweden	Fully equipped cell culture facility and GC-MS/FID/Fractionation workflow integrated with cell culture analysis. InCell 2200 HTS system for high-throughput imaging.	a) In vitro HCS imaging platform: single compound or mixtures	0-1000
Sweden	Fully equipped cell culture facility and GC-MS/FID/Fractionation workflow integrated with cell culture analysis. InCell 2200 HTS system for high-throughput imaging.	b) In vitro reporter cell assay using CALUX bioassays (integration with GC-MS/FID/Fractionation system): single compound or mixtures	0-1000
Sweden	Facility for Zebrafish studies. The zebrafish methods investigate embryotoxic effects according to OECD guideline 236, molecular changes on the transcriptome, behavioral alterations, and morphological changes using high-throughput image analyses and the video tracking software EthoVision®. The earthworm tests investigate uptake and effects, including reproduction and mortality (OECD 11268).	Zebrafish (20 user days/y)	0-1000
Sweden	Facility for Zebrafish studies. The zebrafish methods investigate embryotoxic effects according to OECD guideline 236, molecular changes on the transcriptome, behavioral alterations, and morphological changes using high-throughput image analyses and the video tracking software EthoVision®. The earthworm tests investigate uptake and effects, including reproduction and mortality (OECD 11268).	Earthworm (20 user days/y)	0-1000
Sweden	laboratories and exposure facilities	water samples, extracts, or chemicals	0-1000
Sweden	State-of-the art laboratories needed for cell culturing and performance of effect-based research in vitro.	Environmental samples and pure compounds	0-1000

Annex 6 Specification of Service 06 and description of changes and current storage and processing capacity; Biostatistical and/or bioinformatics tools and platforms.

Service description	Described changes	current storage and processing capacity	Country
R- and Python based platforms, integrating dedicated software of our machine operations.	The capacity and skills will increase	Data storage is performed via our UGent Servers. GLORIA Gezondheidsmonitor uses REDCAP, a shared server of the UZ hospital and UGent.	Belgium
	Expansion to cross-omics analysis + other, new biostatistical methodologies will be implemented.	VITO has central data storage facility and connection with high computing power.	Belgium
Harmonization of MS-based targeted- and non-targeted data across cohorts/platforms using in-house methods (R). Data analysis include knowledge-based integration of health endpoints with omics (whole-genome sequencing, metagenomics, proteomics, metabolomics and exposomics). Satellite databases and geo-exposure maps on environmental factors are available for exposome mapping.		internal cloud	Cyprus
FAIR storage and analysis of mutational data. Our tools (14 software tools) and databases (3 databases) can be accessed via this portal: https://loschmidt.chemi.muni.cz/portal/ .	Our domain is very dynamic. New methods are published every month. We need to keep developing our tools to keep them up-to-date.	Hundreds of thousands of mutations; thousands of proteins.	Czech Republic
Galaxy tools for processing of mass spectrometry datasets	Constant development of tools available	ELIXIR Galaxy resources	Czech Republic
DATA INTEGRATION - Alignment of chemical and biological data: protocols (in silico, AI-based) for prospective risk assessment (individual chemicals, realistic mixtures, probabilistic modelling and derivation of toxicological PoD values); personalized/individualized in silico risks predictions for cohort participants from exposome data (current / retrospective assessment of risks - through integration of exposure data with data on toxicology/biological effects)	As there are more open biological and chemical data available (and there is increasing demand on open data use) we expect slight increase in the capacities	Integrated resources at the level of university (Masaryk University) and department RECETOX (own data storage/processing servers)	Czech Republic
We have no Biostatistical facility			Denmark
Bioinformatics tools for annotation of non-targeted HRMS data System biology and artificial Intelligence (AOP) Combination of multiomics dataset (transcriptomics and metabolomics) to exposure data	Increase the number of tools/services available	Server in each physical platforms 500 samples/year	France
Biostatistical/bioinformatics scripts, metadata Automated data evaluation of HTS bioassay data Data integration from transcriptome over proteome to metabolome data, integration of other parameters with omics-data, workflows for single omics, analysis tools for metagenomics, integration of all types of omics and phenotypical data on microbiome samples	Data scientist is not tenured	Sufficient space for all types of analyses at the UFZ servers	Germany
Bulk RNA sequencing Analysis / Visualization pipelines, scRNAseq / snRNAseq	Introduce new state-of-the-art algorithms in our pipelines, Create new	Our current storage and processing capacity for biostatistics and	Greece

<p>Transcriptomics Analysis, Spatial Datasets Analysis (Imaging Mass Cytometry</p> <p>data, seqFISH, Slide-seqV2, Visium H&E / fluorescence, Merfish, Nanostring, MIBI-TOF,</p> <p>Vizgene), Geneset Enrichment Analysis, GO Analysis, Gene Regulatory Networks</p> <p>Systems Biology Pipelines, Multi-omics Integration / harmonization Analysis, Machine</p> <p>Learning, Deep Learning.</p>	<p>novel pipelines</p> <p>to tackle new technologies / modalities</p> <p>In anticipating changes over the next 5 years, we envision a dynamic evolution marked by an expansion of equipment, use cases, and the user base. Technological advancements will likely lead to the incorporation of new and advanced equipment, enhancing our analytical capabilities and supporting the increasing complexity of research demands.</p> <p>The expansion of use cases is expected to be a pivotal aspect of our growth. As we refine and develop cutting-edge tools and platforms, we anticipate diversifying the applications of our services across various biological data types. This expansion will enable us to address a broader range of research questions and industry requirements.</p> <p>Concurrently, the user base is projected to grow as we adapt and expand our services to cater to a more diverse audience. Our commitment to educational programs and thematic tourism initiatives will contribute to attracting new users interested in emerging trends in biostatistics, bioinformatics, and related fields.</p> <p>In summary, the anticipated changes include the expansion of equipment to support advanced capabilities, an increase in the diversity of use cases, and the growth of our user base through targeted educational and outreach initiatives. These changes are aligned with our commitment to staying at the forefront of innovation in biostatistics and bioinformatics.</p>	<p>bioinformatics follows a rather robust model, leveraging both HPC Cloud and Data Center Cloud infrastructures to meet the diverse needs of our research and analytical endeavors. In the HPC Cloud environment, our cluster is powered by 2 NVIDIA DGX A100s, each equipped with 8 x NVIDIA A100 Tensor Core GPUs. This configuration ensures exceptional performance, fully harnessing the capabilities of NVIDIA CUDA-X™ software. The GPUs are adept at handling computationally intensive tasks, making them well-suited for the demanding workloads in biostatistics and bioinformatics. Access to the HPC Cloud is facilitated through the institutional VPN, ensuring secure connectivity to the DGX A100 Cluster. Containerization, specifically through Kubernetes (K8s), is a pivotal aspect of our HPC Cloud service. Jobs are organized and executed using container-based workflows, allowing for efficient management and scalability. The FIFO scheduler ensures a fair and organized execution of jobs, optimizing resource utilization.</p> <p>On the other hand, the Data Center Cloud complements our infrastructure by providing virtual machines (VMs) with access to predefined resources such as vCPUs, RAM, and storage. Operating systems like Ubuntu and Centos are available for users, offering flexibility in choosing environments that suit their specific requirements. Each user is allocated a public IP, and a Jumphost with private VPN service facilitates secure access to the internal network, ensuring data integrity and confidentiality. Both cloud environments contribute to our overall processing capacity, with the HPC Cloud specifically tailored for model training tasks. This comprehensive setup allows us to effectively manage and analyze large volumes of biostatistical and bioinformatic data, ensuring scalability, security, and efficient use of computational resources.</p>	
<p>The study of the exposome is a useful tool in understanding the interplay between genetics and environmental factors in the development of</p>	<p>New more powerful computing infrastructure will enable us to tackle even more challenging ML problems.</p>		<p>Greece</p>

diseases. However, the diversity of input data (e.g. omics data, DNA/RNA sequencing data, water column, feces, urine, whole blood, animal tissue, plant tissue, animal products, etc.) poses difficulties when using traditional analysis techniques. To this end, state-of-the-art Machine Learning (ML) approaches will be utilized and will enable us make predictions that contribute to uncover specific patterns and relationships within exosome data, shedding light on how exosomes respond to different environmental exposures and contributing to a deeper understanding of the exposome's impact on human health. However, the success of the ML approach heavily relies on the quality and representativeness of the exposome data. Below, we outline a focused Machine Learning approach for exosome data analysis: Integration of Exposome Data (integrate different exposome datasets to create a holistic understanding of the interplay between exosomes and environmental exposures), Data Collection and Preprocessing (gather and clean exosome data, as well as metadata related to environmental exposures), Feature Engineering and Importance Analysis (extract relevant features from exosome data and consider incorporating external exposome-related features), Labeling and Task Definition (classification and regression), Model Selection (choose ML models, including Random Forests, Gradient Boosting Models and several Deep Learning Neural Networks), Model Training, Validation and Evaluation (train the selected model and optimize hyperparameters to achieve the best performance as well as generalizability to ensure its applicability to new data), Interpretability and Visualization (use of visualization tools to interpret model predictions and highlight relationships between exosomal cargo and environmental exposures), Biological Interpretation (collaborate with domain experts to interpret the biological significance of identified patterns and relationships to relate the ML findings to the broader understanding of how exosomes respond to environmental exposures). To deal with the demanding computational tasks arising in Big Data Mining, a high-performance cluster will be available for the full time of the project.

The Intelligent Systems Laboratory (ISL) supports basic research in the development of computational models and their effective implementation, aiming at Knowledge Discovery, inference, and Information Retrieval. The core of our research lies in the intersection of the field of Computer

<p>Science with the fields of Mathematics and Statistics, and focuses on applications in Medical Informatics and Bioinformatics, Economics, and industry. More specifically, our research interests include new training algorithms for Artificial Neural Networks and Machine Learning, Development of Clustering Algorithms, Parallel and Distributed Computing, Knowledge Extraction from large data sets, applications in Biomedical technology and in particular in Image and Multimedia Technology, and Text and Image applications. Our research aims to develop algorithms capable of addressing several key challenges associated with Big Data in a fast and efficient manner, leveraging cloud, as well as distributed and parallel computing. The School of Science provides access to a High-Performance Big Data Analytics System, an infrastructure that consists of one Server for Web Services and Applications, one Storage Server with 1 Petabyte of storage and three Servers for Data Analysis each one having 128 CPU cores with 128 GB RAM and two Nvidia A100 having 80GB VRAM. This infrastructure is capable of efficiently tackling the computational complexity of the ML algorithms that will be developed in this project.</p>		
<p>Include description of biostatistical- and bioinformatic pipelines available, including type of data (e.g. epigenetics, transcriptomics, metabolomics), type of analysis, type of methodology, type of tools and platforms.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In house built biostatistical protocol for analysis of Q-FISH results based on in housed developed biobank. The developed system is evolved based on previously published work regarding telomere analysis within the lab. • Open systems pharmacology software (PK-SIM) for simulations of pharmacokinetic and or pharmacodynamic parameters of molecules of interest. PBPK modeling and simulation allows the in vitro-in vivo extrapolation of experimental results into clinical level. • PCR analysis is based on established protocols 	<p>Validate the established protocols. Exploit innovative techniques for data handling and analysis including machine learning and other relative AI tools</p>	<p>Greece</p>
<p>Agilent's GeneSpring for intuitive data analysis and visualization platform for the analysis of transcriptomics, genomics, metabolomics, proteomics and NGS data within a biological context.</p> <p>Agilent's MassHunter Software for Advanced Mass Spectrometry Applications: Data acquisition software for GC/MS and LC/MS which allows straightforward setup and operation of the entire system, while powerful data analysis software and application-specific software tools streamline the analysis workflow for any sample task.</p>	<p>Addition of functions for the pre-processsing and processing of omics data e.g. semi-automated pipeline for the annotation of the metabolites, and data analysis of single-omics data. Development of a user-interface toll for the bioinformatics analysis of the metabolomics data in the framework of exposome followed by exposome data analysis (e.g EWAS, BKMR etc)</p>	<p>High-Performance Computing (HPC)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High powered, networked computing facilities and websevers and teaching/workshop space. • 40TB server shelf hosted by the IT AUTH Center; Consists of several VMs for different projects. • 8 high-end PCs • 6 high-end laptops <p>Parallel Processing: Optimised data processing pipelines for reproducibility</p>

<p>Powerful library management software with extensive curated libraries and databases for Q-TOF instruments facilitates unknowns identification. Finally, simplified software interfaces for mass spectrometry provide access to the power of mass spectrometry to anyone.</p> <p>In house developed R code based on Bioconductor R packages (e.g. xcms, CAMERA, xMSannotator, IPO, limma, MetaboAnalystR, micOmics, minfi...) for the bioinformatics analysis of DNA methylation, transcriptomics, and metabolomics, as well as for the multi-omics analysis of genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics data.</p> <p>In house developed R code based on Bioconductor R packages for the interpretation of the omics results including gene set enrichment analysis (e.g. limma), enrichment analysis of gene clusters (e.g. clusterProfile), annotation (e.g. AnnotationDbi), functional analysis of biological networks (e.g. BioNet, Cytoescape), GO analysis (e.g. GOstats) etc.</p>		<p>and efficiency.</p> <p>Task Scheduling: Implementing efficient task scheduling for parallel execution of multiple processes.</p> <p>Cluster Computing</p> <p>Database Storage: The AUTH IT Center has allocated 2 SAS HDDs with a total storage capacity of 5 TB to cover project requirements. AUTH has purchased has a server with maximum capacity of 40 TB to cover any extra storage requirements that might present themselves over the course of the ongoing projects.</p> <p>Scalability: Systems can scale up or down based on the evolving demands of projects through the IT AUTH Center.</p>	
<p>Bioinformatics focusing on the development of new methodologies and tools Research activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ü Structural bioinformatics ü Computational Systems Biology. ü Biological Big Data Analysis ü Inter- and Intra- Species Protein-Protein Interaction (PPI) networks. ü Network-based drug repurposing and side effect indications. ü Modeling of human disease networks. ü Development of ML and DL algorithms for biological network analysis. <p>Metabolic Engineering - Bioinformatics Main directions: Identification of driver genes, mutations or cellular networks that could represent candidate biomarkers or therapeutic targets. To this end, we focus mainly on the analysis of genomic and transcriptomic data (Next Generation Sequencing methodologies, microarrays) and taking advantage of sophisticated bioinformatics tools, high-dimensional statistics information theory and machine learning we attempt to holistically describe complex biological processes, like cancer manifestation and progression.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linux cluster with 11 PCs (quad-processors, 2GB RAM) • A linux cluster with 8 dual-processor PCs; Memory: 768 MB RAM X 8; Disc: 40GBX7 and 50GBX1 • A linux cluster with 8 single-processor PCs • Memory: 1GB RAM X 8; Disc: 40GBX6, 120GBX1 and 80GBX1 • Free access to an SMP Hewlett-Packard computer with 48 processors • Memory: 36GB RAM; Disc: There are 86 discs, the capacity of each one of them is 36 GB. • System of 16 nodes Fujitsu, each node involves 2 CPUs and each CPU 6 cores. <p>Maestro environment equipped with modules for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Molecular Modelling (MacroModel) • Ligand receptor docking (Glide) • Protein structure prediction (Prime) • Binding site identification (SiteMap) • QM in active site (QSite) • 3D model generation (LigPrep) • Ligand based pharmacophore modeling (Phase) • Core hopping for lead discovery and optimization (CombiGlide) • Cheminformatics (Canvas) 	<p>Greece</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computation of binding affinities (Liaison) • pKa Prediction • ab-initio electronic structure simulations (Jaguar) • ADME predictions (QikProp) • statistical modeling and QSAR (Strike) • Conformer generation for CADD (ConfGen) 	
<p>standardized GC-MS and LC-MS metabolomic data repository standardized metabolomic data normalization methods</p> <p>Reconstructed metabolic models of various mouse tissues for animal studies (brain, heart)</p> <p>Standardized Meta-database of human protein-protein interactions (PICKLE)</p> <p>Standardized Meta-database of human metabolic models (under development)</p> <p>omic data analysis tools (multivariate statistical analysis)</p>	<p>Increase in the metabolomic data available for integrated analysis and investigation</p> <p>Increase in the metabolic and protein network models</p> <p>Integration of metabolic with protein network models for the consistent investigation of multi-omic data</p>	<p>High-power informatics facility @ FORTH/ICE-HT</p> <p>Access to the ELIXIR compute facility HYPATIA</p> <p>3 Windows servers for storage and data procesing</p>	Greece
<p>The LCSB offers a wide variety of bioinformatics and biostatistical platforms_ _____ which are constantly evolving, ranging from metabolomics through to all _____ levels of omics analysis. Overviews are available on the individual group pages_ _____</p> <p>_____ https://www.uni.lu/lcsb-en/research-groups/bioinformatics-core/ _____</p> <p>_____ https://www.uni.lu/lcsb-en/research-groups/biomedical-data-science/ _____</p> <p>_____ https://www.uni.lu/lcsb-en/research-groups/digital-medicine/ _____</p> <p>_____</p> <p>https://www.uni.lu/lcsb-en/research-groups/environmental-cheminformatics/</p> <p>https://www.uni.lu/lcsb-en/research-groups/systems-ecology/</p> <p>https://elixir-luxembourg.org/</p>		<p>The University of Luxembourg (UL) operates a large academic High Performance Computing (HPC) facility since 2007, which remains one of the key HPCs in the country, offering a cutting-edge research infrastructure to Luxembourg public research while serving as edge access to the Euro-HPC Luxembourg supercomputer operated by LuxProvide focused at serving the private sector. The UL HPC facility focused on the development of large computing power combined with huge data storage capacity to accelerate the research performed in intensive computing and large-scale data analytics (Big Data). Currently, Iris (Rpeak=1071 TFlops) and Aion (Rpeakk=1884 TFlops) are the two production systems sharing the same High Performance Storage solutions. Iris is a Dell/Intel supercomputer which contains x86-64 Intel-based compute nodes, featuring 3 types of computing resources: "regular" nodes, Dual Intel Xeon Broadwell or Skylake CPU (28 cores), 128 GB of RAM; "gpu" nodes, Dual Intel Xeon Skylake CPU (28 cores), 4 Nvidia Tesla V100 SXM2 GPU accelerators (16 or 32 GB), 768 GB RAM; "bigmem" nodes: Quad-Intel Xeon Skylake CPU (112 cores), 3072 GB RAM. Aion is an Atos/Bull/AMD</p>	Luxembourg

		supercomputer which contains x86-64 AMD-based compute nodes, consisting of "regular" nodes, 2 AMD Epyc ROME 7H12 CPU (64 cores), 256 GB of RAM. More details are available at https://hpc.uni.lu/ .	
DIAMONDS Platform: https://diamonds.tno.nl/ EXCITE platform for collection, storage and analyses of sensor data		to be determined	Netherlands
Highly capable infrastructures using in house R scripts.	Increased knowledge and infrastructures.	Terabytes, if large amounts of storage space are needed this can be arranged by the University Service. Virtual machines are running routinely in the lab. If needed a unique virtual machine can be arranged for specific processes. Biostatistics for large data sets are processed using R.	Netherlands
https://www.kwrwater.nl/en/onderzoek/enabling-technologies-en/hydroinformatics https://www.kwrwater.nl/en/actueel/is-there-more-than-just-data/			Netherlands
Bioinformatics pipeline for CyTOF analysis and for transcriptomics analysis		Dedicated server to handle CyTOF data and Sigma 2 infrastructure (national infrastructure) for NGS data. Compliance with GDPR regulations	Norway
numerical representation of genomic and proteomic data, chemometrical analysis of data including machine learning software	personal changes are possible	Access to high performance computer clusters, the storage and computer time is allocated to users accordingly to current needs	Slovenia
We analyze (for our colleagues from the fields of environmental sciences, life science and medicine) different kinds of omics data (incl. all of the abovementioned types, e.g., epigenetic, transcriptomic and metabolomic data. We analyze them with basic statistical approaches (e.g. data summarization, estimating distribution parameters), parametrical and non-parametrical statistical tests (e.g. for differences in distribution), and most often with machine learning methods. We use machine learning to build predictive models for single and multiple targets, and also to estimate the relevance of individual variables (predictors). In this way, we can identify potential biomarkers for different (and possibly multiple) targets (health/clinical outcomes) in different kinds of exposome data.	We expect strong growth, both in volume of services provided and in the number/ FTE of personnel providing them.	The Dept. of Knowledge Technologies of the Jozef Stefan Institute has its own computing equipment, comprising CPU servers, GPU servers, and disk arrays, with a purchase value of approx 0.8 Mio EUR. Of this, equipment for 200 kEUR has been purchased in the last two years. Overall, the CPU servers have more than 700 cores and the GPU servers have tens of GPU cards with more than 110000 CUDA cores. Storage capacity exceeds 2Pb.	Slovenia
Advanced bioinformatics tools data analysis, multi-omics data integration, and MS data association to health outcomes. Harmonization of MS-based targeted- and non-targeted data across cohorts/platforms using in-house methods (R, Phytion). Data analysis includes knowledge-based integration of health endpoints with omics (whole-genome sequencing, metagenomics, proteomics, metabolomics and exposomics). The portfolio includes statistical workflows using dimensionality-reduction techniques, pathway-based integration and machine learning for predictive modeling.		University's Linux-based server provides TB-level storage and high processing capacity. Data processing capacity will depend on the level of biological interpretation required. Current capacity: possibility to identify potential biomarkers and generate hypotheses in small-scale projects (up to 500 samples/month)	Sweden
Bioinformatics for proteomics		National Supercomputer Center at Linköping University (NSC) is a provider of leading edge national supercomputing resources. We provide a wide range of	Sweden

		<p>high performance computing and data services to members of academic institutions throughout Sweden and abroad.</p>	
<p>Human Exposome Assessment Platform (HEAP) is a PaaS developed by the HEAP EU-funded project. It enables heterogeneous exposome data management and analysis, including flexible definition of metadata, implementation of bioinformatics pipelines, Git integration, Machine Learning with world-leading feature store, IoT interface and sharing of data and analysis tools, including reusability of the code. The platform is integrated with R Studio for biostatistics analyses that can be integrated into analysis pipelines. At the moment, the following pipelines are available:</p> <p>1- HPV-Meta: for detection of HPV in RNA/DNA 2- Bio-pipeline: metagenomics analysis of DNA/RNA 3- ML for HPV vaccination group detection 4- Chemical Exposome Pipeline to identify chemical exposome components from samples collected by a wearable exposometer 5- DNA methylation preprocessing and quality control for identifying features associated with certain exposures and accelerated or decelerated epigenetic ageing.</p> <p>The above pipelines are developed and used by the HEAP project consortium.</p>	<p>In the beginning, the service will be provided by the HEAP platform implemented on KI premises. It is possible to scale the service by increasing storage and computation capacities and creating a federated HEAP network with instances in different institutions for sharing data and knowledge.</p>	<p>DELL cluster, 24 machines, 56 CPUs each, ~4TB memory, ~2PB storage Software platform: HopsWorks (Hadoop-based platform), customised for exposome research and scalable to 8 GPUs (on demand) Secure and distributed storage of data Stratified data management and flexible metadata design for datasets Integration with R Studio Machine Learning framework IoT interface</p>	<p>Sweden</p>

Annex 7 Description of service 07 Databases and exposure maps on environmental factors and expected changes that are foreseen in the coming 5 years.

Please describe in the open text field below the service currently offered regarding databases and exposure maps on environmental factors at your institute. Include type of environmental factor available, type of maps (incl geographical area (e.g. region, country, EU wide, etc)), type of platforms used.	Please describe the changes that might occur	Country
<p>___air quality indicators (PM2.5, PM10, NO2, O3; regional area: Wallonia)</p> <p>___air quality index per school (regional area: Wallonia) à dashboard (ArcGIS)</p> <p>___soil quality indicators (metals; regional area: Wallonia)</p> <p>___radon in dwellings (regional area: Wallonia)</p> <p>___transport noise indicators (regional area: Wallonia)</p> <p>___pesticide use on crop (regional area: Wallonia) --> Web App builder (ArcGIS)</p> <p>___pesticide exposure metric (regional area: Wallonia)</p> <p>___pesticide-free zones around sensitive population sites (regional area: Wallonia)</p> <p>___industrial sites (regional area: Wallonia)</p> <p>___contaminated sites (regional area: Wallonia)</p> <p>___population data per ha (per sex, per age; regional area: Wallonia) --> Web App builder (ArcGIS)</p> <p>___sensitive population sites (regional area: Wallonia) --> Web App builder (ArcGIS)</p> <p>___socio-economic and social vulnerability indicators (regional area: Wallonia)</p>	<p>To hire data managers, bioinformaticians and researchers to update databases and maps, develop exposure metrics, spatial epidemiology and analysis of environmental burden of disease</p>	<p>Belgium</p>
<p>Terrascope EOplaza infrastructure:</p> <p>* platform using Sentinel earth observation and meteorological data to give output data about crops & environment (biophysical parameters, growth, crop calendar, ...), biomass changes, habitat maps</p> <p>* platform based on Sentinel 5P data with as output daily to yearly NO2, CO, CH2O, CH4, SO2 measurements on a resolution of 3.5 x 5.5 km2 at global scale</p> <p>Other databases:</p> <p>* maps about detailed land use and environmental aspects (water, air quality, geo cond, urban & green env)</p>	<p>Expansion of existing databases, inclusion of other and external datasets.</p>	<p>Belgium</p>
<p>GLORIA is very extensive. For more information, please contact Prof. Marthe De Boevre</p>		<p>Belgium</p>
<p>Effect of mutations on proteins</p>	<p>New data</p>	<p>Czech Republic</p>
<p>Data Bases: Air Pollutants, Drinking Water Elements, Drinking Water Pollutants, Green Space Noise, Blue Space, Covering Denmark</p>	<p>Including more years of exposure</p>	<p>Denmark</p>
<p>AQ sensors data network (Messinia and Attica Greece)</p>	<p>Increase AQ sensors network</p>	<p>Greece</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type of environmental Factor: Concentrations of pollutants such as particulate matter (PM10, PM2.5, PM1), NO2, SO2, O3, Noise, temperature, socio-economic • Geographical area: Regional and Local • Type of maps: Spatial distribution maps • Platforms used: Geographic Information System (GIS), ArcMap 10.7.1, Agent Based Modelling – ABM • Database of physical activity maps and lifestyle from ? 1000 children for understanding obesogenic behaviors using a TRL8 mHealth app / dashboard in west, east and suburban Thessaloniki, Athens from Greece including ambient information on the location of eating spots and sports/fitness spots. • Database of women in Thessaloniki (> 200 pregnant, high risk, metabolic substrate) including information on eating spots close to home, efood orders, physical activity, HR, lifestyle using an mHealth app (TRL7) • Database of > 4000 subjects in the US for mental health assessment using advanced ML with small cognitive tasks taking into account socioeconomic factors, consumer behavior, pollutants from where they live). 		<p>Greece</p>

<p>Hydrogeochemical data from areas around the Power Public Company plants in the northern part of the Greece and other high-exposure areas (as Lavrio city), at the Mining and Metallurgical Engineering School, NTU Athens.</p>	<p>increased amount of data, integrated data with environmental and biological factors, development of online platforms (would like to), coverage of more areas/regions</p>	<p>Greece</p>
<p>Access to data portals of ASI satellite missions (COSMO-SkyMed, PRISMA and SAOCOM) ASI is provides access to three separate data portals, one for each of the following three operational missions:</p> <p>1) Mission COSMO-SkyMed/SAR X-band Coverage: Worldwide Who can access: Institutional users Permitted use: All (except commercial) Associated fees: See condition on the ASI site</p> <p>2) Mission PRISMA/Optical Hyperspectral Coverage: Worldwide Who can access: All Users Permitted use: R&D only Associated fees: Free of charge</p> <p>3) Mission SAOCOM/SAR L-band Coverage: Europe Who can access: All Users Permitted use: R&D only Associated fees: Free of charge</p> <p>Services currently offered: (i) search and find data on the catalog; (ii) select and order the data from the archive; (iii) task new acquisitions</p> <p>Access is regulated by the published data policy, one for each mission.</p> <p>How to access the data General description of each mission and detailed instructions on how to register and access the data can be found at: 1) COSMO-SkyMed: https://www.asi.it/scienze-della-terra/cosmo-skymed/ 2) PRISMA: https://www.asi.it/scienze-della-terra/prisma/ 3) SAOCOM: https://www.asi.it/en/earth-science/saocom/</p>	<p>Data from the three missions will be made available from one portal. Changes on PRISMA Policy, more open.</p>	<p>Italy</p>
<p>PubChemLite for Exposomics: database of chemicals relevant for exposure DOI 10.5281/zenodo.5995885 ___NORMAN Suspect List Exchange (NORMAN-SLE): database of environmental ___ _____chemicals: https://www.norman-network.com/nds/SLE/ ___ ___ Disease maps via ELIXIR-LU: ___ ___ https://elixir-luxembourg.org/services/catalog/minerva/ ___ ___ MassBank Europe: https://massbank.eu/MassBank/ _____</p>	<p>Potential for new developments, including data platforms for _____environmental data; discussions are underway but early stage</p>	<p>Luxembourg</p>
<p>Occupational exposure databases: ART, DermoExpoDB Occupational exposure models: ARTS, dART, NEQ, ECEL Are job exposure matrices relevant?</p>	<p>newly developed databases and models likely will become available</p>	<p>Netherlands</p>
<p>Geo-spatial modelling of chemical and biological exposures</p>	<p>Increase of expertise and infrastructure quality</p>	<p>Netherlands</p>
<p>We will record environment and lifestyle factors such as household composition, work, contact with animals, physical activity, sleep, stress, smoking, alcohol, medication, dietary habits etc. We can also link this to home address or donation centre location.</p>	<p>the database will grow in sample size and be enriched with data as well as linking possibilities</p>	<p>Netherlands</p>
<p>Exposome data platform; allows stakeholders to see and interact with Geospatially resolved Exposome data (exposome surfaces). These can be viewed on a map and can be linked to address data, for example those available in epidemiological cohorts. Currently available</p>	<p>Expect to increase the number of services that will be made available and also improve the user interface.</p>	<p>Netherlands</p>

data is generated primarily as part of the EU EXPANSE project. All surfaces cover EU-27. Linkage of coordinates to the surface data is done in a secure way.	Also expect to incorporate federated data storage system.	
With GECCO we have 100+ environmental exposure variables available for the whole of NL. GECCO is a Dutch infrastructure to support researchers to study the relation between environmental characteristics and health. It is funded by NWO and partly by Exposome-NL, where it is embedded.	Embedding in wider Exposome-nl data platform	Netherlands
GIS, Slovenia, Europe	we shall further enlarge the platform for the integration of environmental data and human data	Slovenia
air pollution (region)		Slovenia

Annex 8 Specification of Service 08 FAIR cataloging and description of changes that might occur in this service in coming 5 years.

service currently offered regarding FAIR cataloging at your institute.	Changes that might occur in FAIR cataloging	Country
Data management plans cannot be disclosed, all servers at UGent are coded	There will be an increase in both capacity and technical interconnections.	Belgium
<p>FAIR Data Hub at VITO</p> <p>The data hub builds further on the core platform and governance structure built in the HBM4EU project and used further in the Horizon Europe Partnership for the Assessment of Risks of Chemicals (PARC). The core platform was a key enabling tool in carrying out the high-quality research on chemicals exposure and health in HBM4EU, using harmonized and quality controlled HBM datasets from more than 20 different countries.</p> <p>VITO operates the PEH dataplatform: The Personal Exposure and Health (PEH) Data Platform can be used to upload, share and reuse harmonized human biomonitoring data from multiple HBM studies at individual level in a GDPR compliant way. Users, both data providers wanting to share their data, and data users wanting to use data hosted in the platform, get access to the platform service by signing a Protocol which defines their obligations and rights when depositing or using the individual personal data, as well as the data governance and access procedure. Its multilateral nature allows to have coordinated access to extracts of harmonized data from multiple studies in the platform, while respecting the data minimization principles. Tools are available for data harmonization and data validation prior to uploading the data.</p> <p>In the coming year the platform will be transformed to a FAIR data platform, and thus allow users to deposit their data as FAIR data. It will be extended with tools for harmonised calculations of derived variables and summary statistics.</p>	Current data platform will be transformed into a FAIR data platform in the coming year.	Belgium
We have a data catalogue (https://aineistokatalogi.fi/catalog) which includes data sources from THL in a standardized meta data format following the upcoming requirements of EHDS.	Further technical development of the catalogue functions	Finland
The Laboratory of Hydromechanics and Environmental Engineering supports research and teaching in the topics of environmental engineering of water systems, sustainability and climate change, climate hazards and extreme events, smart water systems, environmental and ecological informatics and the study of the Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystem Nexus. It conducts modeling studies of the physical-chemical and biological status of water bodies and has run funded research on lake Karla and Pineios River in Thessaly, but also on other natural ecosystems. The lab focuses on biodiversity	More data are expected to be incorporated in the SustainGraph (https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fenvs.2022.1003599/full?trk=public_post_main-feed-card_feed-article-content) from various different sources.	Greece

<p>modeling studies both in the urban and rural environment with data from EIONET Central Data Repository and the Urban Atlas Copernicus satellite data. It uses machine learning and clustering techniques to provide spatiotemporal heat maps related to various risks. It also studies Nature-Based Solutions and their effects on floods, droughts and extreme events. A significant part of the research conducted focuses on sustainability and UN SDGs, climate change adaptation and mitigation measures, participatory processes and living lab setup for stakeholder engagement, socio-economic vulnerability assessment, climate hazards with a focus on extreme heat and citizen science activities and policies. The lab was a leading part of the team that won recently the first place award in the EUvsVirus Hackathon on detecting the SARS-Cov-2 virus in sewage, through the Sewers4Covid project. The lab includes a large team of over 20 researchers and coordinates or participates in a large number of EU funded projects, such as: ARSINOE, NATALIE, BIONEXT, MI-TRAP, NEXOGENESIS, NEXUSNET, MAGO, LOTUS, SIM4NEXUS, SMS and others. For the purpose of the ARSINOE project (coordinated by UTH Prof. Chrysi Laspidou--director of LHEE), an extensive Knowledge Graph has been developed--the SustainGraph--that collects data from a variety of sources, including Third Party databases and stores them in a visual database. SustainGraph has been named a success story from the Commission and would be a great way to provide a visual way of tracking the progress of the exposome targets and indicators and the evolution of them at national and regional levels – all together in one holistic framework. This can be worked to be the basis for the systemic representation of knowledge related to the exposome, enabling the collection and representation of data while overcoming data management barriers.</p>		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wearable measures of physical activity, HR and food pictures from > 5000 children in European schools, Algorithms for measuring steps in Geohashes for having an idea of a community behavioural profile in Greece and Sweden, Questionnaires, brain imaging biomarkers and light cognitive tasks from > 4000 subjects in the US for diagnosing anxiety, depression suicidality. > 700 citizens in Sykies municipality with HER data and wearable sensors data for CVD screening in a municipality level. Algorithms for ECG, lung sounds AI/DL based analytics for arrhythmia detection and respiratory function assessment. • Open data repository based on the Dataverse software. • Various open access FTP servers hosted by the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki <p>• Our Department is currently hosting multiple</p>	<p>With the rapid advance of recent technologies like Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning as well as the latest improvements in software development methodologies and frameworks, Our IT team is committed to the constant improvement and expansion of its internal infrastructure, equipment and tools.</p>	<p>Greece</p>

scientific data repositories which provide public access to datasets produced from a variety of EU-funded projects. The laboratory also has its own Github account where a number of tools, models and open-source code can be accessed.		
LCSB/ELIXIR-LU being part of IMI-FAIRplus project (https://fairplus-project.eu) developed FAIRification framework, FAIR Cookbook (DOI: 10.1038/s41597-023-02166-3) and FAIR catalog (DOI: 10.1038/s41597-023-02258-0). These tools, resources and knowhow have been used in several IMI, IHI and other EU projects (e.g. SysCID, BIOMAP, ImmUniverse, ImSAVAR, IDERHA, EPND) and national FNR funded projects (e.g. NCERPD, HeartMed, PREADAPT etc.). We have expertise in development of research Data Management Plan and performing Data Process Impact Assessment (DPIA)	..	Luxembourg
MOLGENIS metadata catalogue + FAIR 'omes' MOLGENIS data warehouse	expansion. We now cover rare disease, cancer, exposome, child cohorts, biobanks	Netherlands
Transcriptomics and imaging data basing – metadata	Advancements in image data repositories with standard metadata linkage. Advancements in transcriptomics data repositories with standard metadata linkage	Netherlands
Chemical exposure data from MoBa and NEB are partly available at the IPCHEM, HBM4EU dashboard and PEH platform established in HBM4EU.	Addition of more data	Norway
We are and will be engaged in analyzing different kinds of exposure data and relating such data to relevant with a variety of machine learning and artificial intelligence tools, following the principles of Open Science. We develop ontologies for describing data and data analysis tools, processes and results. We use ontologies for ontology-base data integration, to annotate data, and make them FAIR. We also believe that the results of data analysis (e.g. predictive models) should be FAIR and work in that direction.	We expect strong growth both in volume of services provided and in the number /FTE of personnel providing them.	Slovenia